

RESO

WP2-RP01: RESO Data Catalogue

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Regional Energy System Operator (RESO) Smart Local Energy System (SLES) design is funded by the government's Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy (BEIS) as part of the Industrial Strategy Challenge Fund (ISCF) ([link](#)).

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1.0.3 A few additional datasets, and change of licence to CC-BY 4.0 to be hosted on Zenodo	Dr Joe Day, Dr Grant Wilson	2021-05-20

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West Midlands Regional Energy Systems Operator (RESO)

RESO Data catalogue

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Executive Summary

This report has been created for the Regional Energy Systems Operator (RESO) project where Coventry City Council is a partner organisation. The consortium of RESO project partners also includes West Midlands Combined Authority, Energy Capital, Transport for West Midlands, Enzen, PlacesInCommon, Camirus, University of Birmingham, University of Warwick, Electron, Wattify, Cadent and Western Power Distribution (WPD).

The RESO project has benefitted significantly from having access to non-public data from four main sources, Coventry City Council as the local authority, Cadent as the Gas Distribution Network operator, Western Power Distribution as the Electrical Distribution Network Operator, and Engie as the Heat Network Operator.

This has provided a rich source of data for the RESO project, but has also shown the challenges of interoperability between different sources of data and the gaps of knowledge and areas of uncertainty that exist. It also indicates that much of the richness in analysis comes from data that is not at the moment open or easily interoperable, and this needs to change. The value of understanding local energy systems comes from a multi-vector approach, and from appropriately detailed data both in geography and in time series. The RESO project will continue to advocate for open data sets but also recognise that data providers are themselves on a journey from having data that was internally useful, to providing data that has different requirements from being more open and also on interoperability. Data is fundamental not only to the analysis of local energy systems but would also be critical for a functioning local energy market. This is an area the RESO project will continue to explore through the project timeframe to the end of 2021.

This catalogue has been prepared for the RESO project to present the datasets used by Work package 2 (WP2) to inform the design objectives of the other work packages (specifically WP3 and WP4). The 145 datasets have been categorised into one of eight categories: electricity (35), gas and heat (29), transport (21), multi-vector (18), climate and weather (8), buildings (9), geography (10) and socioeconomic (15) – their relative amounts are shown in Figure 1. This means each dataset can be given an unambiguous shorthand code for use within the project, in the form UOBDC-CATEGORY-NNN (where NNN is a 3-digit numerical code starting at 001).

FIGURE 1 – THE NUMBER OF DATASETS IN THIS CATALOGUE UNDER EACH CATEGORY.

They have also all been presented in tables which adhere to the Dublin Core metadata standard as recommended by the Energy Data Taskforce¹. The ‘Description’ entry has some information on what can be derived directly from the data as well as the use cases of the dataset to provide further insight. Furthermore, a standard vocabulary is used throughout the ‘Subject’ row in order to help readers quickly determine the granularity (both in time and geographically) and focus of a dataset. The ‘Identifiers’ and ‘Rights’ also indicate our understanding of these areas. This is important because even if the data itself not publicly available, its metadata should be presumed open, in line with Energy Data Taskforce recommendations.

It should be noted that this list is not exhaustive and should be viewed as an evolving document as more data becomes available. Also, there are many datasets that although interesting, were not of immediate importance to the RESO project and were therefore not included in this catalogue. This updated version of the internal RESO project Data Catalogue has been made public, with the ethos of: ‘if the RESO project (or a similar smart local energy system project) was starting again, what would be helpful as an initial point of reference to build qualitative and quantitative knowledge of its local energy system?’

Special thanks go to Cadent and WPD (Wattify Limited and the WPD Network Innovation Team) who have supported the RESO project with further knowledge transfer from prior or ongoing [Network Innovation projects](#) mostly publicly available in pdf. Thanks also to Engie, MCS, BEIS and Transport for West Midlands for sharing data with the RESO project.

The authors would also like to express gratitude to the Energy Systems Catapult’s [Common Energy Datasets \(CDaS\)](#) which was produced in a similar spirit and has served as a useful starting point that has been cited in the description of some of these datasets. Finally, it is timely that this work has occurred during the launch of Icebreaker One’s [Open Energy Data Search](#) platform. Their mission to aid low carbon decision making through an improved energy data landscape is one shared by ourselves.

¹ <https://es.catapult.org.uk/reports/energy-data-taskforce-report/>

1 BACKGROUND

In 2019 the UK was the first country to pass a net zero emissions target into law. Being net zero by 2050 underpins the UK's commitment to the UNFCCC COP 21 2016 Paris Agreement to keep global warming under 2°C. However, the cumulative amount of emissions is ultimately the driver of climate change, e.g. it is the amount of CO₂ emissions released on the way to net zero rather than the net zero target itself which is the important factor. Nonetheless, the net zero target by 2050 provides a singular and defined target whereby the UK will no longer be adding to the global total of Green House Gas emissions (from a territorial emissions perspective).

The Regional Energy System Operator (RESO) project is a detailed design project partially funded by Innovate UK from January 2020 to December 2021 with a focus on the decarbonisation of Coventry City Council local authority area. The aim of the RESO project is to create a cleaner, lower cost energy system for Coventry and the West Midlands region that maximises economic opportunities in clean growth and future mobility. Its aim is to help deliver local policy objectives towards the UK's net zero emissions in 2050 framed by the Paris agreement. The timeframe for focus for the RESO project is however 2032, a timeframe when significant decarbonisation must have already taken place within the Coventry City Council local authority area in order to put it on a trajectory appropriate for the UK's 2050 national ambitions.

An aim of the RESO project's detailed design methodology for Coventry is to demonstrate its relevance to the wider region by having an approach for other local authority areas that might be repeatable. Within the overall RESO project context of creating a detailed energy system design, the Energy Informatics Group at the University of Birmingham provides input on data foundations with a particular focus on energy data. Furthermore, data relating to CO₂ emissions is a vital piece of the puzzle of information required to design a local clean energy system. The benefit of this data includes disaggregating the emissions by sector and energy vector at the start of the energy system transition, which is important to inform the scale of the changes required. It also provides knowledge to create an emissions target pathway, so that a future smart local energy system can be quantitatively assessed against this goal.

Finally, it should be noted for the purposes of the RESO project, only emissions of CO₂ are considered (which accounted for 81% of UK greenhouse gas emissions in CO₂ equivalent in 2018²). Local level point source information on other greenhouse gas and air pollutant emissions are available through the National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory ³. Furthermore, the only CO₂ emissions accounted for are those produced in the area from the use or combustion of the following energy vectors: electricity, natural gas, liquid fuels (e.g. petrol, diesel, heating oil) and solid fuels (e.g. coal) and across the following sectors: large industrial installations, industrial, commercial, domestic, agriculture, road transport, railways and internal waterways. Land Use Land Use Change and Forestry and cement

² https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/862887/2018_Final_greenhouse_gas_emissions_statistical_release.pdf

³ <https://naei.beis.gov.uk/data/map-large-source>

production are also excluded in line with equity principles of the Paris Agreement⁴ as detailed in the Tyndall centre methodology. In addition, consumption based emissions (e.g. from imported manufactured goods) are not included in the pathway values.

⁴ <https://carbonbudget.manchester.ac.uk/reports/E08000026/print/>

2 CONTEXT FOR COVENTRY

The city of Coventry is an administrative centre and metropolitan borough in England with an area of 98.64 km². By land use, the local authority is 58% built on, 17% green urban, 25% farmland and <1% attributed to natural area⁵. According to the Office for National Statistics (ONS) estimates, the population of Coventry in mid-2018 was about 366,800⁶ with the Gross Value Add per capita standing at £24,890⁷ (ONS 2017). According to the Local Land and Property Gazetteer there are 145,500 domestic dwellings in Coventry and BEIS 2018 figures state 12.1% of households are in fuel poverty compared to the national average of 10.2%⁸.

The RESO project boundary includes 201 LSOAs. This is made up of the 195 Coventry local authority area LSOAs (green area in Figure 2), and six additional LSOAs, Warwick 005G, Rugby (004D, 001C), Nuneaton & Bedworth (015C, 015D, 015E), the yellow areas in Figure 2. However, for the energy consumption and carbon emission analysis, these additional LSOAs areas were excluded since BEIS publishes the relevant statistics at a local authority level and the additional LSOA contributions will be small compared to the Coventry local authority area.

FIGURE 2 - MAP OF THE 201 LSOAs OF INTEREST FOR THE RESO AREA. THE 195 COVENTRY LOCAL AUTHORITY LSOAs ARE IN GREEN AND THE 6 LSOAs OUTSIDE THE LOCAL AUTHORITY BOUNDARY ARE IN YELLOW

The following sections detail datasets and information that RESO has found helpful to understand its existing and in some cases future energy and emissions. Our hope is that other projects may find this data catalogue to be useful too.

⁵ <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover>

⁶ <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationestimates/bulletins/annualmidyearpopulationestimates/mid2019>

⁷ <https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/grossvalueaddedgva/bulletins/regionalgrossvalueaddedbalanceduk/1998to2017#interactive-map-gross-value-added-gva-per-head-for-nuts3-local-areas-1998-to-2017>

⁸ <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/sub-regional-fuel-poverty-data-2020>

3 ELECTRICITY

3.1 UOBDC-ELEC-001: WPD Distribution Substations Coventry

Title	Extended CSV - WPD Distribution Substations Coventry - RESO_WPD_CSV_05_v1
Creator	WPD
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; Asset Data; Distribution Substation Level; Geospatial Data; Point Layer
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-001: This dataset contains information for approximately 2000 distribution substations in the RESO area and its periphery. While a complete metadata description for column headers is available on the ESC page, the attributes given for each distribution substation are as follows: name and asset number, OS grid reference (i.e. a spatial location which can be converted to an easting/northing for use in QGIS), upstream primary substation name and asset number, asset number of the 11 or 6.6 kV feeder (known as HV feeders) to which the distribution substation is connected, asset type and type ID, nameplate capacity (in kVA and estimated where the asset is not a WPD asset), whether it serves the RESO area, total customers within the RESO area and number of private connections.
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	csv
Identifier	https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/e73qj/extended-csv-wpd-distribution-substations-coventry-reso_wpd_csv_05_v1
Source	WPD operational systems
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	28 primary substations: 930025, 930026, 930027, 930028, 930029, 930030, 930031, 930032, 930033, 930034, 930035, 930037, 930038, 930039, 930040, 930041, 930042, 930043, 930044, 930045, 930046, 930047, 930049, 930050, 930055, 930061, 930079, 930083.
Rights	WPD, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project. A large proportion of the same data is, or has since been made available online via WPDs Energy Data Hub, accessible under standard WPD terms of use. See also UOBDC-ELEC-004.

3.2 UOBDC-ELEC-002: WPD Primary Half-hourly Monitoring Data

Title	Unprocessed half-hourly operational time series data for electrical primary substations
Creator	Dave Phillips (Wattify) and WPD Innovation Team
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; Primary Substation Level; HV Feeder Level; Half-Hourly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-002: Half-hourly raw operational data for the 28 primary level substations covering the RESO geographical area. Data is in a pseudo local time format as it's not in either a UTC format, or in a strictly local time format with British Summer Time.</p> <p>This WPD monitoring data, provided uniquely for the RESO project under terms set out on the web page, contains half-hourly measurements for the power and current of WPD assets from July 2017 to February 2020. The apparent power (in MVA) is given for each primary substation transformer (usually 2 per primary), as well as the real power (in MW) and reactive power (in MVAR) for some substations. While each HV feeder coming off the primary (usually 6-12 per substation) has a current measurement (in A).</p> <p>The data has been cleaned (potential errors such as spikes or zeroes flagged) for 28 primary substations. Specific HV feeders, have yet to be error checked, but can be cleaned on an ad-hoc basis as the project proceeds with area deep-dives. Finally, a separate document has been produced by WP2 has outlined the parsing process, as well as providing feedback to WPD (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4607270)</p>
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	csv
Identifier	https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/29qd0/UOBDC-flagged-halfhourly-wpd-electric-asset-monitoring
Source	WPD operational systems
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	28 primary substations: 690014, 930025, 930026, 930027, 930028, 930029, 930030, 930031, 930032, 930033, 930034, 930035, 930037, 930038, 930039, 930040, 930041, 930042, 930043, 930044, 930045, 930046, 930047, 930049, 930050, 930055, 930061, 930079, 930083.. Timeframe from 2017-07-17 to 2020-02-13
Rights	WPD, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

3.3 UOBDC-ELEC-003: WattNAV power navigator

Title	WattNAV power navigator
Creator	Dave Phillips (Wattify Limited)
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; ; Asset Data; Primary Substation Level; HV Feeder Level; Distribution Substation Level; LSOA Level; Interactive Map
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-003: This interactive map (overlaid on Google Maps) was developed configured for the Coventry area by Wattify using its own WattNAV technology to aid in the visualisation of WPD asset data, easily comparing map data layers with local network asset indicators. The following features can be displayed and by clicking have relevant information brought up: BSP areas, GSPs/BSPs, selected 33 kV routes, the RESO project area, areas of potential developments by Coventry City Council (including sustainable urban extensions, ground mounted solar PV and district heat networks), primary substations and areas served by each primary (colour coded for 6.6 kV and 11 kV networks), circa 2,000 distribution substations, circa 160 approximated HV feeder lines (indicating approximate winter peak maximum demand in Amps) and LSOA boundaries (colour coded by available headroom per property).
Publisher	Wattify Limited
Contributor	
Date	
Type	webpage
Format	html
Identifier	not publicly available; RESO provisional access via a Google Maps link
Source	WPD data and Wattify analysis
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	28 primary substations: 690014, 930025, 930026, 930027, 930028, 930029, 930030, 930031, 930033, 930034, 930035, 930037, 930038, 930039, 930040, 930041, 930042, 930043, 930044, 930045, 930046, 930047, 930049, 930050, 930055, 930061, 930079, 930083.
Rights	Wattify Limited, non-public data, available only for internal use within the RESO project

3.4 UOBDC-ELEC-004: WPD Network Capacity Map

Title	WPD Network Capacity Map
Creator	WPD
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; Asset Data; GSP Level; BSP Level; Primary Substation Level; Interactive Map; Geospatial Data
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-004: This is an interactive map of all the primary substations, BSPs and GSPs in WPD's licence area. It is also colour coded to display the firm capacity and available headroom in MVA in terms of demand or generation which could be added; green if more than 25% of the capacity is available, orange if between 10% and 25% is available and red if less than 10% of the capacity is available.</p> <p>The data is also downloadable as a csv file (under the 'View as > Data' tab), which in addition contains latitude / longitude points for each asset down to primary level (for QGIS), technology and capacity connected (in kVA) and statement of works information.</p>
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	webpage; text
Format	html; csv
Identifier	https://www.westernpower.co.uk/our-network/network-capacity-map-application
Source	WPD
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Entire WPD network. Updated daily.
Rights	<p>Public data, WPD.</p> <p>https://www.westernpower.co.uk/open-data-licence</p>

3.5 UOBDC-ELEC-005: WPD Shaping Sub-transmission

Title	Shaping Sub-transmission East Midlands 2020
Creator	WPD
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; Asset Data; GSP Level; BSP Level; Future Scenarios; Report
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-005: This document considers where future thermal, fault level and voltage constraints will occur on the 132 kV network by considering the growth in distribution connected generation and demand (from EVs, heat pumps, industry etc.) under the framework of four Distribution Future Energy Scenarios (DFES). The two GSPs of relevance for the RESO area (Berkswell and Coventry) are demand constrained by 2022, although only Coventry is generation constrained by 2027 in the Community Renewables scenario. It is suggested to upgrade Berkswell with a 240 MVA transformer in 2022 and transfer Coventry South BSP onto it. Accompanying network diagrams of the EHV network can be downloaded in pdf form and similar documents can be found for the other WPD regions (West Midlands, South West and South Wales).
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	pdf
Identifier	https://www.westernpower.co.uk/smarter-networks/network-strategy/strategic-investment-options-shaping-subtransmission
Source	WPD
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	East Midlands WPD network. Timeframe is 2022 and 2027. Updated every 3 years.
Rights	Public data, WPD. https://www.westernpower.co.uk/open-data-licence

3.6 UOBDC-ELEC-006: WPD Long Term Development Statements

Title	Long Term Development Statement
Creator	WPD
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; Asset Data; GSP Level; BSP Level; Primary Substation Level; Future Scenarios
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-006: The link contains a public document (Part 1) intended as an introduction section with a description of the data available in Part 2, high level maps of the network routes (down to 33 kV) and illustrative costs for feasibility studies of obtaining a connection for new demand or generation. Part 2 is obtained via signing up and requesting access. For the East Midlands, it was released in November 2019, with updates added in May 2020. The data is in the form of a folder of several spreadsheets and interactive pdfs outlining: geographic plans, network configurations under normal operation, circuit data, transformer data, forecast load information (Table 3), fault level information, connected generators (> 1 MW), planned developments at 132 and 33 kV and proposed interests in connections (for generation or demand) down to primary level (Table 6).
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	image; text
Format	pdf; xlsx
Identifier	https://www.westernpower.co.uk/our-network/long-term-development
Source	WPD
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	East Midlands WPD network. Timeframe is 2020-2025. Updated annually.
Rights	Part One: Public data, WPD. Part Two: Requires registration to Partners. https://www.westernpower.co.uk/open-data-licence

3.7 UOBDC-ELEC-007: WPD DataPortal2

Title	DataPortal2
Creator	WPD
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; Asset Data; GSP Level; BSP Level; Primary Substation Level; HV Feeder Level; Distribution Substation Level; LV Feeder Level; Interactive Map; Geospatial Data; Point Layer; Line Layer
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-007: In a similar process to Part 2 of the Long Term Development Statements, access to this platform is granted via request to WPD. The EMU Online interactive map allows users to navigate the entire WPD network down to street (LV) feeder level (on the backdrop of an Ordnance Survey Map) with different colours representing different voltages. HV feeders can also be highlighted to show areas they serve as well as features selected to bring up a tab of information. It is possible to export images to pdf but no geospatial datasets (e.g. vector shapefiles) are available to be downloaded through this platform.</p> <p>However, on request, permissions were upgraded such that a shape file containing the distribution substations and feeder lines down to 11 kV was available for download. They contained information on underground, overhead cables, how the substations were mounted (pole or ground) and names/asset numbers/association of feeders with primaries. In the large majority of cases these tags were consistent with the other distribution substation list and Voronoi polygons could be used to derive the publicly available primary level shapefiles. However, there were a few instances whereby the upstream primary was different in this dataset due to their different timeframes, so the boundaries did not exactly align.</p>
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	image; dataset
Format	html; pdf; shp
Identifier	https://dataportal2.westernpower.co.uk/
Source	WPD
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Entire WPD network. Timeframe is 2019.
Rights	Requires registration to DataPortal2 and approval from WPD. https://dataportal2.westernpower.co.uk/Auth/Register

3.8 UOBDC-ELEC-008: WPD Generation Capacity Register and Embedded Capacity Register

Title	Generation Capacity Register and Embedded Capacity Register
Creator	WPD
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; Generation Data; GSP Level; BSP Level; Primary Substation Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-008: This dataset gives the generation connected to different levels of the distribution network (down to primary substation level, while LV connected technologies such as PV are aggregated to this level) differentiated by technology, changes since the last version and figures for accepted/offered/enquired generation capacities. It is also possible to download a pdf map of the entire network with coloured circles to represent large embedded generators (export capacity > 1 MVA).</p> <p>The Embedded Capacity Register (ECR) provides enhanced information to network stakeholders on Distributed Energy Resources (DER) and network requirements. Additional related datasets are made available by WPD including spreadsheets showing: Interest in a Connection and Substation Planned Work (e.g. for reinforcement).</p>
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset; image
Format	xlsx; pdf
Identifier	https://www.westernpower.co.uk/our-network/embedded-capacity-register
Source	WPD
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Entire WPD network. Timeframe is 2021. Updated monthly.
Rights	Public data, WPD. https://www.westernpower.co.uk/open-data-licence

3.9 UOBDC-ELEC-009: WPD primary substation polygons

Title	Primary substation polygons
Creator	WPD
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; Asset Data; Primary Substation Level; Geospatial Data; Polygon Layer
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-009: This dataset contains the outlines of the areas used in the Network Capacity Map. The shape files for GSP, BSP and primary substation areas may be downloaded under Spatial Datasets at the bottom right of the webpage. This is very useful for analysis in GIS software, e.g. overlaying the area served by a primary substation with LSOA boundaries, postcode centroids or buildings in the Local Land and Property Gazetteer. These boundaries are not 100% congruous with WattNav or the LEAR mappings (it should be noted that a meshed network does not mean 1 building or area is served by 1 primary station 100% of the time), but as they come from WPD themselves, were decided to be the basis of future GIS analysis within the RESO project.
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	gpkg
Identifier	https://www.westernpower.co.uk/system-and-network-data
Source	WPD
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Entire WPD network. Timeframe is 2020.
Rights	Public data, WPD. https://www.westernpower.co.uk/open-data-licence

3.10 UOBDC-ELEC-010: WPD Distribution Future Energy Scenarios Map and Reports

Title	Distribution Future Energy Scenarios
Creator	WPD
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; Local Authority Level; Primary Substation Level; Interactive Map; Future Scenarios; Low Carbon Technologies; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-010: This interactive map contains data for the projected uptake of various low carbon technologies (e.g. heat pumps and EVs), new developments and generation capacity at a local authority or primary substation level for each year from 2020 until 2035 (then in 5 year intervals from 2035-2050) and under each of the four scenarios (broadly aligned with those used in the framework of National Grid FES 2020). The data for each technology projection is able to be exported for download as a csv. The written reports for each region are also available under WPD's website.</p> <p>https://www.westernpower.co.uk/distribution-future-energy-scenarios-regional-information</p> <p>It was last updated in December 2020 to give projections at a more granular primary substation level (previously they were at a BSP level).</p>
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset; text
Format	html; csv; pdf
Identifier	https://www.westernpower.co.uk/distribution-future-energy-scenarios-map
Source	WPD
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Entire WPD network. Timeframe is 2020-2050. Updated every 2 years.
Rights	Public data, WPD. https://www.westernpower.co.uk/open-data-licence

3.11 UOBDC-ELEC-011: WPD Carbon Tracer

Title	Carbon Tracer
Creator	WPD; The Carbon Trust
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; BSP Level; Interactive Map; Generation Data; CO ₂ Emissions Data; Hourly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-011: WPD have created this app and interactive map in partnership with Carbon Trust. Clicking an area or inputting a postcode will give the carbon intensity (for the most recent hour), fuel mix (renewable, fossil fuel, nuclear and other), a colour code (to encourage consumer use at times at times when the grid is 'greener'), renewable energy generation capacity and split of local generation to imported electricity (when local generation assets are generating at maximum capacity). Dates may be selected for historical information and an API is available.</p> <p>https://carbontracer.westernpower.co.uk/faq/how-do-i-use-the-carbon-api</p>
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2018
Type	dataset; text
Format	html; csv; pdf
Identifier	https://carbontracer.westernpower.co.uk/
Source	WPD
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Entire WPD network. Timeframe is 2021. Updated hourly.
Rights	<p>Public data, WPD.</p> <p>https://carbontracer.westernpower.co.uk/faq/how-do-i-use-the-carbon-api</p>

3.12 UOBDC-ELEC-012: WPD EV Capacity map

Title	EV Capacity map
Creator	WPD
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; Asset Data; Distribution Substation Level; Interactive Map; Geospatial Data; Point Layer; Low Carbon Technologies; Transport; Electric Vehicles
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-012: This interactive map was first produced by WPD based on an internal study conducted in 2019. Its purpose is to classify the distribution substations on its network (those that serve residential areas) into three levels of capacity with regards to the rollout of EVs. The three levels used are: extensive capacity, capacity and some capacity with the map colour coded accordingly. The data is also able to be exported as a csv which includes the distribution substation asset names/numbers, EV capacity, licence area (e.g. East Midlands), local authority and latitude/longitude for GIS analysis. This is the most detailed asset data at the LV level which is available to the public without having to make a request to WPD. It is consistent with the full distribution substation list provided to RESO in terms of the asset names, numbers and locations (albeit the co-ordinates are given in different forms). However, the full list made available for RESO is richer in that distribution substations which serve non-residential customers are also included, as well as the relation between the LV substations and their parent HV feeder/substation, customer counts and firm capacities.
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2019
Type	image; dataset
Format	html; csv
Identifier	https://www.westernpower.co.uk/ev-capacity-map-application
Source	WPD
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Entire WPD network.
Rights	Public data, WPD. https://www.westernpower.co.uk/open-data-licence

3.13 UOBDC-ELEC-013: Regional and local authority electricity consumption statistics

Title	Regional and local authority electricity consumption statistics
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Consumption; Local Authority Level; Domestic; Non-domestic; Annual Time Series
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-013: This dataset gives the number of domestic (standard and economy 7) and non-domestic meters at a local authority level, as well as total, mean and median consumption figures for each meter group. A figure for the average domestic electricity consumption per household is also given (not the same as the mean per meter), based on 2016 ONS household estimates.
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	Dataset
Format	Xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistical-data-sets/regional-and-local-authority-electricity-consumption-statistics
Source	Electricity supplier data aggregators
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2005-2019. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

3.14 UOBDC-ELEC-014: Lower and Middle Super Output Areas electricity consumption

Title	Lower and Middle Super Output Areas electricity consumption
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Consumption; MSOA Level; LSOA Level; Domestic; Non-domestic; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-014: This collection contains three datasets which give the total number of meters, as well as total, mean and median electricity consumption figures for each sector and geography. The three datasets are: domestic consumption at MSOA level (unlike the last dataset there is no differentiation between standard and economy 7 meters), non-domestic consumption at MSOA level (for non-half-hourly customers only, half hourly consumption statistics are given aggregated to local authority level in the same dataset) and domestic consumption at LSOA level. The data is available to be downloaded as an excel file with sheets for different years, or a collection of csv files (one for each year).</p> <p>These datasets (as well as the related postcode and local authority level statistics) are all derived from actual meter data held by suppliers. The data is unweather corrected and covers the time period from January 1st to December 31st for half-hourly customers (i.e. a calendar year) but January 31st to January 30th for non-half-hourly customers.</p> <p>It was enquired to BEIS as to whether the half-hourly data could be disaggregated to a smaller geography (e.g. MSOA) but this was deemed to lead to disclosure. Since for most local authorities, the majority of non-domestic electricity consumption is metered under half-hourly arrangements, the non-domestic MSOA statistics do not always provide a clear picture.</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx; csv
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/lower-and-middle-super-output-areas-electricity-consumption
Source	Electricity supplier data aggregators
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2010-2019. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

3.15 UOBDC-ELEC-015: Postcode level electricity statistics

Title	Postcode level electricity statistics
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Consumption; Postcode Level; Domestic; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-015: This dataset contains postcode level electricity usage data (meter numbers, mean and median consumption) for domestic consumers only. There are separate files for standard and economy 7 meters from 2016 onwards. These previously had to be merged (e.g. in python), to obtain total consumption figures for each postcode but the datasets have recently been updated to give this information more readily. It should also be noted, to prevent disclosure, that postcodes with under 5 meters are not published in these statistics (although they are aggregated to the first part of the postcode, e.g. CV1, and this value was 6 before 2021).</p> <p>It was enquired to BEIS as to whether more information on the distribution of data points within a postcode (e.g. maximum and minimum, range or standard deviation) would be able to be released, although this was not deemed feasible whilst maintaining disclosure protection.</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/sub-national-electricity-consumption-data#postcode-level-data
Source	Electricity supplier data aggregators
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2013 and 2015-2019. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

3.16 UOBDC-ELEC-016: Electric prepayment meter statistics

Title	Electric prepayment meter statistics
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Consumption; Local Authority Level; MSOA Level; LSOA Level; Postcode Level; Domestic; Fuel Poverty
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-016: This dataset contains information on the number of prepayment meters as well as mean, median and total consumption of the prepaid electricity at a local authority, MSOA, LSOA and postcode level for 2017. Prepayment customers often overpay for electricity and/or prepayment meters can be indicative of fuel poor households. It is unknown how often this data is intended to be updated.
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2019
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/electric-prepayment-meter-statistics
Source	Electricity supplier data aggregators
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2017.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

3.17 UOBDC-ELEC-017: BEIS DUKES Chapter 5 - Power Stations in the United Kingdom

Title	DUKES Chapter 5 - Power Stations in the United Kingdom
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Electricity; Generation Data; Low Carbon Technologies; Geospatial Data; Point Layer
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-017: This database (found in DUKES 5.11) contains information for all electricity generation capacities of sites ran by a Major Power Producer in the UK (a major power producer is defined as a business whose main purpose is the generation and sale of electricity). The information provided includes: company name, site name, fuel, technology, installed capacity (MW) and devolved nation or English region where the site is located. Although annual generation in GWh is not provided, an indicative value can be calculated based on typical load factors for the technology in question. An expanded version of the database was provided by BEIS via an e-mail request which contains information for the X-Y coordinates of each site and whether it is CHP enabled. On the same public webpage there are other interesting tables containing national level statistics available for download such as the fuels used in electricity supply (DUKES 5.6), industrial auto-generation (DUKES 5.4) and transmission/distribution connected generation capacity (DUKES 5.12), in addition to a pdf map of the thermal and hydroelectric Major Power Producers.
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/electricity-chapter-5-digest-of-united-kingdom-energy-statistics-dukes
Source	BEIS MPP Survey
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 1918-2019. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/ Licence of the extended version uncertain.

3.18 UOBDC-ELEC-018: Carbon Brief Map

Title	Mapped: How the UK generates its electricity
Creator	R. Pearce; S. Evans
Subject	Electricity; Generation Data; Low Carbon Technologies; Interactive Map
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-018: This interactive map was published by Carbon Brief in 2015 (created by R. Pearce and S. Evans) and is essentially an earlier version of the above dataset, but with the benefit of greater visualisation by placing the generation sites on an interactive map. The technologies shown are biomass, coal, gas, hydro, interconnectors, nuclear, oil, solar, waste and wind as circles of different colours and sizes (the larger the circle, the greater the generation capacity). Furthermore, clicking on a circle will bring up information on its name and date of operation.
Publisher	Carbon Brief
Contributor	
Date	2015
Type	image
Format	html
Identifier	https://www.carbonbrief.org/mapped-how-the-uk-generates-its-electricity
Source	DECC; Carbon Brief
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 1918-2015.
Rights	Public data, Creative Commons Licence. https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/legalcode

3.19 UOBDC-ELEC-019: Renewable Electricity by Local Authority

Title	Renewable Electricity by Local Authority
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Electricity; Generation Data; Low Carbon Technologies; Local Authority Level; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-019: This dataset tells users about the electricity generated in MWh and generation capacity in MW of renewable electricity sources for each local authority. The following renewable technologies are listed: solar PV, onshore wind, hydro, anaerobic digestion, offshore wind, wave/tidal, sewage gas, landfill gas, municipal solid waste, animal biomass, plant biomass and co-firing. The data is based on several sources including Ofgem's Renewable Obligation Certificates register, studies by Ricardo Energy and Environment as well as databases compiled by trade associations for the various renewable technologies.</p> <p>https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/729822/Renewables_methodology_note.pdf</p> <p>One issue within the RESO area that was noted is that for the EfW plant, although the capacity figure matched the plant operator's data, the annual generation did not. This might have been either due to an error in the BEIS data or intentional suppression to prevent disclosure.</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/regional-renewable-statistics
Source	Ricardo; Ofgem; Renewable technology trade associations
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2014-2019. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

3.20 UOBDC-ELEC-020: Renewable Energy Planning Database

Title	Renewable Energy Planning Database
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Electricity; Generation Data; Low Carbon Technologies; Geospatial Data; Point Layer
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-020: This database tracks the planning status of renewable electricity projects that are both operational and in the pipeline phase (either being under construction or having planning applications submitted, rejected, approved or pending appeal). It includes the company (planning applicant), various technologies, heights and number of turbines (for wind projects), mounting arrangements (for solar projects), as well as electricity storage and CHP enabled schemes. It contains recent and historical projects (back to a hydro station built in 1924), the planning authority (in most cases the local authority of the project site), as well as the X-Y coordinates of the site.
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	csv; xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/renewable-energy-planning-database-monthly-extract
Source	Barbour ABI
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 1924-2020. Updated quarterly.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

3.21 UOBDC-ELEC-021: Sub-regional Feed-in Tariffs statistics

Title	Sub-regional Feed-in Tariffs statistics
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Electricity; Generation Data; Low Carbon Technologies; Local Authority Level; Domestic; Non-domestic
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-021: This dataset shows the number of domestic and (by inference) non-domestic installations, as well as generation capacity for different sources of renewable electricity accredited under the Feed in Tariff (FiT) scheme from 2010-2019 at a local authority, local enterprise partnership or parliamentary constituency level. It is particularly useful for solar PV, although the scheme is now closed for solar PV in the UK, so in order to retain the value of this information for future installations, a new records system must be maintained (the latest update of this dataset in January 2020 will be the last release). The other technologies recorded are wind, hydro, anaerobic digestion and micro-CHP.
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistical-data-sets/sub-regional-feed-in-tariffs-confirmed-on-the-cfr-statistics
Source	Ofgem Central FiT Register
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is March 2019.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

3.2 UOBDC-ELEC-022: Small Scale Renewable Energy Generator Database

Title	Small Scale Renewable Energy Generator Database
Creator	REF
Subject	Electricity; Generation Data; Low Carbon Technologies; Local Authority Level; Postcode District Level; LSOA Level; Domestic; Non-domestic; Anonymised Individual Records
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-022: This is an anonymised version of the Ofgem Central FiT Register that has been made available to the public through the Renewable Energy Foundation (REF). It contains useful information on the technology, capacity in kW, sector (domestic, commercial, industrial), postcode district, LSOA, local authority, commission date and generation and export tariff arrangements for each anonymised individual installation. The tariff band data could be used to calculate payments made to a given geographic area. The drawbacks are that only 10 pages of results are visible to the public and no download of data functionality exists (although information can be copied and pasted into Excel page by page, and if time is no barrier, a large area of LSOAs could be downloaded on an LSOA by LSOA basis).
Publisher	REF
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	html
Identifier	https://www.ref.org.uk/fits/
Source	Ofgem Central FiT Register
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2010-2019.
Rights	Public data, No licence stated.

3.23 UOBDC-ELEC-023: Feed-in Tariff Installation Report

Title	Feed-in Tariff Installation Report
Creator	Ofgem
Subject	Electricity; Generation Data; Low Carbon Technologies; Local Authority Level; Postcode District Level; MSOA Level; LSOA Level; Domestic; Non-domestic; Anonymised Individual Records
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-023: In 2021, Ofgem have made available a dataset containing information on accredited generation sites held on the Central FiT Register. Due to its size the data has been split into three excel sheets which can be downloaded and it takes a similar style to the information presented in the anonymised REF collection (but without the restrictions). However, the data is slightly richer in that it includes the declared net capacity as well as the installed capacity, tariff description, accreditation route (e.g. MCS or Roofit), MPAN prefix, MSOA (as with LSOA, it is given as its code rather than its name) and whether or not the installation is on a school or initiated by a community group (there was a 12 month extension to the FiT scheme for pre-registered community installations).</p> <p>In terms of the definitive raw data underpinning this set, it was enquired whether the Central FiT Register could be made available to researchers (as it is for registered energy suppliers). However, e-mail correspondence with Ofgem confirmed that it would not be accessible for this purpose. The Local Energy Asset Representation (LEAR) report produced by the Energy Systems Catapult uses LSOA level data to present current PV installations with good granularity. Other potential sources of information at a deeper geographical level (e.g. postcode) could be the Microgeneration Certification Scheme (MCS) database, for which the RESO project is in the progress of negotiating a data sharing agreement or records held internally by WPD on what is connected to their network.</p>
Publisher	Ofgem
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.ofgem.gov.uk/publications-and-updates/feed-tariff-installation-report-31-december-2020
Source	Ofgem Central FiT Register
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2010-2020.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

3.24 UOBDC-ELEC-024: Consumer Load Profiles

Title	Consumer Load Profiles
Creator	Elexon
Subject	Electricity; UPRN Level; Domestic; Non-domestic; Modelled Data; Half-Hourly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-024: This file contains coefficients for the load profiles of the 8 classes of non-half hourly electricity consumers. These are: domestic unrestricted (01), domestic economy 7 (02), non-domestic unrestricted (03), non-domestic economy 7 (04) and non-domestic maximum demand customers with peak load factors of < 20% (05), 20-30% (06), 30-40% (07) and < 40% (08). Profile class can be inferred by the first two digits of an MPAN number (00 indicates a half-hourly customer). The modelled profiles are based on measured smart meter data with a target for a sample of 2500 in each profile class.</p> <p>https://www.elexon.co.uk/operations-settlement/profiling/</p> <p>The coefficients are available in half hourly periods from 01/04/2019 to 31/03/2021. Since the coefficients sum to 1 over a calendar year, they can be renormalised to obtain a synthetic half-hourly demand profile given the annual consumption. This data set (and others) can be downloaded from the Elexon Portal. To access the portal, one must first make an account then log in. This particular file can be found by going to the Operational Data folder, then Market Domain Data (MDD) and downloading the csv named 'Default Period Profile Class Coefficient'.</p>
Publisher	Elexon
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	www.elexonportal.co.uk/mddviewer
Source	Elexon
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2019-2021. Updated every 6 months.
Rights	<p>Non-public data, available via sign up. Elexon.</p> <p>https://www.elexon.co.uk/using-this-website/disclaimer-and-reservation-of-rights/</p>

3.25 UOBDC-ELEC-025: Imbalance Prices

Title	Imbalance Prices
Creator	Elexon
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Markets; National Level; Half-Hourly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-025: The Elexon portal also has data on the imbalance prices which affect all parties (e.g. generation companies, supply companies or trading companies) trading in transmission system electricity under the Balance and Settlement Code. For each half-hourly settlement period, the contracted generation/supply traded by all parties (submitted one hour in advance) is compared with the metered volume of electricity. Any parties that are out of balance will be subject to imbalance charges on a per MWh basis; derived by Elexon and based on the costs incurred by the National Grid either by bids/offers to alter generation/demand, known as the Balancing Mechanism, or directly through its own response/reserve services, to keep the system balanced in real time.</p> <p>There used to be a separate System Buy Price (paid by parties who are in a deficit with respect to their contracted volume) and System Sell Price (paid to parties who are in a surplus with regard to their contracted volume) but these values are now unified into a single price. Finally, the Net Imbalance Volume is defined as the net amount of system imbalance in MWh (positive when more electricity is required by the system and negative when too much electricity is on the system).</p> <p>The csv contains half-hourly time series data for all these values (System Sell Price, System Buy Price and Net Imbalance Volume) from September 2016 until the most recent week. To download this csv, go to Financial and Credit > System Prices > SSP/SBP/NIV. Finally, it is noted the Elexon portal contains other historic datasets relating to system losses, demand, temperature and frequency.</p>
Publisher	Elexon
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	https://www.elexonportal.co.uk/news/latest?cachebust=r7esns0w79
Source	Elexon
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2016-2021. Updated weekly.
Rights	<p>Non-public data, available via sign up. Elexon.</p> <p>https://www.elexon.co.uk/using-this-website/disclaimer-and-reservation-of-rights/</p>

3.26 UOBDC-ELEC-026: Electricity Trading Prices

Title	Electricity Trading Prices
Creator	Nordpool
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Markets; National Level; Half-Hourly Time Series
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-026: Nordpool publish day ahead electricity prices for the UK as well as a range of European nations. This website will be further explored to determine the most valuable datasets under the Nordpool UK tab which would aid the flexibility market design. The daily and weekly data can be manually exported as a csv, although automated extraction is prohibited under their terms and conditions. More bulky data could potentially be available on request, if it was for non-commercial purposes.
Publisher	Elexon
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	xls
Identifier	https://www.nordpoolgroup.com/Market-data1/#/n2ex/table
Source	Nordpool
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2019-2021. Updated daily.
Rights	Public data, Nordpool. https://www.nordpoolgroup.com/About-us/Terms-and-conditions-for-use/

3.27 UOBDC-ELEC-027: Carbon Intensity API

Title	Carbon Intensity API
Creator	National Grid; University of Oxford; Environmental Defence Fund; World Wildlife Fund
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; National Level; Regional Level; Half-Hourly Time Series; Interactive Map; Generation Data; CO2 Emissions Data
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-027: This project by an environmental consortium containing the National Grid and the University of Oxford estimates the carbon intensity and fuel mix of the electricity network for all DNO regions (e.g. WPD East Midlands) of the UK at half-hourly intervals, as well as a forecasted values for the next 48 hours to enable the planning of energy use, when the grid is less carbon intensive. A cursory investigation of their predicted values against actual values for carbon intensity suggests a strong correlation. There is also an API which can be accessed by the link at the bottom of the page along with its documentation. It is therefore possible to capture regional carbon intensity in a time series over the period back to January 2019.
Publisher	National Grid
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	xls
Identifier	https://www.nordpoolgroup.com/Market-data1/#/n2ex/table
Source	National Grid
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2019-2021. Updated half-hourly.
Rights	Public data, National Grid. https://github.com/carbon-intensity/terms/

3.28 UOBDC-ELEC-028: GridWatch

Title	Gridwatch
Creator	Elexon; University of Sheffield
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; National Level; Five-Minute Time Series; Generation Data
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-028: This website shows the fuel mix and generation for each technology of the UK national grid electricity in almost real time (the last 5 minutes) using data from Elexon and the University of Sheffield. It also shows the total demand, as well as England-Scotland and North-South power flows (from January 2016). It is available for download in csv form back until May 2011 by clicking the download tab and selecting the desired range.
Publisher	Gridwatch
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	https://www.gridwatch.templar.co.uk/
Source	Elexon; University of Sheffield
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2011-2021. Updated five-minutely.
Rights	Public data, No licence stated.

3.29 UOBDC-ELEC-029: Elexon Sum Plus Embedded Net Imports (ESPENI)

Title	Elexon Sum Plus Embedded Net Imports (ESPENI)
Creator	University of Birmingham; I.A.G. Wilson
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; National Level; Half-Hourly Time Series; Generation Data
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-029: This dataset is based on a combination of Elexon data (for transmission connected generation) as well as data from the National Grid (for embedded solar and wind generation connected at the distribution level). The imports and exports have also been summed to yield the net imports, reflecting the demand of Great Britain, while the data has been cleaned (suspected errors removed) and presented in UTC.
Publisher	Zenodo
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3884858
Source	Elexon; National Grid
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2009-2021. Updated monthly.
Rights	Public data, Elexon. https://www.elexon.co.uk/using-this-website/disclaimer-and-reservation-of-rights/ https://data.nationalgrideso.com/licence CC-BY-NC 4.0

3.30 UOBDC-ELEC-030: Household Electricity Survey and Model Tester

Title	Household Electricity Survey and Model Tester
Creator	Intertek
Subject	Electricity; National Level; Domestic; End Use
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-030: The Household Electricity Survey report is an in-depth study based on a sample of 251 households (including gas heated, all electric heated and multiple fuel heated properties) from five pre-defined demographic categories across the whole of England. It also includes hourly consumption data of the different appliances, which could be useful for understanding domestic electricity use at a greater time granularity. The model tester spreadsheet is also useful to see raw data points for households filtered by different criteria (e.g. housing type, size, composition, age, metering arrangement, heating, social grade and occupation) and compare with the Cambridge Housing Model.</p> <p>https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/spreadsheet-tools-for-users</p> <p>Other useful reports from 2014 entitled 'Correlation with Low Carbon Technologies' and 'Electricity Price Signals and Demand Response', which respectively investigate the potential for solar PV, EVs and heat pumps and Time of Use Tariffs to alter the demand profile of domestic consumers. These are available for download in the same section of the BEIS website.</p>
Publisher	DECC
Contributor	
Date	2013
Type	text; dataset
Format	pdf; xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/household-electricity-survey--2
Source	Intertek
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2010-2011.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

3.31 UOBDC-ELEC-031: Coventry & Solihull Waste Disposal Company - Export Meter Data

Title	Coventry & Solihull Waste Disposal Company – Export Meter Data
Creator	CSWDC
Subject	Electricity; EfW; Generation Data; Half-Hourly Time Series
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-031: This data was received for the RESO project through communicating directly with Coventry and Solihull Waste Disposal Company who operate the EfW plant in the Whitley area of the city. Data is given at a half-hourly level for exported electricity at the 2 MPANs. Further information on the plant is available on the CSWDC public website and various other documents (including KPIs, annual reports, and biogenic content) were provided to RESO by CSWDC. The time series data was consistent with the reported annual electricity value. https://www.cswdc.co.uk/key-performance-information
Publisher	
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	Not publicly available
Source	CSWDC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	CSWDC EfW plant. Timeframe is Jan 2018-Dec 2019.
Rights	CSWDC, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project

3.32 UOBDC-ELEC-032: Cleaned half-hourly operational time series data for electrical primary substations in Coventry

Title	Cleaned half-hourly operational time series data for electrical primary substations in Coventry
Creator	Dave Phillips (Wattify) and WPD Innovation Team
Subject	Electricity Network; Primary Substation Level; Half-Hourly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-032: Half-hourly operational data for the 28 primary level substations covering the RESO geographical area. Data has been combined from the raw data sets, has been parsed to give a UTC time series component, and cleaned to a) identify zero values and times when electrical flow changes from one transformer to another within the primary substation and b) interpolate values into those data points identified.</p> <p>This provides a dataset that is representative of the typical electrical flow from a primary level substation, rather than the peak or zero amounts that might happen if normally open network assets are then closed (and vice versa) to allow sections of the network to be de-energised.</p> <p>The values are taken from the MVA values from the transformers in the primary substation; the feeder level current data and the MVA_r values have not been cleaned and are therefore not contained in this dataset.</p> <p>This WPD monitoring data, is provided uniquely for the RESO project under terms set out below and contains half-hourly measurements for the power and current of WPD assets from July 2017 to February 2020. The apparent power (in MVA) is given for each primary substation transformer (usually 2 per primary). The data has been cleaned with potential errors such as spikes or zeroes flagged for 28 primary substations.</p>
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	Grant Wilson i.a.g.wilson@bham.ac.uk
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	csv, Utf-8
Identifier	https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/2zg7p/wpd-halfhourly-mva-data-for-coventry-UOBDC-project-area-primary-substations-cleaned
Source	WPD operational systems
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	28 primary substations: 690014, 930025, 930026, 930027, 930028, 930029, 930030, 930031, 930033, 930034, 930035, 930037, 930038, 930039, 930040, 930041, 930042, 930043, 930044, 930045, 930046, 930047, 930049, 930050, 930055, 930061, 930079, 930083. Timeframe is from 2017-07-17 to 2020-02-13
Rights	WPD; non-public data; only for internal use within the RESO project.

3.33 UOBDC-ELEC-033: National Grid electricity transmission network maps

Title	National Grid electricity transmission network maps
Creator	National Grid
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; Transmission Level; Geospatial Data; Line Layer; Point Layer
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-032: The National Grid is responsible for the high voltage electricity transmission network which takes power from large power generators and feeds it into the fourteen local distribution networks (managed by six regional operators) as well as transmission connected consumers, such as large industrial sites and the electrified rail network.</p> <p>A high level image of the transmission network lines (which operate at 400, 275 and occasionally 132 kV) is shown on the webpage and shapefiles may be downloaded publicly by selecting the respective file at the bottom of the page. There are 5 shape files available: overhead lines, cables, towers, substations and a combination of all four assets.</p> <p>The use for this geospatial data could be to determine if there are any transmission connected electricity users or generators within a local authority area (or confirm their absence, as in the case of Coventry). This could then be a way to identify the transmission connected organisation, and make a request for their consumption data to give a truer reflection of the electricity demand of an area (because transmission connected electricity is not accounted for in the BEIS local authority level energy statistics). Furthermore, proximity to the transmission network may present opportunities for future low carbon electricity generation or ancillary services projects.</p>
Publisher	National Grid
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset; image
Format	shp; pdf
Identifier	https://www.nationalgrid.com/uk/electricity-transmission/network-and-infrastructure/network-route-maps
Source	National Grid
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2021.
Rights	Public data, National Grid. https://www.nationalgrid.com/uk/electricity-transmission/network-and-infrastructure/network-route-maps

3.34 UOBDC-ELEC-034: WPD Connections Charging Statements

Title	WPD Network Connections Charging Statements
Creator	WPD
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Network; Cost of Connections; Low Carbon Technologies
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-034: Worked examples of costs of connecting e.g. LCTs within the East Midlands region, showing the typical workings for apportionment of cost of connection between the Network Operator and the Customer for customer information and guidance purposes. Note that further costing information and guidance is available for Use of System charges from various WPD and Ofgem sources.
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	WPD
Date	2020 – updated regularly
Type	Text
Format	Pdf
Identifier	https://www.westernpower.co.uk/connections-landing/connections-regulations-and-policy/connections-charging-statements
Source	WPD
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	East Midlands WPD network (other regions also available). Timeframe is 2020. Updated regularly.
Rights	Public data, WPD. https://www.westernpower.co.uk/open-data-licence

3.35 UOBDC-ELEC-035: Coventry LEAR - PV potential for LSOAs, postcodes and UPRNs

Title	Coventry LEAR - PV potential for LSOAs, postcodes and UPRNs
Creator	ESC
Subject	Electricity; Generation Data; Solar PV; Future Scenarios; Buildings; Domestic; LSOA Level; Postcode Level; UPRN Level
Description	UOBDC-ELEC-035: This additional dataset was obtained from the ESC via request as a follow up to the LEAR report which had identified areas of rooftops as suitable for solar PV clusters. The initial LEAR report only gave pictorial representation of these areas, but through an e-mail agreement not to share outside the RESO project, the results of the numerical analysis behind these figures was obtained, first aggregated to an LSOA and postcode level, then for all the individual UPRNs. At all granularities, the number of dwellings suitable for PV, total number of dwellings (including and excluding flats), suitable roof area and generation capacity in kW are given.
Publisher	
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	not publicly available
Source	ESC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry; 2020
Rights	ESC, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

4 GAS AND HEAT

4.1 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-001: Weather Uncorrected Sub-national gas consumption statistics – annual

Title	Weather Uncorrected Sub-national gas consumption statistics – annual
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Gas; Domestic; Non-domestic; Local Authority Level; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-001: Weather uncorrected gas demand data for each local authority area from 2015 to 2019 (separate csv files). Coventry has an LA code of E08000026. Data includes: Region name, Local Authority name, LA code, LAU1 code, number of gas meters (domestic, non-domestic and total), gas sales in GWh (domestic, non-domestic and total), mean and median gas sales (domestic, non-domestic and total) and Number of Non-Consuming MPRN's (thousands).</p> <p>Like the electricity data, it does not include transmission connected customers and follows broadly the same geographical granularity and format. However, some differences include that this data is weather corrected, is based on Xoserve held data (rather than aggregated supplier data) and runs from mid-May to mid-May (as opposed to January to January).</p> <p>Another problem occurs from the misallocation of non-domestic meters to the domestic sector (and less frequently, the reverse), since an industry standard cut-off point of 73200 kWh per year is used to which meters below this value are assumed to be domestic and those above non-domestic. It's estimated up to 2 million small business premises in the UK are misclassified this way.</p> <p>Note: annual data is not a calendar year, it is from Mid-May to Mid-May https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/946789/sub-national-methodology-and-guidance-booklet-2020.pdf</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	csv
Identifier	https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/946436/Weather_Uncorrected_Sub-national_gas_consumption_statistics_2015-2019.zip
Source	Uses MPRN demand data (measured and estimated) from Xoserve
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	GB; 2015-2019; annual values
Rights	Unclear. Therefore thought to be under Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.2 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-002: Weather corrected Lower and Middle Super Output Areas gas consumption – annual

Title	Weather corrected Lower and Middle Super Output Areas gas consumption – annual
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Gas; Domestic; Non-domestic; MSOA Level; LSOA Level; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-002: Weather corrected gas demand data for LSOA and MSOA areas.</p> <p>For LSOA domestic gas csv files data include: Local Authority Name, Local Authority Code, MSOA Name, Middle Layer Super Output Area (MSOA) Code, LSOA Name, Lower Layer Super Output Area (LSOA) Code, Number of consuming meters, Consumption (kWh), Mean consumption (kWh per meter), Median consumption (kWh per meter) and Number of non-consuming meters.</p> <p>For MSOA domestic gas csv files data include: Local Authority Name, Local Authority Code, MSOA Name, Middle Layer Super Output Area (MSOA) Code, Number of consuming meters, Consumption (kWh), Mean consumption (kWh per meter), Median consumption (kWh per meter) and Number of non-consuming meters.</p> <p>For MSOA non-domestic gas csv files include: Local Authority Name, Local Authority Code, MSOA Name, Middle Layer Super Output Area (MSOA) Code, Number of meters, Consumption (kWh), Mean consumption (kWh per meter) and Median consumption (kWh per meter).</p> <p>Note: annual data is not a calendar year, it is from Mid-May to Mid-May https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/946789/sub-national-methodology-and-guidance-booklet-2020.pdf</p> <p>As with electricity, the number of gas meters along with total, mean and median consumption, are available for the domestic sector at MSOA and LSOA level. For the non-domestic sector, however, the number of meters as well as total, mean and median consumption are available at MSOA level for all distribution connected consumers; unlike for electricity where only non-half-hourly meters were disaggregated to this level.</p> <p>An overview of weather correction is given by: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/369933/Overview_of_Weather_Correction_of_Gas_Industry_Data.pdf</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	csv
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/lower-and-middle-super-output-areas-gas-consumption
Source	Uses MPRN demand data (measured and estimated) from Xoserve

Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	GB; 2010-2019; annual values
Rights	Unclear. Therefore thought to be under Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.3 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-003: Postcode level gas statistics - annual

Title	Weather corrected postcode level gas consumption – annual
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Gas; Domestic; Postcode Level; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-003: Weather corrected gas demand data for postcodes and partial postcodes. Data includes: POSTCODE, Number of meters, Consumption (kWh), Mean consumption (kWh) and Median consumption (kWh).</p> <p>Note: annual data is not a calendar year, it is from Mid-May to Mid-May https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/946789/sub-national-methodology-and-guidance-booklet-2020.pdf</p> <p>An overview of weather correction is given by: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/369933/Overview_of_Weather_Correction_of_Gas_Industry_Data.pdf</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	csv
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/sub-national-gas-consumption-data
Source	Uses MPRN demand data (measured and estimated) from Xoserve
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	GB; 2013-2019; annual values (more accurate after 2017)
Rights	Unclear. Therefore thought to be under Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.4 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-004: West Midlands Local Distribution Zone gas demand - hourly

Title	West Midlands Local Distribution Zone gas demand – hourly
Creator	Cadent
Subject	Gas; Gas Networks; Local Distribution Zone Level; Hourly Time Series
Description	UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-004: West Midlands LDZ hourly gas demand. Coventry was apportioned a time series demand by scaling down this profile based on Coventry's share of annual demand.
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	csv
Identifier	Not publicly available
Source	Cadent operational monitoring
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	West Midlands Local Distribution Zone; 2017-2020; annual values (more accurate after 2017); Timeframe from 2017-07-17 to 2020-02-13; hourly values
Rights	Cadent restricted licence – only to be used within the RESO project

4.5 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-005: Non-gas map - annual

Title	Non-gas map – annual
Creator	Kiln, BEIS
Subject	Gas; Off-gas Properties; Heat; Building Type; Domestic; Socioeconomic Data; Fuel Poverty; Welfare; Tenure; Energy Efficiency; Local Authority Level; LSOA Level; Postcode Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-005: Non-gas map</p> <p>This data-rich interactive map can be used as a reference value for: the number of properties in a local authority, and by zooming further in, LSOA or postcode that are off the gas grid (for Coventry this is 22%); their types of heating systems as per the 2011 census; types of properties as per the 2011 census: terrace, semi-detached, detached and flats (e.g. purpose built, commercial and converted); tenures as per the 2011 census (e.g. social rent, private rent, owner occupied); fuel poverty rates, number of rooms and EPC ratings. The shading scale may be changed from percentage of off-gas properties to other variables by clicking on the paintbrush icons to the left of the category. The data at the geographical granularity shown for the area of the map displayed on screen can be downloaded by clicking 'Download CSV' at the bottom of the tab on the left had side of the page.</p> <p>Non-gas map is an excellent resource to gain an understanding of local energy data within the domestic heating sector and the underlying datasets could be updated or combined with domestic electricity and gas consumption data which are available from BEIS at the same geographical granularity (a full list of their sources used is accessible by clicking the 'i' icon in the lower right of the page). Its only drawback is being from various data sources from different time periods (some of which go back to 2011). Finally, after obtaining a login which is done by opening by the link at the top right of the page, postcode level data for off gas properties, distances from gas grid and EPCs is available.</p>
Publisher	Kiln, BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	csv
Identifier	https://www.nongasmap.org.uk/
Source	Various
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	LSOA (public); Postcode (via sign up); annual values
Rights	Various, check website 'information' page

4.6 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-006: Xoserve off-gas postcodes

Title	Xoserve off-gas postcodes
Creator	Xoserve
Subject	Gas; Gas Network; Off-gas Properties; Domestic; Non-domestic; Postcode Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-006: Xoserve off-gas postcodes</p> <p>The data contain a list of postcodes where Xoserve hold no record of a gas connection by either large or small gas transporters. The Postcode list also contains data for islands which are not connected the GB Mainland Gas network and any fuel supplies they may have are not recorded on Xoserve systems.</p> <p>Active Postcode List as of November 2017. Gas Connection Record as of 06/12/2017.</p> <p>This postcode list is an updated version of the input used to create the non-gas map. However, one key difference is that it only contains the postcodes with 100% of properties off the gas network. It is also used in the Coventry Local Energy Asset Representation from the Energy Systems Catapult to visualise the areas of interest that do not have a gas connection.</p>
Publisher	Xoserve
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	Text
Format	Xlsx
Identifier	https://www.xoserve.com/media/2687/off-gas-postcodes-v2.xlsx
Source	Xoserve
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	GB; postcode; 2017
Rights	<p>Contains Ordnance Survey data © Crown copyright and database right 2017</p> <p>Contains Royal Mail data © Royal Mail copyright and database rights 2017</p> <p>Contains National Statistics data © Crown copyright and database right 2017</p>

4.7 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-007: Biogas map - annual

Title	Biogas Map – annual
Creator	NNFCC
Subject	Gas; Bioenergy; Biogas; Low Carbon Technologies; CHP; AD; Interactive Map; Postcode Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-007: Biogas map</p> <p>Shows all operational anaerobic digestion plants in the UK (excluding water treatment facilities)</p> <p>A spreadsheet in xlsx format that includes the following data: Region, County, Developer, Site name, Postcode, Longitude, Latitude, Capacity (kWe), Biomethane capacity (Nm³/hr biomethane), Output, Status, Completion, Type, Feedstock, Total feedstock (tpa), Manure/ Slurry (tpa), Crop (tpa), Food Waste (tpa), Crop Waste (tpa) and Other Waste (tpa).</p>
Publisher	NNFCC
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.biogas-info.co.uk/biogas_map_2020_site_list_external/
Source	NNFCC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK; 2020; annual values
Rights	Unclear – felt to be copyright of NNFCC

4.8 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-008: UK CHP Development Map

Title	UK CHP Development Map
Creator	DECC
Subject	Heat; Heat Density; Domestic; Non-domestic; Public Sector; District Heat Networks; Interactive Maps; LSOA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-008: UK CHP Development Map</p> <p>The CHP Focus Development Map shows total heat loads in most built-up areas of the UK down to an LSOA level and broken down by sectors (including a percentage for district heating). The sectors listed (along with total heat demand) are: Large Industrial, Small Industrial, Domestic, Commercial Offices, Government Buildings, Education, Health and District Heating. Additional point layers can be toggled on such as large heat loads, thermal power stations and EfW plants. Areas can be selected and polygons can be drawn, then the resulting data downloaded as an excel file. It is unclear how the data has been compiled, i.e. whether empirical or estimated (and to what degree), weather corrected or not, and for which year, and whether the year is a calendar year.</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://chptools.decc.gov.uk/developmentmap
Source	DECC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	LSOA; MSOA; Local authority; annual values
Rights	Unclear. Therefore thought to be under Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.9 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-009: CHP Focus Scheme Database

Title	CHP Focus Scheme Database
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Heat; Electricity; CHP; Non-domestic; Postcode Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-009: CHP Focus Scheme Database</p> <p>The data published is obtained via the CHPQA programme from schemes who gave their permission for the information to be published. Organisations can ask for their data to be removed.</p> <p>Headers include: COMPANYNAME, PRIMEMOVER, SECTOR, CHPTPC (kWe), TOWN, COUNTY, POSTCODE and CHPREGIO.</p> <p>This partial database includes data for large CHP sites including their location, sector and total electrical power capacity. It can be used as an alternative source for estimating their yearly generation, using a load factor of 40% and the following formula, if real CHP data is unavailable.</p> <p>CHP generation (GWh) = CHP capacity (MW) * load factor * 8760 / 1000</p> <p>A drawback is its non-completeness due to relying on voluntary sign ups from CHP generators. A complete list is currently unavailable from BEIS due to reasons of commercial sensitivity.</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	csv
Identifier	https://chptools.decc.gov.uk/chp/public
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	GB; Provides postcode data
Rights	Unclear. Therefore thought to be under Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.10 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-010: Combined Heat and Power in Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland and the regions of England in 2018

Title	Combined Heat and Power in Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland and the regions of England in 2018
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Heat; Electricity; CHP; Generation Data; Regional Level
Description	UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-010: Combined Heat and Power in Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland and the regions of England in 2018 Special feature article report on CHP installations in 2018 containing information on the number of CHP schemes, capacity, heat and electricity generation and fuel used for projects which is available aggregated to the level of Scotland, Wales or the English regions.
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2019
Type	Text
Format	application/pdf
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/energy-trends-september-2019-special-feature-article-combined-heat-and-power-in-scotland-wales-northern-ireland-and-the-regions-of-england-in-20
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Scotland, Wales or the English regions; 2018; annual value
Rights	Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.11 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-011: Experimental statistics on heat networks - data tables

Title	Experimental statistics on heat networks - data tables
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Heat; District Heat Networks; Regional Level; Local Authority Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-011: Experimental statistics on heat networks - data tables</p> <p>A range of statistics at the regional level such as: Heating / Hot Water Capacity (MW), Heating / Hot Water Generation (GWh), Heating / Hot Water Supplied (GWh), Cooling Capacity (MW), Cooling Generation (GWh) and Cooling Supplied (GWh).</p> <p>This dataset gives the estimated number of heat networks at a local authority level as well as more details (sector, capacity etc.) at a regional or national level. This can be used to produce the estimated district heat network energy generation and supply, if the local heat network operators cannot be identified or engaged with. This dataset does not disclose the source of heating by sector or fuel at a local level.</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2018
Type	text
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/energy-trends-march-2018-special-feature-article-experimental-statistics-on-heat-networks
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Most data e.g. energy data at regional level; count of CHPs at local authority level; 2015
Rights	Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.12 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-012: English Housing Survey 2018: energy report

Title	English Housing Survey 2018: energy report
Creator	MHCLG
Subject	Heat; Buildings; Electricity; Gas; Domestic; Tenure; Building Type; Energy Efficiency; Retrofit; National Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-012: English Housing Survey 2018: energy report</p> <p>This report contains national statistics for housing archetypes, heating systems and current insulation levels. The English Housing Survey is a continuous national survey that collects information about people' housing circumstances and the housing stock in England. The Scottish equivalent is known as Scottish House Condition Survey and in Wales this is the Welsh House Condition Survey. It can be used to understand (at a national level) how heat is used, paid for and retained in domestic buildings.</p> <p>https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/kvqnv/common-energy-datasets</p>
Publisher	MHCLG
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/english-housing-survey-2018-energy-report
Source	MHCLG
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	England, 2018
Rights	Thought to be under Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.13 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-013: UK Level District Heating Schemes List

Title	UK Level District Heating Schemes List
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Heat; CHP; Gas; District Heat Networks; Postcode Sector Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-013: UK Level District Heating Schemes List</p> <p>Freedom of information request on: a) The location of the heat networks b) The number of final customers, broken down into domestic and commercial final customers and c) The approximate amount of heat supplied by the scheme in kWh on an annual basis, either in total or on an average per customer basis</p> <p>A UK Level District Heating Schemes List was made partially available through a 2017 freedom of information request. This large dataset contains the locations (up to the last 2 postcode digits) of UK district heat networks. It can be used an alternative way to identify district heat network operators and quantify their energy supplied to domestic and non-domestic buildings. To obtain the file, scroll down the page to the response and download Spreadsheet 26801.xlsx. Upon opening the file, the postcodes may be filtered through searching the drop-down menu in cell A1. An online map can then be used to search for the postcode area (excluding last two digits) and identify potential sources of input energy for the heat network.</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2018
Type	text
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/uk_level_district_heating_scheme#incoming-1090845
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	GB; Partial postcode; year is not clear
Rights	Thought to be under Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.14 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-014: Comprehensive CHP and District Heat Network database

Title	Comprehensive CHP and District Heat Network database
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Heat; CHP; Gas; District Heat Networks; Postcode Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-014: Comprehensive CHP and District Heat Network database</p> <p>Enquired by e-mail to heat statistics team in BEIS and the reply was that this is commercially sensitive data unavailable to researchers. However, it was mentioned that more disaggregated on data on these technologies could be added to future statistics, similar to "Experimental statistics on heat networks - data tables" (likely released at the end of 2020). The input for this dataset and its update are responses to the Heat Metering and Billing Regulations (the quality of data is likely to improve on previous collection, due to e.g. drop down options replacing user inputted answers).</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	Unknown
Type	Unknown
Format	Unknown
Identifier	Unknown
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Unknown
Rights	Unavailable

4.15 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-015: Engie Operational heat data - hourly

Title	Engie operational heat data – hourly
Creator	Engie
Subject	Heat; District Heat Networks; EfW; Non-domestic; Hourly Time Series
Description	UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-015: Engie operational heat data – hourly. Includes heat supplied to the different buildings on the heat network, electricity consumption and CO ₂ emissions.
Publisher	Engie
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	csv
Identifier	Not available
Source	Engie
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Heatline data only (District heating system in Coventry); from 2017-09-01 to 2021-04-30 (updated each month); total heat in kWh at a building meter level (9 buildings)
Rights	Restricted under Data Sharing Agreements between Engie and the University of Birmingham and Coventry City Council to analyse and aggregate data with the RESO project.

4.16 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-016: Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HDNU) Project Data – Coventry City Council

Title	Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HDNU) Project Data – Coventry City Council
Creator	WSP for Coventry City Council and BEIS
Subject	Heat; District Heat Networks; Low Carbon Technologies; Domestic; Non-domestic; Future Scenarios
Description	UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-016: Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HDNU) Project Data – Coventry City Council Coventry City Council have been involved in this project in parallel to RESO. It is essentially looking at 3 clusters in Coventry for the design of feasible low carbon district heat networks. The designs of these schemes have not been shared outside of the RESO project
Publisher	WSP
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	Text
Format	application/pdf
Identifier	
Source	WSP
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry area
Rights	Confidential (WSP, Coventry City Council and BEIS)

4.17 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-017: BEIS DUKES Chapter 4 - Gas Statistics - annual

Title	BEIS DUKES Chapter 4 - Gas Statistics - annual
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Gas; Gas Networks; End Use; Domestic; Non-domestic; National Level; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-017: BEIS DUKES Chapter 4 - Gas Statistics - annual</p> <p>Like the chapter for electricity, this collection contains statistics for the supply and demand of natural gas at a UK level. For example, the supply and consumption of natural gas and colliery methane (DUKES 4.2) contains annual values from 1996-2019 for various fractions of supply and demand.</p> <p>https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/904797/DUKES_4.2.xls</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/natural-gas-chapter-4-digest-of-united-kingdom-energy-statistics-dukes
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	GB; 1996-2019; annual values
Rights	Thought to be under Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.18 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-018: Estimates of heat use in the United Kingdom in 2013 - annual

Title	Estimates of heat use in the United Kingdom in 2013
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Heat; End Use; Gas; Domestic; Non-domestic
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-018: Estimates of heat use in the United Kingdom in 2013</p> <p>This dataset yields the breakdown of gas consumption by end use in the home and commercial (non-industrial) sectors using Tables 2, 3 and 4 on pages 96, 98 and 99. These are: (i) 77% space heating, (ii) 21% water heating and (iii) 2% cooking for the domestic sector, (iv) 75% space heating, (v) 14% water heating, (vi) 8% cooking and (vii) 2% other uses in the commercial sector and (viii) 11% space heating, (ix) 77% process heat and (x) 12% other uses in the industrial sector.</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2015
Type	text
Format	application/pdf
Identifier	https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/386858/Estimates_of_heat_use.pdf
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	GB; 2013
Rights	Thought to be under Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.19 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-019: Measurement of domestic hot water consumption in dwellings

Title	Measurement of domestic hot water consumption in dwellings
Creator	DECC
Subject	Heat; Hot Water; Domestic; National Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-019: Measurement of domestic hot water consumption in dwellings</p> <p>This report produced by the Energy Savings Trust for DEFRA and the DECC seeks to measure volumetric consumption of hot water (and associated energy requirements), patterns in time of use and temperature, compare these with BRE domestic energy model assumptions and identify where in the house water is being consumed. It used a sample of 120 houses.</p> <p>https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/kvqnv/common-energy-datasets</p>
Publisher	DECC
Contributor	
Date	2011
Type	text
Format	application/pdf
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/measurement-of-domestic-hot-water-consumption-in-dwellings
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	120 houses; 2011
Rights	Originally Crown copyright although now thought to be under Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.20 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-020: Energy Savings Trust – savings per insulation technology

Title	Energy Savings Trust – savings per insulation technology
Creator	EST
Subject	Heat; Domestic; Energy Efficiency; Retrofit; Buildings; National Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-020: Energy Savings Trust – savings per insulation technology</p> <p>These graphs from the Energy Savings Trust Savings show the annual financial savings attainable for various improved building efficiency measures for terraced, semi-detached, detached households and flats. These values can be converted to annual energy savings in kWh (using, for example, the conversion 1 kWh of domestic gas costs £0.0427). Similar data is available for different low carbon technologies under the Renewable Energy tab and appliances under Home Energy Efficiency tab.</p>
Publisher	EST
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	webpage
Identifier	https://energysavingtrust.org.uk/home-insulation
Source	EST
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	GB
Rights	Copyright Energy Savings Trust

4.21 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-021: Water source heat map layer

Title	Water source heat map layer
Creator	DECC
Subject	Heat; District Heat Networks; Heat Pumps; Rivers; Low Carbon Technologies; Future Scenarios
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-021: Water source heat map layer</p> <p>A detailed water source heat map has been developed to highlight the opportunities for deploying innovative heat pump technology. This map identifies the thermal potential of waterbodies in England and highlights the presence of existing environmental constraints. It is designed to support local authorities, communities and developers in investigating waterbodies with the best heat potential in their areas of interest.</p> <p>https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/kvqnv/common-energy-datasets</p>
Publisher	DECC
Contributor	
Date	2015
Type	Text
Format	
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/water-source-heat-map-layer
Source	DECC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Urban areas and rivers with > 100 MW heat output capacity
Rights	Thought to be under Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.22 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-022: H21 Leeds City Gate

Title	H21 Leeds City Gate
Creator	Leeds City Gate
Subject	Gas Network; Heat: Hydrogen; Low Carbon Technologies; Future Scenarios
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-022: H21 Leeds City Gate</p> <p>Hydrogen is an alternative fuel that can be used by gas networks and this source provides some information on hydrogen as a result of the H21 Leeds project. For instance, there is some data on the costs of re-purposing the network or the carbon emissions of low carbon hydrogen.</p> <p>https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/kvqnv/common-energy-datasets</p>
Publisher	Leeds City Gate
Contributor	
Date	2016
Type	text
Format	application/pdf
Identifier	https://www.northerngasnetworks.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/H21-Report-Interactive-PDF-July-2016.compressed.pdf
Source	Leeds City Gate
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Leeds area, 2017-2025
Rights	Publicly available document published by Leeds City Gate

4.23 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-023: Coal mine interactive map

Title	UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-023: Coal mine interactive map
Creator	Coal Authority; British Geological Survey
Subject	Heat; District Heat Networks; Mine Heat; Heat Pumps; Low Carbon Technologies; Future Scenarios; Geospatial Data; Raster Layer
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-023: Coal mine interactive map</p> <p>Please be aware that this data represents a snapshot in time from the national coal mining database which is regularly updated with new information. Date of last data extract: 11 April 2018</p> <p>The UK has a strong heritage of coal mining and it is estimated that around 25% of the nation's population live above abandoned coal mines (https://www.gov.uk/guidance/using-coal-mining-information). Many of these mines are now flooded and could be used as a heat sink for a low carbon district heat network. To explore this potential further, the Coal Authority and British Geological Survey have released an interactive map to display mining features as various layers. The options to be displayed are: coal reporting areas, NE mining and groundwater constraints, coal outcrops, probable/past shallow coal mine workings, surface mining (past/current), fissures and breaklines, mine entries and entry potential zones of influence, surface coal resource areas, development high risk areas and abandoned mines catalogue.</p> <p>As well as viewing the data online, the features are available as raster layers through encouraged use of a Web Mapping Service client. However, if vector layers are needed along with feature details, then a request must be submitted to the Coal Authority using the e-mail address at the bottom of the page. Pricing will vary depending on the level of data asked for. Finally, the metadata for each dataset is also publicly available through following link at the bottom of the page and case studies on mine water treatment are presented on another government webpage (https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/coal-mine-water-treatment).</p>
Publisher	Coal Authority; British Geological Survey
Contributor	
Date	2018
Type	text
Format	raster images for GIS
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/guidance/using-coal-mining-information
Source	Coal Authority / British Geological Survey
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	GB
Rights	Open Government Licence v3.0 http://nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.24 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-024: National Transmission System gas network route maps

Title	National Transmission System gas network route maps
Creator	National Grid
Subject	Gas; Gas Network; Transmission Level; Geospatial Data; Line Layer; Point Layer
Description	<p>UOBDC-ELEC-032: The National Grid is responsible for the high pressure gas transmission network which takes gas from terminals on the coast and feeds it into one of eight local distribution zones (managed by four regional operators) as well as transmission connected consumers, such as major power stations and large industrial sites.</p> <p>An image showing a high level map of the layout of this network is located on this webpage. A more detailed pdf image of a 100 x 100 km square (two letter OS grid area) is available to be downloaded under the gas network maps tab. Dated from 2017, there are 29 of these regional maps across the UK which show the locations of the high pressure pipelines. Additionally, shapefiles for the pipes and sites (or a combination of both) are able to be downloaded for non-commercial use only. These are more recently updated than the pdf maps and it is stated that to obtain sub-transmission shapefiles, the relevant regional gas distribution network operator should be approached.</p> <p>Despite being nationally significant infrastructure, its locational data can still be useful for local energy system planning. This is because it can be used to identify transmission connected sites and then request their consumption data (or infer their absence in an area where there are no high pressure pipelines, as is the case for Coventry), as well as assess the potential of an area for low carbon gas (e.g. hydrogen or biomethane) playing a significant role in its future energy mix based on its proximity to existing infrastructure.</p>
Publisher	National Grid
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset; image
Format	shp; pdf
Identifier	https://www.nationalgrid.com/uk/gas-transmission/land-and-assets/network-route-maps
Source	National Grid
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2017 and 2021.
Rights	Public data, National Grid. https://www.nationalgrid.com/uk/gas-transmission/land-and-assets/network-route-maps

4.25 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-025: Renewable Heat Incentive monthly deployment data

Title	Renewable Heat Incentive monthly deployment data
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Heat; Domestic; Non-domestic; Electricity; Heat Pumps; CHP; Solar Thermal; Bioenergy; Low Carbon Technologies; Local Authority Level
Description	UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-025: This dataset gives the number of domestic and non-domestic renewable heat incentive accreditations at a local authority level for the various eligible technologies such as air/ground/water source heat pumps, biomass/biogas boilers, solar thermal systems and CHP. Capacity is only given for non-domestic installations and technology breakdown is only given at a regional level. However, the latest dataset contains additional data tables compared to the previous version; these supplementary tables cover – e.g. domestic technologies by local authority and technologies by SIC grouping.
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx; ods; csv
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/renewable-heat-incentive-statistics
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain; 2011-2021; updated monthly
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

4.26 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-026: Renewable Heat Premium Payment Scheme: Heat Pump Monitoring: Cleaned Data, 2013-2015

Title	Renewable Heat Premium Payment Scheme: Heat Pump Monitoring: Cleaned Data, 2013-2015
Creator	UCL; DECC
Subject	Heat; Heat Pumps; Low Carbon Technologies; Domestic; Electricity; Half-Hourly Time Series; Future Scenarios; After Diversity Maximum Demand
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-026: This data was recorded from a sample of approximately 700 domestic heat pumps which were monitored from 2011-2015 while receiving subsidies under the Renewable Heat Premium Payment (RHPP) scheme. Aggregated profiles derived from this collection and published by Love et al were used as the basis for synthetic heat pump after-diversity demand curves in the RESO project.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.07.026</p> <p>One potential issue with this approach could be to what extent the RHPP sample is reflective of the Coventry building stock (at different geographical levels)?</p>
Publisher	UK Data Service
Contributor	
Date	2017
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	http://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-8151-1
Source	UCL; DECC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry; 2020
Rights	UK Data Service, non-public data, requires approval on their platform and non-commercial use only.

4.27 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-027: Cadent postcode level annual gas consumption

Title	Cadent postcode level annual gas consumption
Creator	Cadent
Subject	Gas; Domestic; Non-domestic; Postcode Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-027: As partners of the RESO consortium, Cadent have provided their own gas consumption statistics for the postcodes in the project area of interest. Each postcode with at least one gas meter is listed as a column in excel and for those with four or more connections, an annual consumption in kWh for the gas year 2019-20 is given. For postcodes with less than four gas meters, the annual consumption value has been removed for data protection reasons. However, all of these suppressed values have been aggregated to the entire RESO area.</p> <p>The data has been useful to compare with other statistics made available by BEIS or Xoserve. In particular, it can yield insight into the non-domestic annual gas consumption of a postcode by subtracting the BEIS quoted values (notwithstanding the uncertainties such as differing time periods, sources and cases in which it is unclear whether a meter serves a domestic or non-domestic property).</p>
Publisher	Cadent
Contributor	Cadent
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	Not publicly available
Source	Cadent
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	RESO project area. Timeframe is 2019-2020.
Rights	Cadent, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

4.28 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-028: Correla Data Discovery Platform

Title	Correla Data Discovery Platform
Creator	Correla
Subject	Gas; Domestic; Non-domestic; Postcode Level; UPRN Level; Monthly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-028: Correla is a new independent company which was previously a subsidiary of Xoserve (the UK's central gas data service provider).</p> <p>https://www.xoserve.com/news/xoserve-board-announces-investor-and-new-operating-model-update/</p> <p>They have produced a Data Discovery Platform at the request of Coventry City Council who wanted a quick and reliable method to assess the impact of interventions on gas consumption (e.g. recipients of retrofit grants). As RESO partners, the University of Birmingham Energy Informatics Group have also been granted access to this platform hosted on the Birst platform.</p> <p>This provides time series data for the rolling Annual Quantity and is also available at a monthly granularity from 2017 to present, as well as the class of the meter and whether it is smart or not.</p>
Publisher	Correla
Contributor	Xoserve; Coventry City Council
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	csv, xlsx
Identifier	Not publicly available
Source	Xoserve
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry. Timeframe is 2017-2021.
Rights	Correla, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

4.29 UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-029: Cadent gas pipeline shapefiles

Title	Cadent gas pipeline shapefiles
Creator	Cadent
Subject	Gas; Gas Network; Geospatial Data; Line Layer
Description	<p>UOBDC-GAS-HEAT-029: This dataset was obtained from Cadent and contains a skeletal line representation of the gas pipes within the same geographical area as that served by the 25 RESO primary substations of interest. The four layers are: NTS (which just passes through the outskirts of the boundary), IP-HP (intermediate pressure to high pressure at 2 to 70 bar), MP-IP (medium to intermediate pressure at 75 mbar to 2 bar) and LP (low pressure below 75 mbar).</p> <p>https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/566152/climate-adrep-national-grid-gas.pdf</p> <p>Uses of this data can be a side-by-side visual comparison with the electricity network geospatial files from WPD (or district heat networks), identifying non-low pressure connected consumers, validating areas without access to the gas grid areas and assessing the suitability of hydrogen and/or biomethane injection/repurposing.</p>
Publisher	Cadent
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	shp
Identifier	Not publicly available
Source	Cadent
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	
Rights	Cadent, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

5 TRANSPORT

5.1 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-001: Road transport energy consumption at regional and local authority level

Title	Road transport energy consumption at regional and local authority level
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Transport; Local Authority Level; Roads; Vehicles; Liquid Fuels; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-001: This dataset can be used to break down the liquid fuels (petrol and diesel) consumed in the transport sector into vehicle types (e.g. cars, LGVs, HGVs, buses and motorcycles). For each vehicle type, its consumption in ktoe is given by the kind of road travelled on (motorway, A road or minor road). This could be useful, should a local authority wish to understand the traffic flows in greater detail and where they can exert their influence. E.g. minor roads within urban areas can be affected by local policies whereas motorways are under the control of an external body (Highways England) and are likely to represent long distance traffic passing through the local authority, rather than making shorter journeys within its boundaries.</p> <p>The totals are consistent with the GWh road transport consumption figures in UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-001. Importantly, the values are based on where the fuel is consumed (i.e. as vehicles move) rather than where the fuel is purchased. The data is based on a study by Ricardo Energy and Environment which in turn takes its inputs from the Department for Transport's traffic activity and fleet composition data. Unfortunately local level consumption figures for the transport energy vectors of electricity, LPGs or biofuels are excluded from this dataset due to lack of geographical information (Localised Sankey Diagram methodology: Coventry City Council area (link not yet publicly available)). It should also be noted that unlike for domestic gas and electricity, LSOA level statistics are not available for road transport fuel consumption. Finally, unlike gas and electricity, there is not a strong seasonality to fuel consumption which remains fairly consistent throughout the year, notwithstanding the unprecedented drop in demand during the 2020-21 COVID-19 pandemic.</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistical-data-sets/road-transport-energy-consumption-at-regional-and-local-authority-level
Source	Ricardo; DFT
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2005-2018. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0.

<https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/>

5.2 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-002: QS416EW - Car or van availability

Title	QS416EW - Car or van availability
Creator	ONS
Subject	Transport; OA Level; LSOA Level; MSOA Level; Local Authority Level; Postcode Sector Level; Postcode District Level; Vehicles; Domestic; Fuel Poverty
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-002: These datasets, as part of the 2011 Census, detail the car or van ownership of OAs, LSOAs or various higher geographies in England and Wales. A downloadable file can be produced to breakdown the number of households with 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5+ private cars or vans, as well as the rural/urban classification of the geographical area.</p> <p>The menus can be navigated through to customise the downloaded data (this process is similar for several datasets on the nomis website which form a part of this data catalogue). The guide me step-by-step feature in the top left of the page makes this procedure clear to new users. The formats available to download data include xls, csv or tsv. The data can also be viewed in web browser or as a map (for a maximum of 10,000 areas), and has an API functionality.</p> <p>https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/api/v01/help</p>
Publisher	ONS
Contributor	
Date	2013
Type	dataset
Format	xls; csv; tsv
Identifier	https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/census/2011/qs416ew
Source	ONS; 2011 Census
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2011. Updated every decade.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

5.3 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-003: Road Traffic Statistics

Title	Road Traffic Statistics
Creator	DFT
Subject	Transport; Local Authority Level; Interactive Map; Traffic; Roads; Vehicles; Geospatial Data; Point Layer; Annual Time Series; Hourly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-003: This data collected by the DFT is based on the approximately 8000 manual roadside counts carried out by trained enumerators each year as well as automatic counters (sensors embedded into the road) at over 10,000 locations.</p> <p>The data is available via an interactive map of Great Britain where the counting locations can be identified by zooming in. Clicking on a count point will bring up a menu where the profile of the point can be viewed and raw count data as well as its latitude and longitude downloaded (in either csv or json format). The summary statistics tab then gives the annual vehicle miles by vehicle type at a national, regional or local authority level (as well as count data for that region/local authority).</p> <p>Moreover, the data downloads page also gives several files including: all traffic metadata (pdf), raw count data (at an hourly granularity, although with gaps when monitoring had paused), annual average daily flow (by direction and in both directions) and shapefiles for the major road network. Notes on the quality of the data (a counted or estimated column flag is used, with the latter recommended to be used with caution) and a full methodology document is also available. Finally, there exists an API documentation to aid access to the data which does not require a sign up.</p> <p>https://roadtraffic.dft.gov.uk/api/</p>
Publisher	DFT
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	csv; json
Identifier	https://roadtraffic.dft.gov.uk/#6/55.254/-11.107/basemap-regions-countpoints
Source	DFT
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2000-2019. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

5.4 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-004: Waze for Cities

Title	Waze for Cities
Creator	Waze
Subject	Transport; Interactive Map; Traffic; Roads; Vehicles; Geospatial Data; Point Layer; Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-004: Waze is an app developed by Google with a live map to inform drivers on traffic updates in real time and promote car sharing services. As reported in an article by Intelligent Transport:</p> <p>“Mapping service Waze is to make data gathered from across the UK accessible to local authorities to help them plan transport upgrades in the future. The tech firm’s maps use crowd-sourced data from users to update traffic conditions and live information about road congestion or accidents. The company has announced that it will make its Waze for Cities Data available for more than 1,000 global partners to seamlessly access Waze made available on the Google Cloud Platform, with 12 initial partners in the UK.”</p> <p>https://www.intelligenttransport.com/transport-news/89550/waze-to-share-traffic-data-with-transport-authorities/</p> <p>These partners include local/combined authority transport departments in the West Midlands, Oxfordshire, Essex, Greater Manchester, Leeds, Middlesbrough and London. Any other interested public sector partner can apply for a free, two-way exchange of data under Waze for Cities (linked as this dataset’s identifier).</p>
Publisher	Waze
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	unknown
Format	unknown
Identifier	https://partnerdash.google.com/waze/u/0/start#p=start&program=CCP&reason=no_access
Source	Google
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK/world. Updated in real time.
Rights	Non-public data, Google. Requires sign up, terms unknown.

5.5 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-005: All Vehicles (VEH01)

Title	All Vehicles (VEH01)
Creator	DFT
Subject	Transport; Vehicles; Electric Vehicles; Low Carbon Technologies; Local Authority Level; Postcode District Level; Quarterly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-005: This data is based on licensing statistics held by the Department for Transport (DFT) and Driver and Vehicle Licensing Agency (DVLA). Most relevant for the purposes of data related to the energy transition, licenced plug in EV numbers are given for each quarter from Q4 2011 to Q3 2020, so trends can be observed. The main issue with the accuracy of the data is that it counts the number of plug in vehicles in a local authority (VEH0131/VEH0132, the latter giving the breakdown between plug-in hybrids and pure battery electric vehicles) or partial postcode area (VEH0134), e.g. CV1, by mapping them to the addresses they are registered at. For most privately owned vehicles this will be the address where they are kept and therefore may be mostly used within that local authority (at least for short journeys). However, company or rental vehicles will be registered to a commercial premises which could potentially be a large distance from the residential property where they are kept and local authority where they do most of their travelling. As a result, one way to obtain a more conservative estimate is to use the value for privately owned ultra-low emissions vehicles within a local authority which can be found on sheet 'VEH0132d' of the dataset VEH0132 (downloadable from the same page as VEH0131). A further dataset for use in tandem with this one is VEH0105 which gives the number of registered vehicles in a local authority; with this information and the data from VEH0131, the percentage of registered vehicles which are plug in electric models can easily be calculated. Other datasets which may be of interest are those on the model types of cars and year of manufacture (the body type information is available at local authority and partial postcode level).</p>
Publisher	DFT
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	ods
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistical-data-sets/all-vehicles-veh01
Source	DVLA
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is Q4 2011-Q3 2020. Updated quarterly.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

5.6 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-006: Zap-Map

Title	Zap-Map
Creator	Zap-Map
Subject	Transport; Electric Vehicles; EV Charging Infrastructure; Low Carbon Technologies; Interactive Map
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-006: This handy website allows visitors to visualise the public EV charging infrastructure of GB through an interactive map. Live information on the availability of a charge point is displayed as well as the type of charger and its speed; these are colour coded, purple for rapid, blue for fast and yellow for slow. Therefore, the map can be useful to inspect areas of the country with a high, medium or low density of public charging infrastructure, in addition to comparing which organisations are providing the chargers (e.g. councils, private businesses or domestic users willing to share their access with others).</p> <p>There are no public download options but Zap-Map may be approached to share their dataset. This is the case with the ESC, who have used this information in their LEAR reports to show the distribution of charge points and give some insight into the evolution of the types of public chargers by year (2013-2020). The data originates from charge point operator networks, open charge map, the national charge point registry and contributions from users. There are also some interesting national level statistics on the annual growth of EV charging infrastructure under the Stats > UK Charge Points menu.</p>
Publisher	Zap-Map
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	image
Format	html
Identifier	https://www.zap-map.com/live/
Source	
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK and ROI. Timeframe is 2021. Updated five minutely.
Rights	Public data, Zap-Map. https://www.zap-map.com/terms-and-conditions/

5.7 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-007: National Charge Point Registry

Title	National Charge Point Registry
Creator	DFT
Subject	Transport; Electric Vehicles; EV Charging Infrastructure; Low Carbon Technologies; Geospatial Data; Point Layer; UPRN Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-007: This publicly available, DFT dataset is a component of the Zap-Map interactive map. It is a rich file which contains information on the number of chargers, types of charger, their kW ratings, address/postcode/local authority (including the name of the building, e.g. the supermarket), latitude/longitude, whether it is on/off street and the charger owner/controller. It also has a UPRN column, which although mostly blank at the moment, indicates there is ambition to integrate this dataset with that identification system.</p> <p>This map can be useful for combining with other geospatial data (such as LSOA/primary substation boundaries or road networks) to assess the ability of current EV charging infrastructure to meet demand against present and future EV ownership figures.</p>
Publisher	DFT
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	csv; xml; json
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/guidance/find-and-use-data-on-public-electric-vehicle-chargepoints
Source	
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2020.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

5.8 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-008: Electric Nation

Title	Electric Nation
Creator	WPD
Subject	Transport; Electric Vehicles; EV Charging Infrastructure; Low Carbon Technologies; Report; Domestic; Distribution Substation Level; Half-Hourly Time Series; Anonymised Individual Records
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-008: This collection of study outputs is available to download in the form of a final technical report, summary report and series of presentations. The study was conducted from 2016-2019 by a consortium containing WPD, ea technology, Drive Electric and Crowd Charge. 700 participants from across the WPD network area had their charging patterns analysed under different scenarios (including charging at will, limited charging during peak hours, interactive charging apps and incentivised charging with an effective time of use tariff). The results were intended to help answer key questions the country faces around increased EV charging: when do people charge, are people happy to have their charging managed and can incentives modify their habits etc. Ultimately studies like this will help network operators understand the constraints on the LV network arising from EV ownership; as the typical load profiles shown as part of the findings could potentially be applied to other areas. Finally, a follow up project exploring the merits of V2G (vehicle to grid) technologies has been announced for 2020-2022. Further pseudo-anonymised datasets used in the project have been released to the public by WPD. These include: Greenflux and Crowd Charge charging transactions, applied capacity profile, communication data and a vehicle database.</p> <p>https://www.westernpower.co.uk/electric-nation-data</p>
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2019
Type	text; dataset
Format	pdf; xlsx
Identifier	https://electricnation.org.uk/resources/smart-charging-project/
Source	WPD; Crowd Charge; Drive Electric; ea technology
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Entire WPD network. Timeframe is 2016-2019.
Rights	Public data, WPD. https://www.westernpower.co.uk/open-data-licence

5.9 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-009: TfWM ULEV Strategy

Title	Transport for West Midlands ULEV Strategy
Creator	Cenex
Subject	Transport; Electric Vehicles; EV Charging Infrastructure; Low Carbon Technologies; Report; Future Scenarios; Air Quality
Description	UOBDC-TRANSPORT-009: This project was carried out by Cenex on behalf of the West Midlands Combined Authority and their Transport for West Midlands department. It is currently confidential but has been shared with the RESO project for internal use. Completed in 2020, its aim is to help create a strategy for ultra-low emission vehicles (ULEVs) in tandem with addressing other issues such as air pollution, traffic congestion and opportunities for new industries. Outputs included recommendations for public transport, targeted investment in charging infrastructure, and evidence based projections for the number of ULEVs and charge points. It was also considered how the distribution of these would vary geographically across the West Midlands depending on socioeconomic factors (i.e. the least deprived areas being more likely to be early adopters).
Publisher	Cenex; TfWM
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	pdf
Identifier	not publicly available
Source	Cenex
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	West Midlands Combined Authority. Timeframe is 2020-2040.
Rights	TfWM, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

5.10 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-010: DC-Share Project

Title	DC-Share Project
Creator	WPD; Ricardo; Electricity Northwest; Turbo Power Systems; Vectos
Subject	Transport; Electricity Networks; Electric Vehicles; EV Charging Infrastructure; Low Carbon Technologies; Report; Distribution Substation Level
Description	UOBDC-TRANSPORT-010: This project is funded by Ofgem (under the Network Innovation Competition) and will run from 2020-2023. It will be delivered by a consortium of WPD, Electricity Northwest, Turbo Power Systems, Vectos and Ricardo Energy and Environment (project lead). The basic aim of DC share is to create a ring of direct current cables from the spare capacity of alternating current distribution substations which can power rapid EV charging points (an innovative approach to maximising the capability of existing transformer assets). The project proposal can be downloaded from the webpage and a proposed trial site in Taunton has been identified. Monthly updates are also provided through the link under identifier.
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	pdf
Identifier	https://www.westernpower.co.uk/innovation/projects/dc-share
Source	WPD; Ricardo; Electricity Northwest; Turbo Power Systems; Vectos
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Taunton. Timeframe is 2020-2023. Updated monthly.
Rights	Public data, WPD. https://www.westernpower.co.uk/open-data-licence

5.11 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-011: Data Shine Commute Map

Title	Data Shine Commute Map
Creator	UCL
Subject	Transport; Commute Data; Vehicles; Public Transport; Active Travel; MSOA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-011: This interactive map of GB has been produced by UCL and is a useful aid to visualise commuter flows between MSOAs and by method of travel, based on 2011 census data. Clicking on an MSOA will bring up a series of blue or red lines connecting that MSOA to others. Blue lines indicate people travelling to work in the selected MSOA, while red lines represent people leaving the MSOA to work in another. The data is displayed in tabular form in the bottom left of the page for all commuter flows in both directions (and the number of residents living and working in the same MSOA) of sample size ≥ 6 (presumably to prevent disclosure).</p> <p>The box in the top left of the page can be used to toggle the lines to show only to here/from here or both (which is the default setting). It can also, interestingly, be used to disaggregate the data into mode of transport: metro (i.e. tube or tram), train, bus/coach, motorbike, taxi, car (driving), car (as a passenger), cycling, walking or other.</p> <p>The data can be downloaded as a geospatial KML file through the webpage although not as a csv. However, the underlying data is based on "WU03EW - Location of usual residence and place of work by method of travel to work (MSOA level)" published by the ONS in 2014 and available for public download at:</p> <p>https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/query/construct/summary.asp?reset=yes&mode=construct&dataset=1208&version=0&anal=1&initset=</p> <p>Finally, it is worth noting the same group has produced quality interactive maps of most other 2011 census datasets which are available to download at OA level (a link for Data Shine Census is in the bottom right of the Commute map).</p>
Publisher	UCL
Contributor	
Date	2016
Type	image; dataset
Format	html; kml
Identifier	https://www.westernpower.co.uk/innovation/projects/dc-share
Source	ONS; 2011 Census
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	England and Wales. Timeframe is 2011.
Rights	<p>Public data, Open Data Commons Open Database License v1.0, Open Government Licence v3.0.</p> <p>https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1-0/</p> <p>https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/</p>

5.12 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-012: Estimates of Rail Station Usage

Title	Estimates of Rail Station Usage
Creator	ORR
Subject	Transport; Rail; Public Transport; Annual Time Series
Description	UOBDC-TRANSPORT-012: This data published by the Office for Road and Rail (ORR) statistics gives passenger numbers for all the mainline railway stations in GB. A spreadsheet is available for download which can be filtered by local authority to show passenger numbers (in terms of entries/exits and interchanges) with annual time series from 1998-2019. The estimates are produced by Steer for ORR, with a link to their methodology presented on the page. Finally an interactive map (double click to zoom) and bar chart for the selected station's passenger numbers 2010-2019 can be viewed on this page.
Publisher	ORR
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	ods; csv
Identifier	https://dataportal.orr.gov.uk/statistics/usage/estimates-of-station-usage/
Source	ORR
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 1998-2019.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

5.13 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-013: Network Rail data open data feeds

Title	Network Rail data open data feeds
Creator	Network Rail
Subject	Transport; Rail; Public Transport; Electricity; Electricity Network; Half-Hourly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-013: Network rail provides several datasets to interested parties who can sign up and request access. These are: BPLAN, train planning data, including locations and sectional running times (updated twice yearly); Corpus, location data (updated monthly); Movement, train positioning and movement in real-time; RTPPM, performance of trains against the timetable, measured as the percentage of trains arriving at their destination on-time (updated every minute); Schedule, daily extracts and updates of train schedules from the Integrated Train Planning System, in CIF and JSON formats (updated overnight each night); SMART, train describer berth offset data used for train reporting (updated monthly); TD, train positioning data at signalling berth level (updated in real-time); TSR, details of temporary reductions in permissible speed across the rail network (updated weekly on a Friday); VSTP, train schedules created via the very short term plan process which are not available via the Schedule feed (updated in real-time) and a daily extract of the infrastructure model from the Integrated Train Planning System in XML format (updated overnight each night).</p> <p>Furthermore, of relevance for energy systems, although perhaps not to the direct concern of DNOs as most mainline electrified rail connects directly to the transmission network at dedicated substations in ~50 km track intervals (https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/3872/low-cost-electrification-report.pdf), a month of half-hourly consumption data was provided on specific request for two substations (Patford Bridge and Long Buckby Wharf) which feed two sections of line in both directions from Northampton to Coventry and Nuneaton both via Rugby.</p>
Publisher	Network Rail
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	cif; json; xml; xlsx
Identifier	https://www.networkrail.co.uk/who-we-are/transparency-and-ethics/transparency/open-data-feeds/
Source	Network Rail
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Patford Bridge and Lock Bucky Wharf substations. Timeframe is July 2020-August 2020.
Rights	Public data, Network Rail. Time series data on request, licence terms unknown. https://www.networkrail.co.uk/terms-and-conditions/

5.14 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-014: National Travel Survey

Title	National Travel Survey
Creator	DFT
Subject	Transport; Rail; Public Transport; Vehicles; Active Travel; National Level; Regional Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-014: The National Travel Survey, published by the DFT, looks at how, why, when and where people travel and other factors that influence this.</p> <p>https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/kvqnv/common-energy-datasets</p> <p>The collection is mostly at a national level (with some regional data and splits between areas classed as urban or rural), while sections include: average number of trips made and distance travelled, driving licence holding/vehicle availability, mode of travel, road safety, cycling, school travel, concessionary travel, mileage by occupancy and vehicle availability by e.g. income/ethnicity/household type/disability status.</p> <p>Although there is no granular (i.e. local authority or LSOA level) data, it could be possible to reconstruct findings for small areas based on the links in the National Travel Survey and census statistics that are available at that geography (e.g. age, income or occupation).</p>
Publisher	DFT
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text; dataset
Format	pdf; ods
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/national-travel-survey-statistics
Source	DFT
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2019. Updated annually.
Rights	<p>Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0.</p> <p>https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/</p>

5.15 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-015: TfWM Bus Consumption Data

Title	TfWM Bus Consumption Data
Creator	TfWM
Subject	Transport; Public Transport; Bus; Local Authority Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-015: This dataset was provided to RESO by TfWM to help in the analysis of bus routes and their fuel consumption in the Coventry local authority area. The headers of the data columns provided for each route are: Service No., Route Description (e.g. Coventry to Leamington, via University, Kenilworth), Direction (I or O, inbound or outbound), Operator, Trips per day (on weekdays, Saturdays and Sundays), Total trips per week, Distance per trip and total distance travelled per week.</p> <p>It is noted that some of these routes pass through Coventry and go to destinations beyond its boundary. The main use of this data could be to explore how much electricity would be required to electrify the bus fleets, where charging infrastructure should be located (with potential for 'opportunity charging') and cross referencing the miles travelled/fuel consumption with other data sources such as those published by BEIS and DFT.</p>
Publisher	TfWM
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	not publicly available
Source	TfWM; Coventry bus route operators
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry. Timeframe is 2020.
Rights	TfWM, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

5.16 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-016: VLR project data

Title	VLR project data
Creator	CCC; WMG
Subject	Transport; Public Transport; Rail; Future Scenarios; Electricity
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-016: Coventry City Council (CCC) are currently working on an innovative project with Warwick Manufacturing Group (WMG) to implement a very light rail (VLR) route in Coventry. The project is in its R&D phase, with an expectation to build a prototype in 2021 be operating by 2025. There are plans for initial routes, however, these are not yet in the public domain.</p> <p>The project team believe that the permanence of a visible public transport network (such as a tram system) gives it an advantage of promoting a modal shift against traditional methods (e.g. buses). It should be noted that encouraging public transport will face additional challenges in the wake of the Covid pandemic (although by the end of the decade, this will likely become less of an issue).</p>
Publisher	CCC; WMG
Contributor	
Date	unknown
Type	unknown
Format	unknown
Identifier	not publicly available
Source	CCC; WMG
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry. Timeframe is 2020-2025.
Rights	CCC, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

5.17 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-017: TfWM All Traveller Segmentation Dashboard v2

Title	TfWM All Traveller Segmentation Dashboard v2
Creator	TfWM
Subject	Transport; Socioeconomic Data; Consumer Segmentation
Description	UOBDC-TRANSPORT-017: TfWM have given the RESO project access to their dashboard which gives statistics for transport use in the WMCA and uses a consumer segmentation approach. It is based on Tableau. The value of this data for Coventry and access to other internal TfWM datasets will be explored.
Publisher	TfWM
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	html
Identifier	not publicly available
Source	TfWM; Experian
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	West Midlands Combined Authority.
Rights	TfWM, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

5.18 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-018: Integrated Transport Network (ITN) Layer

Title	Integrated Transport Network (ITN) Layer
Creator	OS
Subject	Transport; Roads; Geospatial Data; Lines Layer
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-018: The OS MasterMap Integrated Transport Network (ITN) Layer consists of a fully topologically structured link-and-node network representing the roads network of Great Britain, from motorways to pedestrianised streets. The network lines follow topographic detail available in OS MasterMap Topography Layer. Information about the factors that may influence a driver's choice of route is available as an optional Road Routing Information (RRI) theme, extending the functionality of the roads network (https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/kvqnv/common-energy-datasets). In terms of the RESO project, it could be used for: mapping roads in Coventry, road network analysis, routing applications, scheduling and fleet management, traffic analysis, accessibility studies, and to analyse network resilience and the effects of planned road closures.</p> <p>As well as transport applications, it can also be useful to get roads as geospatial data objects to perform electricity and gas network analysis; the LEAR model by the ESC uses the road network to simulate the paths of gas pipes and LV wires which is a reasonable assumption in most urban areas.</p> <p>The data is available for education and research purposes through the Edina platform for Universities and other subscribed institutions. Other public sector organisations can usually obtain access through a public sector geospatial agreement, while commercial organisations will be required to register for an exploratory licence to try out data and eventually get a contract with OS (terms dependent on the intended data use). Finally it should be noted that this dataset was discontinued by OS in 2019 and has been replaced by the updated 'OS MasterMap Highways Network' which has links to the Unique Street Reference Numbers of AddressBase Premium (https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/mastermap-highways).</p>
Publisher	OS; EDINA
Contributor	
Date	2019
Type	dataset
Format	GML
Identifier	https://digimap.edina.ac.uk/webhelp/os/data_information/os_products/mastermap_itn.htm
Source	OS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2019. MasterMap Highways is updated every 6 weeks.

Rights	OS, non-public data, only for institutions subscribed to EDINA. https://digimap.edina.ac.uk/webhelp/os/copyright/licence_agreement.htm
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5.19 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-019: Uptake of Ultra Low Emission Vehicles in the UK

Title	Uptake of Ultra Low Emission Vehicles in the UK
Creator	Brook Lyndhurst
Subject	Transport; Roads; Geospatial Data; Lines Layer
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-019: This report was conducted for the DFT to understand the demographic makeup of early adopters of EVs as well as the barriers to their expanded ownership. As it was written in 2015, it could be compared or validated against actual observed trends in EV ownership over the last 5 years (the authors predicted that there would not be substantial changes in EV ownership demographics until beyond 2018-2020). Furthermore, the findings could be scaled down to the RESO area and combined with local (e.g. census or deprivation) data to theoretically disaggregate current EV ownership to smaller geographies (i.e. local authority to LSOA/primary substation area) and link with existing forecast studies (e.g. DFES) to produce more geographically granular projections.</p> <p>A similar report was published as part of Ofgem's Future Insight Series: Implications of the transitions to EVs.</p> <p>https://www.ofgem.gov.uk/publications-and-updates/ofgem-s-future-insights-paper-5-implications-transition-electric-vehicles</p> <p>The relation in the graph on pg. 30 of this document was used to conduct a high level forecast for the number of EVs at a primary substation level in the RESO area (before the WPD DFES maps were updated to primary substation level granularity).</p>
Publisher	DFT
Contributor	
Date	2015
Type	text
Format	pdf
Identifier	https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/464763/uptake-of-ulev-uk.pdf
Source	Brook Lyndhurst
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2015-2020.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

5.20 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-020: Experian Auto data

Title	Experian Auto data
Creator	Experian
Subject	Transport; Vehicles; Postcode Sector Level
Description	UOBDC-TRANSPORT-020: The RESO project have been in touch with Experian, through TfWM, who have a granular car keepership dataset, including models at a postcode sector level based on DVLA data. An agreement for RESO partners to access this data has been discussed.
Publisher	TfWM
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	text
Format	csv
Identifier	not publicly available
Source	Experian; DVLA
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	West Midlands Combined Authority. Timeframe is 2021.
Rights	Experian, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

5.21 UOBDC-TRANSPORT-021: Project Shift Progress Report

Title	Progress Shift Progress Report
Creator	UKPN
Subject	Transport; Electricity Networks; Electric Vehicles; EV Charging Infrastructure; Low Carbon Technologies; Report; Distribution Substation Level; Domestic; Half-Hourly Time Series; Electricity Markets; Future Scenarios
Description	<p>UOBDC-TRANSPORT-021: This report gives initial results and early insights from an investigation facilitated by UKPN involving three market-based mechanisms which enable smarter charging of EVs while being kept at home (e.g. off-street, overnight parking). Three customer propositions have been developed by Kaluza, Octopus Energy and ev energy and were trialled on groups totalling 800 customers in 2020 (with results separated into before and after the UK lockdown which began on 23rd March 2020). The price signals used to incentivise off-peak charging were Time of Use Distribution Use of System (DUoS) (Kaluza), capacity based DUoS (Octopus Energy) and LV flexibility procurement (ev energy).</p> <p>The RESO project has found the average half-hourly data from the pre-Covid 19 lockdown useful for producing synthetic after diversity demand profiles per EV. The ev energy results in Figure 28 were used for this because they had a high amount of customers with pure EVs and a low amount of manual overrides for charging. As with the RHPP dataset for heat pumps, this demand could be added to the baseline WPD monitoring data to observe the effect on the existing primary substation headroom when an arbitrary amount of low carbon technology uptake has occurred. Again like the RHPP dataset, uncertainty arises from the fact that this relatively small sample of early adopters might not be representative of the population in general, in terms of both charging behaviour and type of vehicle (or heating behaviour and type of heat pump).</p>
Publisher	UKPN
Contributor	Kaluza; Octopus Energy; ev energy
Date	2021
Type	text
Format	pdf
Identifier	https://innovation.ukpowernetworks.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/UKPN_Shift_Interim_Report_v05.pdf
Source	UKPN; Kaluza; Octopus Energy; ev energy
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK with greater representation of UKPN network. Timeframe is 2020.
Rights	Public data, UKPN. https://innovation.ukpowernetworks.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/UKPN-Innovation-Data-Sharing-Policy-7-Nov-19.pdf

6 MULTIVECTOR ENERGY DATA

6.1 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-001: BEIS Total final energy consumption at regional and local authority level – annual values

Title	BEIS Total final energy consumption at regional and local authority level
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Electricity; Gas; Solid Fuels; Liquid Fuels; Transport; Bioenergy; Domestic; Non-domestic; Local Authority Level; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-001: BEIS Total final energy consumption at regional and local authority level in units of kilo tonnes of oil equivalent and GWh. Categories are split into energy vectors (coal, manufactured fuels, petroleum products, gas, electricity and bioenergy and wastes) and broken into sectors such as industrial and commercial, industrial, domestic, rail, road transport, public sector and agriculture. Not all energy vectors have sector disaggregation i.e. bioenergy and wastes had no disaggregation before the latest release.</p> <p>This dataset forms the core skeleton of the Sankey diagram produced for the RESO Project (Localised Sankey Diagram methodology: Coventry City Council area (link not yet publicly available)). Data is available for all English, Scottish and Welsh local authorities with annual values from 2005 until 2018 (the latest year at publication date of 2020) for observing historical trends. A wide range of energy vectors are presented in this dataset, so it serves as a reference for the largest components of the local energy consumption: (i) domestic gas, (ii) non-domestic (labelled by BEIS as industrial & commercial but includes all consuming sectors except domestic properties) gas, (iii) domestic electricity, (iv) non-domestic (also labelled industrial & commercial but the same situation as for gas) electricity and (v) road transport. Consumption data for bioenergy and wastes (not including their use for electricity generation or biomethane injection), solid fuels (including coal listed separately) and non-road transport petroleum products are also included. In addition, there is also a dataset with the carbon emissions of local authorities that is numerically consistent with this dataset after applying conversion factors.</p> <p>https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/uk-local-authority-and-regional-carbon-dioxide-emissions-national-statistics-2005-to-2018</p> <p>The major limitation of this dataset for considering end uses of energy is the lack of disaggregation between consuming sectors for non-domestic electricity and gas. In the framework of national energy consumption statistics and in local datasets for petroleum products, a split between the industrial, commercial, agriculture, public administration (essentially the public sector) and transport sectors based on their Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) 2007 codes has been used. However, in this report, methods will be suggested to approximate these breakdowns. Also notably not included are: (i) electricity for transport as a separate column (although it does fall under industrial and commercial electricity), so that electric rail and EVs may be compared to their fossil fuel counterparts, (ii) locally generated electricity which is self-consumed by the producer and does not travel through the public grid (since electrical data is based on aggregated meter readings) and (iii) energy from heat networks (although if they are powered by mains gas, this will be counted under the industrial and commercial gas total), which despite all being a relatively small component of local energy systems presently, have</p>

	potential to play a much more significant role in the future as local authorities pursue decarbonisation agendas. Moreover, the same limitations apply as to the smaller area geography gas and electricity consumption statistics (as these statistics are based fundamentally on the same inputs).
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/total-final-energy-consumption-at-regional-and-local-authority-level-2005-to-2018
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Local Authority; 2005-2018, annual values
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

6.2 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-002: Sub-national residual fuel consumption statistics: 2005 to 2018 – annual values

Title	BEIS Total final energy consumption at regional and local authority level
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Solid Fuels; Liquid Fuels; Bioenergy; Domestic; Non-domestic; Local Authority Level; Annual Time Series
Description	UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-002: Sub-national residual fuel consumption statistics: 2005 to 2018 – annual values. This dataset is similar to the UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-001 data, but additionally can be used to differentiate commercial and industrial petroleum consumption. Its values are given in ktoe, so must be multiplied by 11.63 before being compared to GWh values. The totals are calculated from a model produced by Ricardo Energy and Environment. This model is based on the National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory point sources database together with other data (such as domestic heating types from the 2011 census or employment statistics) which are mapped together to produce estimates for each sector's consumption at local authority level. The sub-national residual fuel consumption dataset is based on the results of the National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory (NAEI) and Greenhouse Gas Inventory (GHGI) survey carried out by Ricardo. Residual fuels are defined as non-gas, non-electric and non-road transport fuels and cover consumption of coal, petroleum, manufactured solid fuels, and bioenergy and wastes not used for the generation of electricity or road transport.
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	csv; pdf
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistical-data-sets/estimates-of-non-gas-non-electricity-and-non-road-transport-fuels-at-regional-and-local-authority-level
Source	Ricardo; NAEI; BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Local Authority; 2005-2018; annual values; All sectors covered (except aviation and national navigation)
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

6.3 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-003 Energy Consumption in the UK - annual values

Title	Energy Consumption in the UK
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Electricity; Gas; Liquid Fuels; Solid Fuels; Bioenergy; Domestic; Non-domestic; Building Activity; End Use; National Level; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-003: Energy Consumption in the UK is an annual set of statistics published by BEIS. It covers a wide range of sectors and contains useful tables for understanding energy demands of vectors by end use across the domestic, transport, service (including the commercial and public sector) and industrial sectors at a national level. Its energy consumption data is largely sourced from the Digest of UK Energy Statistics, although some tables are modelled based on the relevant research not being undertaken recently</p> <p>(https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/820843/Energy_Consumption_in_the_UK_ECUC_MASTER_COPY.pdf).</p> <p>The tables are categorised under six collections: Consumption, Energy intensity, Primary energy, End uses, Electrical products and Supplementary data. As of 2019, there is also an interactive dashboard available to help visualise either energy consumption by fuel for the selected sector, energy consumption by sector for the selected fuel and energy intensity by sector https://beis1.shinyapps.io/ecuk/</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	xlsx; pdf; ods
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/energy-consumption-in-the-uk
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK; 1970-2018; annual values
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

6.4 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-004: Digest of United Kingdom Energy Statistics - annual

Title	Digest of United Kingdom Energy Statistics
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Liquid Fuels; Solid Fuels; Bioenergy; CHP; Low Carbon Technologies National Level; Annual Time Series
Description	UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-004: Digest of United Kingdom Energy Statistics. The digest is a rich source of cross vector data with chapters dedicated to national level statistics and trends in solid fuel, liquid fuel (petroleum) and renewable energy consumption.
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	xlsx; pdf; ods
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/digest-of-uk-energy-statistics-dukes-2020
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK; 1970-2018; annual values
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

6.5 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-005: National Energy Efficiency Data-Framework (NEED)

Title	National Energy Efficiency Data-Framework (NEED)
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Electricity; Gas; Domestic; Non-domestic; Building Activity; Building Type; Tenure; Demographics; Building Ages; Energy Efficiency; Anonymised Individual Records; National Level; Local Authority Level; UPRN Level; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-005: This webpage lists all the documents relevant to the NEED framework whose purpose was to build understanding of energy use and energy efficiency in all UK buildings. Its inputs are aligned with the electricity and gas meter data which are used to compile the BEIS statistics at postcode, LSOA, MSOA and local authority levels. Further data on energy efficiency measures are drawn from the Homes Energy Efficiency Database (HEED), Green Deal, the Energy Company Obligation (ECO) and the Feed-in Tariff scheme, as well as building and household characteristics from a range of sources (e.g. the Valuation Office Agency and Experian).</p> <p>The datasets available to the public are ones which assess the impact of measures (e.g. insulation, renewable electricity) and give a detailed view of how energy (gas and electricity) consumption relates to one of several variables (e.g. property type, tenure, income number of adults etc.).</p> <p>Perhaps the richest datasets are found under "Record level data", a large collection of anonymised meter level records available in a sample of 50,000 or 4 million entries. Moreover, the "Consumption data tables" give local authority level data on how a single variable relates to gas or electricity consumption and through "Data explorer", two variables can be selected to create a table of values showing their relationship towards gas or electricity consumption (although this is not possible at local authority level).</p> <p>The non-domestic NEED framework was updated in 2020; building on the BEES framework, the supporting data tables give some real helpful information on the energy intensities of different non-domestic buildings by their business activity. Finally, at the bottom of the page there are a collection of special features/ad-hoc requests which could also be useful.</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2019
Type	dataset; text
Format	csv; xlsx; pdf
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/national-energy-efficiency-data-need-framework
Source	BEIS; Xoserve; Electricity supplier data aggregators
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain; 2013-2020; updated annually

Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/
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6.6 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-006: Annual Gas and Electricity Consumption at the Meter Level (NEED)

Title	Annual Gas and Electricity Consumption at the Meter Level (NEED)
Creator	ONS
Subject	Electricity; Gas; Domestic; Non-domestic; Energy Efficiency; UPRN Level; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-006: This dataset contains the raw annual consumption figures for gas and electricity meters matched to the Unique Property Reference Number (UPRN) of an associated building. The gas data is weather corrected, while the electricity data is not. Electricity meters also contain the profile class of the user and an aggregated version of this collection is used by BEIS as the input for the publishing of postcode, LSOA and higher geography gas and electricity statistics.</p> <p>As this dataset contains data points for individual consumers, it has a high risk of disclosure and thus is only available via the ONS Secure Research Service.</p> <p>https://www.ons.gov.uk/aboutus/whatwedo/statistics/requestingstatistics/approvedresearcherscheme#accessing-the-secure-research-service-srs</p> <p>Upon completion of accreditation training, researchers must make a proposal and then access the data through a portal in an ONS safe room. The findings from working with this secure data can then only be taken away from the safe room or published, if the supervisors are satisfied there is no risk of disclosure.</p>
Publisher	ONS
Contributor	
Date	2019
Type	dataset
Format	STATA
Identifier	not publicly available
Source	Xoserve; Electricity supplier data aggregators
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain; 2004-2017; updated annually
Rights	Non-public data, only for ONS accredited researchers and subject to application.

6.7 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-007: Beyond Average Consumption

Title	Ofgem Data Portal
Creator	CSE; Ofgem
Subject	Electricity; Gas; Domestic; Consumer Behaviour; Socioeconomic Data; Demographics; National Level
Description	UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-007: In a similar line of thought to the NEED datasets, OfGEM commissioned a piece of work by the Centre for Sustainable Energy, which seeks to understand links between demographic/income factors and energy consumption with accompanying data tables. Furthermore, a Chi-squared Automatic Interaction Detector (CHAID) method is use to segment the UK's energy consumers into 12 archetypes.
Publisher	CSE
Contributor	
Date	2014
Type	text
Format	pdf
Identifier	https://www.cse.org.uk/projects/view/1223
Source	CSE
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK; 2011
Rights	Public data, CSE, fair dealing provisions of the Copyright Designs and Patents Act 1988. https://www.cse.org.uk/terms-and-conditions

6.8 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-008: Ofgem Data Portal

Title	Ofgem Data Portal
Creator	Ofgem
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Networks; Electricity Markets; Gas; Gas Networks; Gas Markets; Domestic; Non-domestic; Customer Satisfaction; Energy Suppliers; National Level; Regional Level; Annual Time Series; Quarterly Time Series; Monthly Time Series
Description	UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-008: This online portal from Ofgem provides data on retail, wholesale, customer service and network aspects of electricity and gas markets. They are mostly in the form of various interactive bar charts, pie charts or line graphs with an accompanying online data table. The data is mostly at a high geographical granularity, mostly the whole of GB and broken down by energy supplier or network operator region.
Publisher	Ofgem
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	html; pdf
Identifier	https://www.ofgem.gov.uk/data-portal/overview
Source	Ofgem
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK; 2014-2021; updated regularly
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.ofgem.gov.uk/copyright-and-disclaimer

6.9 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-009: Smart meter statistics

Title	Smart meter statistics
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Electricity; Gas; Smart Meters; Domestic; Non-domestic; National Level; Quarterly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-009: These statistics give the number of smart meters in the UK for each quarter from 2013 to 2020. The figures are broken down between the domestic/non-domestic and gas/electricity consumers; they also differentiate between smart meters, smart type meters/advanced meters and traditional meters.</p> <p>The underlying statistics come from the energy suppliers. Large suppliers (>250,000 customers) were mandated in 2013 to provide quarterly figures on smart meter uptake and small suppliers have provided yearly figures too since Q4 2015. Unfortunately, these statistics cannot be disaggregated by BEIS, but a DNO region level dataset on the rollout of smart meters (both monthly and cumulative) has been provided by Electralink.</p> <p>https://www.electralink.co.uk/monthly-smart-meter-installs/</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx; ods
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/smart-meters-statistics
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain; 2013-2020; updated quarterly
Rights	<p>Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0.</p> <p>https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/</p>

6.10 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-010: Coventry Local Energy Asset Representation (LEAR)

Title	Coventry Local Energy Asset Representation (LEAR)
Creator	ESC
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Networks; Gas; Gas Networks; Off-gas Properties; Liquid Fuels; Electric Vehicles; EV Charging Infrastructure; Socioeconomic Data; Solar PV; Generation Data; Buildings; Building Type; Building Ages; Domestic; Non-domestic; Energy Efficiency; Retrofit; Low Carbon Technologies; Report; Mappings; LSOA Level; Postcode Level; Primary Substation Level; HV Feeder Level; Half-Hourly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-010: This analysis has been conducted by the Energy Systems Catapult (ESC) through their own methodology which draws on various public datasets and information provided by network operators, many of which are alluded to in this document (the methodology and its inputs are explained in a document that accompanies the Coventry report).</p> <p>The LEAR is both available as a pdf document and set of data tables in excel (called the Data Export). The purpose is essentially to create an energy profile of a specified area based on its electricity and gas consumption/infrastructure, as well as other building and demographic factors. The energy outputs are mostly given at an annual level, but also 24-hour, half-hourly profiles are synthesised for electricity, gas and oil demand on a peak winter day, winter weekday, winter weekend, summer weekday and summer weekend.</p> <p>The report contains lots of maps based on these parameters and the raw data behind them is contained on its own sheet of the spreadsheet. These sheets are described as follows: Rurality, Domestic_BuildingType, Domestic_BuildingAge, Domestic_BuildingTypeAndAge, Domestic_FloorArea, Domestic_Heating, Domestic_Loof, Domestic_Wall, Domestic_Window, Domestic_PredominantHome, Non-Domestic_FloorArea, PointSourceEmissions, Domestic_Demand_LSOA, NonDomestic_Demand_LSOA, Total_Demand_LSOA, Demand_Totals, Demand_Profiles, OffGas, SubstationCounts, FeederLengths, PostcodesGas, Substation_Capacity, Feeder_Capacity, Substation_Buildings, Renewable_Generation, FiT_by_LSOA, RooftopSolarAreas, PluginVehicles, PublicEVChargepoints, ChargepointUptake, OffStreetParking, ListedBuildings, HeritageSites, Social_FuelPoverty, Social_IMD, Social_Crime, Social_Education, Social_Employment, Social_Environment, Social_Health, Social_Housing, Social_Income and EPCs.</p> <p>The ESC has provided this analysis to the Coventry RESO area and other PFER projects, but does welcome approaches from any groups or local authorities with an interest in this type of data.</p>
Publisher	ESC
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset; text
Format	xlsx; pdf
Identifier	https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/e5qxg/coventry-lear

Source	ESC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry; 2020
Rights	ESC, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project and other PFER projects.

6.11 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-011: Localised Sankey Diagram methodology: Coventry City Council area

Title	Localised Sankey Diagram methodology: Coventry City Council area
Creator	University of Birmingham
Subject	Electricity; Gas; Liquid Fuels; Domestic; Non-domestic; Public Sector; End Use; CO ₂ Emissions Data; Energy Costs; Annual Time Series; Local Authority Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-011: This document intends to act as a methodology for producing a Sankey diagram to represent the local energy flows in an area in terms of the different vectors, sectors and end uses. It is colour coded for the different vectors (blue for gas, red for electricity, grey for liquid fuels etc.) and available at 3 scales in different units: energy (GWh), carbon emissions (kt CO₂) and cost (£ million).</p> <p>Several of the publicly available datasets referred to in this document act as inputs for this method. Initially, it was just intended to produce a local energy flow Sankey diagram for the RESO area, but the document eventually developed a wider focus; such that any local authority could follow the steps and visualise the quantitative multi-vector energy flows for their area. To accompany this document, there is also an interactive spreadsheet which allows users to quickly input values from the different sources and compute the relevant output from which a visual Sankey diagram can be produced (using sankeyMATIC).</p> <p>http://sankeymatic.com/build/</p> <p>It should be noted that the methodology takes a high level view and makes plenty of assumptions, however as a basic guide, it can be the first step to a more complex energy system analysis; e.g. one that considers seasonality or vector substitution (i.e. hydrogen/electricity for natural gas/liquid fuel). It is intended for the methodology to ultimately become open data and is currently a work-in-progress, but interested parties are advised to contact j.k.day@bham.ac.uk for more information.</p>
Publisher	
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text; image; dataset
Format	docx; pdf; xlsx
Identifier	not yet publicly available

Source	BEIS; ONS; Kiln; CDRC; NNFCC; DFT; DECC; ESC; CCC; University of Warwick
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry; 2017; potential to be updated annually
Rights	Intended for the methodology to become open data.

6.12 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-012: Coventry City Council Estate – Energy Manager Live data

Title	Coventry City Council Estate – Energy Manager Live data
Creator	CCC
Subject	Electricity; Gas; Liquid Fuels; Non-domestic; Public Sector; Monthly Time Series; Half-Hourly Time Series; UPRN Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-012: This dataset yielded the electricity and gas consumption of the local authority's own operations (either as half-hourly data, if automated meter readings, or monthly manual readings) which can be useful to compare with the total energy demand of the area, e.g. to see how much influence the council has on the whole area's system through its own choices of energy procurement. Similar datasets should be available for the health and education sectors, if NHS or academy trusts are approached. Other annual energy consumption estimates can be produced purely from employment data or Display Energy Certificate data.</p> <p>The data was obtained via access to an online portal and through analysing the sites on a building level basis. The council's total electricity consumption in 2019 was found to be 9 GWh (0.7% of total electricity consumption in Coventry) and 11 GWh for gas (0.4% of the total gas consumption in Coventry). These values will have been reduced in recent years as secondary schools have moved out of direct local authority control and one limitation could be that the data portal only counts sites where the City Council is involved in the billing process either as a payee occupier or recipient landlord. Public lighting has not been included so far, but national level data is available from DUKES 5.2 which states 1878 GWh for the UK in 2018. This scales down to 10 GWh for Coventry by population share (which as it turns out, is very close to the actual value). The street lighting contractor (in Coventry's case, Balfour Beatty) has been engaged with to obtain more data.</p> <p>There is no standard energy monitoring practice for local authorities and the capacity for energy analysis from in-house staff will vary, but it is certain that someone at each local authority will be responsible for the bill payments of council occupied properties and tracking expenditure. Although to conclude, local authorities should certainly be engaged with to share their internal energy consumption data with interested parties (Localised Sankey Diagram methodology: Coventry City Council area (link not yet publicly available)).</p>
Publisher	Energy Manager Live
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	html; xlsx
Identifier	not publicly available
Source	CCC
Language	en-GB
Relation	

Regional Energy System Operator (RESO)

Coverage	Coventry; 2000-2020; updated regularly
Rights	CCC, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

6.13 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-013: University of Warwick – Energy Audit

Title	University of Warwick – Energy Audit
Creator	University of Warwick
Subject	Electricity; Gas; Liquid Fuels; CHP; District Heat Networks; Generation Data; Non-domestic; Heat; Energy Efficiency; Solar PV; Low Carbon Technologies; CO ₂ Emissions Data; Public Sector; Higher Education
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-013: This internal dataset gave a detailed account of multi-vector energy consumption at the University of Warwick campus (a significant energy consuming site in Coventry). If there is a similar large energy user, such as another higher education institution in the local authority, they too can be approached to share their data. Also, University of Warwick have invested heavily in Combined Heating and Power (CHP) and district heating at their Energy Centre, so could be a case study for a smart local energy system.</p> <p>The CHP generated 33 GWh of electricity and provided 67 GWh of heat for district heat networks in 2018-19. Universities (as significant power/heat consumers and leaders of innovation) should be engaged with to share data and learning with other actors in the local decarbonisation strategy (Localised Sankey Diagram methodology: Coventry City Council area (link not yet publicly available)).</p>
Publisher	
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	not publicly available
Source	University of Warwick
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	University of Warwick; 2005-2019
Rights	University of Warwick, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

6.14 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-014: Higher Education Provider Data: Estates Management

Title	Higher Education Provider Data: Estates Management
Creator	HESA
Subject	Electricity; Gas; Liquid Fuels; Non-domestic; Generation Data; CO ₂ Emissions Data; Public Sector; Higher Education
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-014: The Higher Education Statistics Agency releases environmental information on its members' estates (HE institutes are mandated to provide data on various topics for its statutory customers, such as the Department of Education). On the webpage, it is possible to see a list of the available energy related datasets or filter them into relevant subjects. The topics listed are: Buildings and spaces, Carbon emissions, Water, Energy, Transport, Waste, Management and performance, and Finances and people. For example, in the Energy topic, each university's annual energy consumption (in kWh), generated renewable electricity (kWh), electricity exported to grid (kWh), water consumption (in m³) and liquid fuel consumed in its internal vehicle fleet (in litres) are given.</p> <p>The data can be viewed online or downloaded as a csv for each academic year, 2015/16 to 2018/19, with headers for all the information provided under each topic. It is sourced by the respective estates management teams at each campus and is stated as being available under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence.</p>
Publisher	HESA
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	https://www.hesa.ac.uk/data-and-analysis/estates
Source	UK university campuses
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK university campuses; 2015/16-2018/19 academic years; updated annually
Rights	Public data, Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence. https://www.hesa.ac.uk/about/website/terms

6.15 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-015: National Grid Future Energy Scenarios 2020

Title	National Grid Future Energy Scenarios 2020
Creator	National Grid
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Networks; Gas; Gas Networks; Hydrogen; Liquid Fuels; Bioenergy; Generation Data; Domestic; Non-domestic; Heat; Heat Pumps; Low Carbon Technologies; Electric Vehicles; CO ₂ Emissions Data; Future Scenarios; National Level; GSP Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-015: This piece of work is the latest in the collection of annual Future Energy Scenarios (FES) produced by the National Grid. Released in July 2020, this year's version is the first to be made after the net-zero carbon 2050 target was announced by the UK government. It does not, however, consider the effects of the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic, but this will be factored into the 2021 release.</p> <p>The 3 main documents relating to FES are the 'FES in 5', which gives a brief, high-level overview of the 4 scenarios, the full written report and a data workbook containing spreadsheets of the underlying statistics and projections. The 4 scenarios featured in FES 2020 are: Leading the Way, System Transformation, Consumer Transformation and Steady Progression. The first three are all compliant with the net-zero 2050 target whereas Steady Progression is intended to serve as a business as usual for comparison. The main differences from previous editions are the focus on hydrogen (particularly in System Transformation) and the power sector completely decarbonising by 2032 with negative emissions through to 2050 due to bioenergy being combined with carbon capture and storage; carbon negative electricity is deemed necessary due to the impracticalities of decarbonising some sectors such as air travel or industrial processes in the given timeframe. System Transformation envisions a faster hydrogen rollout, while Consumer Transformation predicts a greater role for local solutions and electrification of heat. Leading the Way, on the other hand, takes aspects from both of these to decarbonise in the fastest manner.</p> <p>In terms of the data workbook, the Contents sheet gives a good overview of the available data which is broken into several chapters (e.g. Consumer View, System View). The last of these chapters, gives the building blocks and GSP area level projections for various low carbon technologies.</p> <p>Finally, it should be noted that the RESO project found this data workbook particularly useful for forecasting purposes by scaling down the projections for hydrogen consumption by sector to the Coventry area based on its share of current gas/petroleum consumption for the given purpose (e.g. domestic heat or HGV transport).</p>
Publisher	National Grid
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text; dataset
Format	pdf; xlsx
Identifier	https://www.nationalgrideso.com/future-energy/future-energy-scenarios/fes-2020-documents

Source	National Grid
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain; 2019-2050; updated annually
Rights	Public data, National Grid. https://www.nationalgrideso.com/terms-and-conditions

6.16 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-016: Net Zero South Wales Project

Title	Net Zero South Wales Project
Creator	Regen; WPD; Wales and West Utilities
Subject	Electricity; Electricity Networks; Gas; Gas Networks; Hydrogen; Domestic; Non-domestic; Heat; Heat Pumps; Low Carbon Technologies; Generation Data; Electric Vehicles; CO ₂ Emissions Data; Future Scenarios; OA Level; Primary Substation Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-016: This project conducted by Regen with the support of WPD and Wales and West Utilities (the regional gas network operator) developed 3 scenarios for a net-zero energy system in South Wales by 2050. The framework was based on 3 scenarios: a high hydrogen, core hydrogen and high electrification. In addition, for the high hydrogen scenario, a hybrid heat sensitivity analysis was carried out to study the effect of hybrid hydrogen-heat pump heating systems replacing pure hydrogen boilers.</p> <p>Lots of input datasets were used as a baseline (detailed in the report) as well as network operator asset data. South Wales contains a mixture of urban and rural communities, along with heavy industrial clusters. Outputs included maps of technology and demand profiles, as well as carbon emissions.</p> <p>Accompanying spreadsheets may be downloaded which detail the projections of various technologies within various sectors (e.g. domestic heat, large industrial processes, electricity storage etc.) at a primary substation level, for each year until 2050. The methodology outlined could be applicable to other areas and the basic framework of 3 scenarios (high hydrogen, high electrification and mixed) will be considered by the RESO project for Coventry. In conclusion, it is a helpful report which sets out the expanded use of the most likely two vectors for a low carbon future and how that may vary based on location.</p>
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text; dataset
Format	pdf; xlsx
Identifier	https://www.westernpower.co.uk/net-zero-south-wales-project
Source	Regen; WPD; Wales and West Utilities

Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	South Wales; 2020-2050
Rights	Public data, WPD. https://www.westernpower.co.uk/open-data-licence

6.17 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-017: MCS installations data

Title	MCS installations data
Creator	MCS
Subject	Low Carbon Technologies; Heat Pumps; Solar PV; CHP; Domestic; Non-domestic; Postcode Level; UPRN Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-017: The Microgeneration Certification Scheme (MCS) is a quality assurance body whose standards are used in the installation of low carbon technologies in order for the installed equipment to be eligible for FiT or RHI payments. https://mcscertified.com/</p> <p>Therefore, they hold the records of every MCS accredited low carbon technology (e.g. solar PV, solar thermal, small scale wind turbines, micro-CHP, air/ground/water source heat pumps and biomass boilers) installed in the UK from 2007 to the present day. Through the Prospering from the Energy Revolution (PFER) network, it had been found that MCS were willing to share granular data from their database. MCS were engaged with and through a data sharing agreement were able to provide an excel file containing data on installations with sheets for each year 2007-2020 and the following column headers: Commissioning Date, Address Line 1, Address Line 2, Address Line 3, County, Postcode, Local Authority, Total Installed Capacity (in kW) and Technology Type. More information is held by MCS and other headers were shown in a sample file, but to minimise data protection risks, these were redacted from the received version.</p> <p>This dataset gives great insight into low carbon technology deployment at a much more geographically granular level than is available publicly from either Ofgem, BEIS or the electricity networks. Using a string matching method, it can be combined with the LLPG to get the UPRNs and latitude-longitude co-ordinates of the property; a first iteration of this approach yielded ~80% accuracy, but this could be higher by using fuzzy matching. The data could also be compared with the FiT register, BEIS local authority statistics and WPD's generation capacity register or DFES. Furthermore, it could even be away to determine the LV part of the network (or HV feeder) that generation assets or heat pumps are connected too.</p>
Publisher	MCS
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	Not publicly available
Source	MCS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2007-2020.
Rights	MCS, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

6.18 UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-018: Smart Energy Research Lab Observatory Data, 2019-2020: Secure Access

Title	Smart Energy Research Lab Observatory Data, 2019-2020: Secure Access
Creator	UCL
Subject	Electricity; Gas; Domestic; Smart Meters; Consumer Behaviour; Anonymised Individual Records; UPRN Level; Half-Hourly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-018: The Smart Energy Research Lab (SERL) is a UKRI Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council funded 5-year project to provide access to valuable, high-resolution energy data for UK researchers.</p> <p>https://serl.ac.uk/about-serl/</p> <p>The dataset contains information including: daily and half-hourly monitoring data (for both electricity and gas), technical meter data, EPC data, weather data and SERL surveys completed by the user of each meter. It is intended to recruit 10,000 participants by March 2021, with 4,800 recruited by October 2020.</p> <p>https://serl.ac.uk/researchers/</p> <p>As this data is very sensitive and discloses consumption patterns at an individual household level, access is controlled and only granted securely to accredited researchers and approved projects. The following steps must be carried out (with an estimated timescale of 3 months):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ONS Safe Researcher training and exam 2. University ethics approval 3. Project approval from the UK Data Service and SERL Data Governance Board <p>https://serl.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Accessing-SERL-Observatory-data-info-for-researchers-v04.pdf</p> <p>The Energy Informatics Group at University of Birmingham are in the process of this approval, to support the RESO project and wider research aims of the group through exploratory analysis.</p> <p>Finally, an informative summary on the availability/regulatory environment for smart meter data and its applications has recently been published by Icebreaker One's Open Energy.</p> <p>https://energydata.org.uk/data-protection-and-smart-meter-data/</p>
Publisher	UK Data Service
Contributor	University of Essex; Cardiff University; University of Edinburgh; Leeds Beckett University; Loughborough University; University of Southampton; EST; Ipsos MORI
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	unknown
Identifier	http://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-8666-3
Source	
Language	en-GB

Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2019-2020.
Rights	Secure (non-public) data, only for access by accredited researchers and approved projects. https://beta.ukdataservice.ac.uk/datacatalogue/studies/study?id=8666#!/details

7 WEATHER AND CLIMATE

7.1 UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-001: UK local authority and regional carbon dioxide emissions national statistics: 2005 to 2018

Title	UK local authority and regional carbon dioxide emissions national statistics: 2005 to 2018
Creator	BEIS; DEFRA; Ricardo; UKCEH; Forest Research; Aether; Gluckman Consulting; Hartley McMaster LTD
Subject	Climate; CO ₂ Emissions Data; Electricity; Gas; Liquid Fuels; Transport; Industrial; Domestic; Non-domestic; LULUCF; Local Authority Level; Annual Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-001: This dataset provides a breakdown of the carbon dioxide emissions of different sectors at local authority level (broadly consistent with those used in BEIS Total final energy consumption at regional and local authority level but with some variations). It could also be used to make an alternative high-level Sankey diagram with the flows representing carbon instead of energy, if it is not desired to apply separately derived carbon intensity factors or a more nuanced system view.</p> <p>CO₂ is the only greenhouse gas considered in this dataset (and the RESO project), since it accounts for 81% of UK greenhouse gas emissions in CO₂ equivalent. The following sectors are omitted from the local statistics: international aviation/shipping, domestic aviation/shipping, exports and military transport. It should also be noted that, notwithstanding the omitted sectors, these are in line with UK government territorial production-based statistics; not footprint-based in which the emissions associated with the production of imported goods are also reported. Data for electricity (split domestic/non-domestic), gas (split domestic/non-domestic) and road transport consumption (split motorways, A roads and minor roads) are broadly consistent with Total final energy consumption at regional and local authority level and a constant value of 0.26 kg CO₂ / kWh for electricity has been used across the country for 2017 data. Also included sectors are: large industrial installations, industrial and commercial other fuels, domestic other fuels, diesel rail, transport (other) and LULUCF. As explained in their methodology report, the transport (other) column does refer to inland water transport, ground-based air support traffic, coal railways and liquefied petroleum gas vehicles. The omission of electric transport as a sub-sector will become more of an issue in future. Ultimately, this dataset will have to differentiate between electric rail and road based EVs to provide more insight.</p> <p>There are two local datasets provided, a 'Full dataset' and 'Subset dataset'. The only difference being that the latter omits motorway road transport, diesel rail transport, LULUCF and large industrial installations (which are all deemed beyond the control of a local authority to significantly influence). In addition, on the rightmost sheet (called Pollution Inventory), there is a list of single point emissions from large industrial sites and sources of point emissions.</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text; dataset

Format	pdf; ods; xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/uk-local-authority-and-regional-carbon-dioxide-emissions-national-statistics-2005-to-2018
Source	BEIS; DEFRA; Ricardo; UKCEH; Forest Research; Aether; Gluckman Consulting; Hartley McMaster LTD
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2005-2018. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

7.2 UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-002: National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory – Point Source Emissions

Title	National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory – Point Source Emissions
Creator	BEIS; DEFRA; Ricardo; UKCEH; Forest Research; Aether; Gluckman Consulting; Hartley McMaster LTD
Subject	Climate; CO ₂ Emissions Data; Air Quality Data; Interactive Map; Industrial; Non-domestic; Geospatial Data; Point Layer; Individual Records
Description	<p>UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-002: This website contains data on the emissions of various pollutants and where they are emitted from. The pollutants listed by their emissions in tonnes include CO₂ (as weight of carbon, so multiply by 3.7 to get the actual CO₂ in kg), CH₄, N₂O, SO₂, CO, HCl, NH₃, NO_x, particulate matter (PM₁₀), various heavy metals, volatile organic compounds, dioxins and benzene. The data for the site is also given by its name, sector, operator and easting-northing (for display in GIS), although no postcode or local authority column is present.</p> <p>While containing data for a large number of sites (over 5000 across the UK), it tends to contain more information on the public sector (e.g. hospitals, universities) and very large industrial sites (e.g. steel works, petrochemical processing facilities), with less information on medium sized private sector industrial facilities that could be significant users of onsite fossil fuel combustion.</p> <p>As explained on the webpage, the sources of this data are the Environment Agencies of England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland; the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register; the EU Emissions Trading Scheme; process operators; trade associations; historic regulator data (following site visits) and modelled estimates produced by Ricardo Energy Environment or internally by apportioning national emissions based on a related statistic. The excel file can be downloaded from the bottom of page for the latest 2018 dataset. The website contains other useful data under data tab (accessed via the top left of the page) such as interactive maps (for carbon emissions by sector as per the previous dataset and air pollutants), air quality data and emissions factors.</p>
Publisher	BEIS; DEFRA
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://naei.beis.gov.uk/data/map-large-source
Source	BEIS; DEFRA; Ricardo; UKCEH; Forest Research; Aether; Gluckman Consulting; Hartley McMaster LTD
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2018. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0.

https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

7.3 UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-003: UK AIR – Air Information Resource

Title	UK AIR – Air Information Resource
Creator	DEFRA
Subject	Climate; Air Quality Data; Interactive Map; Geospatial Data; Point Layer; Hourly Time Series; Daily Time Series; Annual Time Series
Description	UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-003: This website maintained by DEFRA holds a vast collection of datasets on air quality. The three broad categories of datasets are monitoring data (for over 1500 automatic and manual sites across the UK), descriptive statistics (e.g. annual means, maxima and minima) and exceedance statistics (information on levels of pollutants above a certain threshold whose metric varies). The menu on the right hand side of the page gives many additional links including a data selector, regional data, a data catalogue and spatial objects. There is also a 1 k x 1 km resolution map available for the modelled quantities of various air pollutants.
Publisher	DEFRA
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	image; dataset
Format	html; csv
Identifier	https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/data/
Source	DEFRA
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2000-2021. Updated daily.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

7.4 UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-004: Access to Healthy Assets and Hazards

Title	UK AIR – Air Information Resource
Creator	University of Liverpool
Subject	Climate; Air Quality Data; Socioeconomic Data; Health; Interactive Map; LSOA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-004: An index called Access to Healthy Assets and Hazards (AHAH) has been created by a team of researchers at the University of Liverpool. It is a multidimensional index based on four domains of accessibility: retail environment, health services, physical environment and air quality. These various health and quality of life related datasets are combined at an LSOA level.</p> <p>The original sources, their metadata and how they are inputted into the index is available for download on this page and an interactive map is also available. The air quality component is based on particulate data for PM₁₀, NO₂ and SO₂. While the other categories are quantified as follows: Retail environment (access to fast food outlets, pubs, off-licences, tobacconists and gambling outlets), Health services (access to GPs, hospitals, pharmacies, dentists and leisure services) and Physical environment (Blue Space, Green Space – Active and Green Space - Passive).</p> <p>In order to download data, an account must be registered with the CDRC (Consumer Data Research Centre). Datasets badged as open can then be downloaded simply by making an account and logging in.</p>
Publisher	CDRC
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	image; dataset
Format	html; csv
Identifier	https://data.cdrc.ac.uk/dataset/access-healthy-assets-hazards-ahah
Source	University of Liverpool
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2017.
Rights	Public data (requires sign up), Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

7.5 UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-005: Tyndall Carbon Budget Tool

Title	Tyndall Carbon Budget Tool
Creator	University of Manchester
Subject	Climate; CO2 Emissions Data; Report; Local Authority Level; Future Scenarios; Annual Time Series
Description	UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-005: The Tyndall Carbon Budget Tool has been produced by the University of Manchester. A series of reports are provided for every UK local authority, giving a scale of the decarbonisation rates required, so that each area can make its own reasonable contribution to UK carbon reduction efforts. The carbon emissions considered are terrestrial and energy related only (so are in line with BEIS statistics, while only land use and cement production are excluded). The report authors adopted a grandfathering approach to determine the fairest way to apportion the UK carbon budget rather than by population or Gross Value Added (so areas with relatively higher emissions today get a larger share of the allowed budget and vice versa). The report finds for Coventry that a yearly compound reduction in emissions of 13.1% is required to keep Coventry within its allocated budget of 8.4 Mt CO ₂ . A carbon budget approach as opposed to a net-zero target, also highlights the need for exponential as opposed to linear reductions in emissions, since a straight line with the same net-zero or 90% reduction point, will have a larger 'area under the curve', i.e. the cumulative carbon dioxide emissions over that period will be greater (Localised Sankey Diagram methodology: Coventry City Council area (link not yet publicly available)).
Publisher	University of Manchester
Contributor	
Date	2019
Type	text; image
Format	html
Identifier	https://carbonbudget.manchester.ac.uk/reports/
Source	University of Manchester; BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2017-2050.
Rights	Public data, University of Manchester.

7.6 UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-006: MIDAS Open hourly air temperature

Title	MIDAS Open hourly air temperature
Creator	University of Birmingham; Grant Wilson
Subject	Weather Data; Temperature; Hourly Time Series
Description	<p>UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-006: A form of this data has been provided through Coventry City Council but could also be obtained from the Met Office's MIDAS Open via the CEDA archive. The data is for a weather station in Coventry called Bablake in the Coundon area of the city. The Met Office has over 200 automatic weather stations across the UK (https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/weather/learn-about/how-forecasts-are-made/observations/weather-stations#:~:text=The%20Met%20Office%20has%20a,humidity%3B%20cloud%20height%20and%20visibility), so it is likely that such data should also exist for most areas and population centres in the country.</p> <p>At an hourly granularity, the columns provided include air temperature, dew point and wet bulb temperature (all in °C), as well as relative humidity in %. The data has been parsed into a single file in UTC format. The use case of this dataset can be to link it with demand for domestic heat in order to produce synthetic load profiles (e.g. for electric heat pumps or gas boilers).</p>
Publisher	ESC; University of Birmingham
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/2kr1d/midas-open-hourly-air-temperature-data
Source	CEDA; Met Office
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Bablake weather station. Coventry. Timeframe is Nov 2001-Aug 2020.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

7.7 UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-007: Renewables Ninja

Title	Renewables Ninja
Creator	ETH Zurich
Subject	Weather Data; Temperature; Irradiance; Wind; Hourly Time Series; Solar PV; Low Carbon Technologies; Interactive Map
Description	UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-007: This interactive map allows users to place a coordinate which yields the hourly output of a PV system of defined kW capacity/azimuth/tilt as a csv. Also available is the climate data (air temp, precipitation, irradiance etc.). It is a useful resource for both estimating solar PV yields and obtaining free climate data 2000-2018 (both at an hourly level). Users may sign up to get most recent data (2014 onwards) and 50 downloads per day instead of 5.
Publisher	ETH Zurich
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	https://www.renewables.ninja/
Source	NASA; MERRA; CM-SAF; SARAH
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	World. Timeframe is 2000-2018.
Rights	Public data, CC BY-NC 4.0. https://www.renewables.ninja/about

7.8 UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-008: Place-based carbon calculator

Title	Place-based carbon calculator
Creator	CREDS; University of Leeds; University of Manchester; Transport for the South East; Steer
Subject	Climate; CO ₂ Emissions Data; Interactive Map; Domestic; Gas; Electricity; Heat; Transport; Buildings; Socioeconomic Data; Consumer Behaviour; LSOA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-WEATHER-CLIMATE-008: This granular CO₂ emissions visualisation tool has been developed by a team of researchers funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). https://www.carbon.place/about.html</p> <p>It is a work in progress, but the current version allows for any LSOA in England to be selected and given a score from A+ to F- based on its per capita carbon footprint percentile relative to the national average (e.g. A+ the lowest 1% and F- the highest 1%). The scores are further segmented for each LSOA by gas, electricity, other heating, car driving, van driving, flights and consumption (of goods and services). The last two in this list are very interesting additions, as it was something the RESO project considered beyond its scope and were unaware that methodologies for estimating granular emissions data existed.</p> <p>There are other filters which may be applied to the map such as political boundaries (local authorities, parliamentary constituencies, wards and parishes), 15-minute travel areas (by various modes of transport), ONS LSOA classification, public transport stops and where there could be more cycle lanes in the future.</p> <p>It is possible that the underpinning data could be available for download as a csv when the project reaches full development; interested parties may sign up to a mailing list too.</p> <p>https://www.carbon.place/</p> <p>Another tool, IMPACT – Community carbon calculator, has been developed by CSE, BEIS, University of Exeter, Energy Hub and Nottingham City Council Energy Services. https://impact-tool.org.uk/</p> <p>This tool allows parishes or local authorities to be searched and display data for their territorial or consumption based footprints. The data is also downloadable in bulk as a csv file and a methodology paper gives the sources and techniques used. https://impact-tool.org.uk/static/doc/Impact-methodology-paper-v1.6.pdf</p>
Publisher	CREDS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	html
Identifier	https://www.carbon.place/map.html
Source	
Language	en-GB
Relation	

Coverage	England. Timeframe is 2020.
Rights	Public data, Creative Commons Licence. https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/

8 BUILDINGS

8.1 UOBDC-BUILDINGS-001: Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) database

Title	Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) database
Creator	MHCLG
Subject	Buildings; Electricity; Gas; Heat; Energy Efficiency; Retrofit; Fuel Poverty; Tenure; Building Ages; Building Type; Building Activity; Domestic; Non-domestic; Public Sector; UPRN Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-BUILDINGS-001: A growing number of domestic and non-domestic properties are now covered by Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs). These give a rating of A-G based on the costs of meeting the building's energy demand which depends on a number of factors such as lighting, heating system, building fabric and insulation measures. In general, a more modern building or one with retrofitted efficiency improvements such as double glazing or cavity wall insulation, will score better than an older dwelling without these measures. It is based on an assessment carried out in person by a certified assessor. In 2020, 66% of homes were rated EPC D or below with socially rented properties generally scoring better than privately rented or owner occupied houses.</p> <p>https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/945899/201216_BEIS_EWP_Command_Paper_Accessible.pdf</p> <p>A UK government target is to get as many homes to EPC C and above by 2035, which is set in motion by policies such as an EPC E being required to start a new let since 2018 https://www.gov.uk/guidance/domestic-private-rented-property-minimum-energy-efficiency-standard-landlord-guidance</p> <p>Similarly, public sector buildings (above a certain significance/number of visitors) must have a Display Energy Certificate (DEC), which uses a slightly different methodology, but essentially also scores a building based on its energy efficiency. EPC and DEC data is accessible through signing up for approval, after which a link to the register will be sent via email. It can be searched either manually by address, postcode or local authority, or there is also an API functionality. EPCs or DEC data can be downloaded as a csv either individually or in bulk. An explanation of the columns provided on an EPC are given in the guidance notes, as well as notes on the data quality and regulatory context (https://epc.opendatacommunities.org/docs/guidance).</p> <p>For the RESO project area of interest, the EPC addresses were matched to a record in the LLPG, so that they could be displayed on a map. This was then colour coded in the style of EPCs (e.g. dark green for A ratings and dark red for G ratings) to identify clusters of poorly performing housing stock and indicate the typical energy efficiency of a neighbourhood. Another use for this data could be to compare predicted energy use with measured consumption (e.g. BEIS or Xoserve data) or to identify areas of intervention for reducing fuel poverty; an annual gas or electricity consumption above or below the expected value could be an indicator of excessive or inadequate expenditure on energy caused by a worse building performance than predicted by its EPC or lack of income.</p>
Publisher	MHCLG

Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	https://epc.opendatacommunities.org/
Source	EPC register
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	England and Wales. Timeframe is 2008-2020. Updated every 2 months.
Rights	Public data (requires sign up), Royal Mail (address and postcode columns), Open Government Licence v3.0 (all other columns). https://epc.opendatacommunities.org/docs/copyright

8.2 UOBDC-BUILDINGS-002: Dwelling Age Group Counts

Title	Dwelling Age Group Counts
Creator	University College London
Subject	Buildings; Energy Efficiency; Retrofit; Building Ages; LSOA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-BUILDINGS-002: This interactive map and accompanying dataset (compiled by UCL) are useful for understanding the age distribution of the domestic building stock within a local authority and total number of properties in a local authority, by aggregating up from the LSOA granularity it is presented in. Particularly for the creation of a local Sankey diagram, it aids in the calculation of insulation savings through cavity wall insulation (homes built before 1930 are generally not deemed suitable for CWI) and solid wall insulation (generally the type of insulation most suitable for homes built before 1930). In a more detailed model, perhaps linking with the EPC database, this dataset could add potentially more value in terms of the links between the energy efficiency of domestic buildings and their age distribution, beyond just one cut of date at 1930 (Localised Sankey Diagram methodology: Coventry City Council area (link not yet publicly available)).</p> <p>Like other CDRC datasets, users must sign up to be able to download. It is based on data held by the Valuation Office Agency and the Land Registry. Also available (although perhaps of less direct use for energy analytics) are the quarterly median house prices and transactions. The build periods are as follows: pre-1900, 1900-1919, 1920-1929, 1930-1939, 1945-1954, 1955-1964, 1965-1972, 1973-1982, 1983-1992, 1993-1999, 2000-2009, 2010-2015 and unknown period. There are also columns for the first and second modal periods, their percentages of total dwellings and ratio of the second modal percentage of total to the first modal percentage of total.</p>
Publisher	CDRC
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset; image
Format	csv; html
Identifier	https://data.cdrc.ac.uk/dwelling-ages-and-prices
Source	HR Land Registry; VOA
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	England and Wales. Timeframe is pre-1900-2015.
Rights	Public data (requires sign up), Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

8.3 UOBDC-BUILDINGS-003: New Build Dwellings Data

Title	New Build Dwellings Data
Creator	MHCLG
Subject	Buildings; New Builds; Domestic; Energy Efficiency; Retrofit; Building Ages; Local Authority Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-BUILDINGS-003: This data published by MHCLG gives sets of statistics on the housing supply in local authorities across the UK. The statistics likely to be of particular use concern those around the building of new houses and who they were built by (private sector, housing association or local authority). Table 253 gives the data for dwellings started and dwellings completed in England for each year from 1980-81 to 2019-20 (235a has quarterly rather than annual figures). On the other hand, Tables 214, 215 and 216 give the data for Wales, Scotland and Northern Ireland quarterly from Q1 1978 to Q1 2019. These sets for the devolved nations were actually discontinued in 2019 and will now be accessed through the respective nation's statistical agency.</p> <p>https://statswales.gov.wales/Catalogue/Housing/New-House-Building</p> <p>https://www.gov.scot/publications/housing-statistics-for-scotland-new-house-building/</p> <p>https://www.communities-ni.gov.uk/topics/housing-statistics</p> <p>In terms of energy, it could be a good cross reference with other datasets (EPCs and Dwelling Ages Counts) to see the percentage of homes in a local authority built in recent years. In addition, the trends could give some indication of the expected number of houses to be built in the near future, although perhaps not as accurately as the Local Plan which is statutory.</p>
Publisher	MHCLG
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	ods
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistical-data-sets/live-tables-on-house-building
Source	MHCLG
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	England. Timeframe is 1980-2019. Updated annually.
Rights	<p>Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0.</p> <p>https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/</p>

8.4 UOBDC-BUILDINGS-004: Coventry Local Plan

Title	Coventry Local Plan
Creator	CCC
Subject	Buildings; New Builds; Domestic; Non-domestic; Socioeconomic; Energy Efficiency; Retrofit; Generation Data; Low Carbon Technologies; Local Authority Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-BUILDINGS-004: Local plans are written documents developed by a local authority through a consultation with their community which set out a vision for the future development of an area and serve as a statutory plan, the first point of reference for which future planning applications will be assessed against.</p> <p>https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/582669/Local_Development_Documents_policy_factsheet.pdf</p> <p>It is intended for all local authorities in England to have one, Scotland and Wales having their own devolved planning systems. At the turn of 2017, 70% of English local authorities had a local plan in place, rising to 90% by 2020. So although they may be subject to revisions and updates, encouraged by government to take place every 5 years, they do set a strong direction of travel for how the local authority views the issue of future developments. It is likely DFES will be drawing on the figures for their own projections of new domestic properties and commercial floor space by primary substation area. Finally, at a smaller level of geography, there is another type of planning document called a neighbourhood plan. These can be initiated by a town or parish council, neighbourhood forum or community group, and once approved by a referendum have the same legal status as a local plan.</p> <p>https://www.gov.uk/guidance/neighbourhood-planning--2</p> <p>With specific regard to the RESO project, the Coventry Local Plan (along with other information on developments held by the council) has been useful for determining the allocation of new buildings and their effect on the electricity network by their situated primary substation area. The Coventry document from 2017 outlines planning policies pertaining to the local governance of Coventry City Council until 2031. Particularly relevant could be pages 57-59, showing site allocations for 10,060 of the 24,600 new homes proposed to be built between 2017 and 2031. Also relevant are, on pages 82-83, the allocation of additional retail space and pages 43-44, the allocation of 107 hectares for employment purposes. These could potentially be displayed geospatially, by drawing approximate polygons in GIS software. Furthermore, there is appetite from the Council in Coventry to build on its vehicle industry heritage and be placed at the heart of opportunities brought about by the coming Green Industrial Revolution, e.g. in terms of trying to attract a gigafactory for the manufacturing of EV batteries.</p> <p>https://www.coventry.gov.uk/news/article/3588/coventry_and_warwickshire_ready_for_electric_vehicle_revolution</p>
Publisher	CCC
Contributor	
Date	2017
Type	text
Format	pdf

Identifier	https://www.coventry.gov.uk/downloads/file/25899/final_local_plan_december_2017
Source	CCC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry. Timeframe is 2018-2031. Potentially updated every 5 years.
Rights	Public data, CCC. https://www.coventry.gov.uk/custom/terms

8.5 UOBDC-BUILDINGS-005: Building Energy Efficiency Survey Sector Tables (BEES)

Title	Building Energy Efficiency Survey Sector Tables (BEES)
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Buildings; Non-domestic; Building Activity; Energy Efficiency; Retrofit; Electricity; Gas; Heat
Description	<p>UOBDC-BUILDINGS-005: These datasets by BEIS are based on a survey conducted in 2014-15 with 3690 participants (including interviews and site visits) across 10 sectors and 38 sub-sectors of non-domestic energy consumers. It seeks to understand how energy (both electrical and non-electrical, i.e. gas) is used and the potential for abatement through various measures.</p> <p>It is useful for comparing the energy intensity in kWh/m² for either electricity or non-electrical energy, or for its end use (e.g. space heating, hot water, lighting, catering etc.) for different types of buildings based on their activity or floor area. Distributions are also given for the energy intensity of each subsector (10th percentile, lower quartile, median, upper quartile and 90th percentile), as well as capital costs and greenhouse gas savings of potential abatement. It is also noteworthy that analysis excludes energy for processes in the industrial sector (i.e. it just accounts for the building's energy demands not the demand from manufacturing).</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2016
Type	dataset; text
Format	xlsx; pdf
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/building-energy-efficiency-survey-bees
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	England and Wales. Timeframe is 2014-2015.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

8.6 UOBDC-BUILDINGS-006: Valuation Office Agency (VOA) rating list

Title	Valuation Office Agency (VOA) rating list
Creator	VOA; HMRC
Subject	Buildings; Non-domestic; Building Activity; UPRN Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-BUILDINGS-006: The VOA is an agency of HM Revenue & Customs responsible for setting the value of properties and their liability for council tax (most domestic properties) and business rates (most non-domestic properties). The amount to be paid ultimately depends on factors such as the market value of the house or floor areas/nature of activities within a commercial premises.</p> <p>The VOA rating list covers around 2 million non-domestic properties in England and Wales. 80% of records are based on site building surveys whereas 20% are based on specialised surveys/construction costs/annual accounts.</p> <p>https://voaratinglists.blob.core.windows.net/html/documents/2017%20Compiled%20List%20and%20SMV%20Data%20Specification.pdf</p> <p>This list can be downloaded on the page in csv form by accepting the terms and conditions. Under the epochs heading, there are two types of list for 2010 and 2017, the entries and the summary evaluations (the latter being more rich as it includes data for the floor areas by activity and rateable values). There are also some updated entries and valuations able to be downloaded below the change updates heading. It is planned to compile an entirely new list for 2022.</p> <p>The files are large; 2017 summary evaluations is approximately 1 GB uncompressed and contains too many rows to be fully displayed in Microsoft Excel 2016. Furthermore, despite being a csv when unzipped, the files are asterisk delimited as opposed to comma delimited, which means some parsing may be required to fully utilise the data. The lack of column headers does limit the ability to quickly read values, however, these can be determined from the technical guide, linked at the bottom of their page (API usage is also encouraged). More immediately human readable data could alternatively be accessed from local councils themselves in pdf format, as is the case for Coventry (although this lacks the level detail on, for example, floor spaces).</p> <p>https://www.coventry.gov.uk/downloads/file/25291/non_domestic_rates_-_full_rating_list_from_voa</p> <p>Nevertheless the full dataset in its richness has many uses for energy researchers. Deeper insight on building use than in the LLPG alone (e.g. different activities in different stories/areas of a single floor) can be used to produce more accurate models of the energy demands of non-domestic buildings as per the 3D stock model developed by UCL.</p> <p>https://journal-buildingscities.org/articles/10.5334/bc.52/</p> <p>In addition, the information provided on land for car parking can help understand the potential for workplace or public EV charging. Finally, what is really valuable about this dataset, is that each property has an identifier called a Unique Address Reference Number all of which have been linked to the widely used UPRN through AddressBase Premium (and then can subsequently be merged with LLPGs). The presence of identifiers linked to an easting/northing, therefore, helps facily display the premises geospatially as opposed to having to derive the co-ordinates from the address alone (as was possible through manipulating strings in the domestic EPC database, then</p>

	merging with the LLPG with a match rate of 88%; although it can be possible to skip this step and get the data directly from OS on request). https://www.geoplace.co.uk/blog/2018/persistent-and-well-behaved-identifiers
Publisher	VOA; HMRC
Contributor	
Date	2017
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	https://voaringlists.blob.core.windows.net/html/rlidata.htm
Source	VOA; HMRC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	England and Wales. Timeframe is 2017. Updated every 5-7 years.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0, VOA. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/ https://www.tax.service.gov.uk/business-rates-find/terms-and-conditions

8.7 UOBDC-BUILDINGS-007: UK Buildings

Title	UK Buildings
Creator	Geomni
Subject	Buildings; Domestic; Non-domestic; Building Age; Building Type; Building Activity; Energy Efficiency; Geospatial Data; Polygon Layer; UPRN Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-BUILDINGS-007: Created by Geomni and based on aerial imagery as well as published open data, this geospatial dataset contains a layer of polygons to represent the nation's building stock and provide information on each building's use, age and other attributes. Previous versions only covered urban areas with more than 10,000 residents, but the latest release covers the entire of Great Britain and the Belfast urban area of Northern Ireland (however, the most detailed data is only available for 500 urban areas). In addition to age and use, this part of the layer has information on the number of floors, floor area and structure for each address, right down to the level of wall type, insulation measures fitted, rooms of each type and whether a basement or open fireplace is present. It also has the UPRNs and TOIDs for each object, where appropriate, which allows for integration with other datasets that relate to those identifiers. The structure of the data is such that a building is defined as a continuous block of premises (e.g. dwelling footprints) and addresses (e.g. dwellings with a UPRN), with premises being a subset of buildings (and occasionally addresses being a subset of premises in the case of converted flats). The meaningful data on the topics discussed is given on a per address basis.</p> <p>Geomni encourage interested parties to get in touch to discuss their requirements and can prepare a bespoke quotation to enable access to the prospective user. Different payment rates will apply depending on nature of intended use (e.g. a licence for education or non-commercial research at a university will be less costly than one for commercial research at a for-profit organisation). It is made available to some universities through the EDINA platform, although this is not as rich as the full version (for example, UPRNs are not included as an attribute, nor is there the level of detail on the characteristics of the buildings). In addition, sample data may be obtained for a small area (approx. 4 km²) upon request via email, as well as a full reference guide to explain the various data column headers.</p> <p>As a result of the level of detail, there is excellent scope for this dataset to enable energy modelling and research. It has been used by a group at UCL as an input for their 3-D stock energy model of London (https://journal-buildingscities.org/articles/10.5334/bc.52/). Alternatively, it could be used in tandem with the LLPG to cross reference information such as the building use, UPRN or through a matching UPRN, allocate an address to the UKBuildings object. This could then enable matching with address string based datasets such as the EPC database, and be another aesthetic way to visualise building performance. Furthermore, the buildings with their addresses and postcodes could be used to approximate the meters from BEIS statistics to physical locations, as well as locating buildings to LV substation areas using the WPD data on how many customers there are per LV substation. Finally, the BEES tables could be used to estimate the energy use of non-domestic buildings and compare with the metered gas and electricity consumption statistics published by BEIS at MSOA level.</p>
Publisher	Geomni
Contributor	

Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	gpkg
Identifier	https://www.geomni.co.uk/ukbuildings
Source	Geomni
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2020.
Rights	The Geoinformation Group Limited, non-public data, only for institutions subscribed to EDINA. https://digimap.edina.ac.uk/webhelp/digimapsupport/license_and_terms_of_service/geomni_eula_aug2020.pdf

8.8 UOBDC-BUILDINGS-008: OS Mastermap (Topography and Building Height Attribute)

Title	OS Mastermap (Topography and Building Height Attribute)
Creator	OS
Subject	Buildings; Domestic; Non-domestic; Roads; Geospatial Data; Polygon Layer; UPRN Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-BUILDINGS-008: This geospatial layer produced by OS is a highly detailed and accurate map of the land and streets covering Great Britain which is updated every 6 weeks. It is based on a vector layer consisting of polygons, lines and points that represent a number of topographic features (roads, buildings, fields, woodland, paths, fences etc.). Each surface or object is classified into a descriptive group and given an unambiguous TOID (topographic identifier), as well as spot heights for land, so that the terrain can be visualised. There is also an additional sublayer called Building Height Attribute.</p> <p>https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/mastermap-building</p> <p>This is particular dataset is useful for interpreting and visualising urban topographies in 3-D as it contains information on the heights of buildings under five different metrics: ground level (AbsHMin), base of the roof (AbsH2), highest part of the roof (AbsHMax), relative height from the ground to the base of the roof (RelH2) and relative height from the ground to the highest part of the roof (RelHMax).</p> <p>https://digimap.edina.ac.uk/webhelp/os/data_information/os_products/os_building_heights.htm</p> <p>The layer can also account for fine detail such as chimneys, extensions to a building or sheds.</p> <p>The uses of these datasets could be to assess sites for renewable energy infrastructure, off-street EV charging or determine the floor space of a building (by estimating its number of stories and multiplying by the footprint area) in order to model its thermal properties which could be compared with real consumption data or EPCs. An example of this kind of analysis is the work carried out by Moreno et al, which compared the theoretical energy demand of LSOAs (based on their constituent buildings' heights and footprints from OS, along with other typologies) to the metered consumption published at the same geography by BEIS.</p> <p>https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344429469_Mapping_Priority_Energy_Intervention_Areas_in_Birmingham_UK</p> <p>As with the other OS geospatial data, it is available to most universities through Digimap and to public sector and commercial organisations under the previously described terms. Sample data is also available for download by selecting the tab with that title. As well as this dataset, the OS offer other layers for open access (which can be found in their complete products list page) including: Open UPRN, Open USRN, Open TOID and Open Linked Identifiers which make the identifiers available for each property, street, topographic object and in Linked Identifiers, the relationship between them as well as their metadata. Additionally, Open Roads, Open Rivers and Open Greenspace serve as streamlined versions of their respective non-open sets. Finally, other notable premium datasets in this collection include OS VectorMap Local (similar to MasterMap</p>

	<p>Topography but with an included raster layer), OS MasterMap Water Network Layer and MasterMap Greenspace Layer. The latter two give more detail than their open sets, such as the flow rate and gradient of each river section, and the function of every green space (e.g. allotment, sports field etc.).</p> <p>https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products</p>
Publisher	OS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	GML; csv
Identifier	https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/mastermap-topography
Source	OS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2019-2020. Updated every 6 weeks.
Rights	OS, non-public data, only for institutions subscribed to EDINA. https://digimap.edina.ac.uk/webhelp/os/copyright/licence_agreement.htm

8.9 UOBDC-BUILDINGS-009: EPC-UPRN list of mappings

Title	EPC-UPRN list of mappings
Creator	OS
Subject	Buildings; Electricity; Gas; Heat; Energy Efficiency; Retrofit; Fuel Poverty; Tenure; Building Ages; Building Type; Building Activity; Domestic; UPRN Level Geospatial Data
Description	<p>UOBDC-BUILDINGS-009: It was found in a 2018 article by GeoPlace that OS holds a record link between the LMK_KEY unique identifiers of an EPC and the UPRN used in AddressBase Premium and council LLPGs. Importantly this UPRN is not the same as the BUILDING_REFERENCE_NUMBER used in EPCs.</p> <p>https://www.geoplace.co.uk/blog/2018/persistent-and-well-behaved-identifiers</p> <p>Therefore, to improve on the address string matching method used previously (with an accuracy of 88% for Coventry), the identifier linkage data was then obtained from the OS by making a direct request through their contact form.</p> <p>https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/contact-us</p> <p>Two versions of csv files were received with geographical coverage of the entire CV postcode area. The file contained the full amount of LMK_KEY digits linked to UPRN and postcode. These were then merged, first with the bulk EPC downloads for Coventry and surrounding local authorities, before being combined with the LLPG. This allowed for a higher matching rate than the previous attempt (99.7%). However, it was further found that sometimes the local authority or postcode in the EPC doesn't equal the local authority or postcode in the LLPG, highlighting further inconsistencies between datasets of different sources.</p>
Publisher	OS
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	Not publicly available
Source	OS; MHCLG
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	CV postcode area. Timeframe is 2007-2020.
Rights	OS, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

9 GEOGRAPHY

9.1 UOBDC-GEO-001: Coventry Online Planning Map

Title	Coventry Online Planning Map
Creator	CCC
Subject	Buildings; Domestic; Non-domestic; Roads; Future Scenarios; New Builds; Interactive Map; Geospatial Data; Point Layer
Description	<p>UOBDC-GEO-001: This interactive map of Coventry is available to the public to show various planning measures across the local authority area. Set against the back drop of a high resolution Ordnance Survey map, the following map layers are available: adopted highways, bridge structures, building control (current and historical), conservation and heritage, constraints, parish/ward boundaries, planning applications (current, enforcement and historical), policy, public rights of way (actual and claimed), section 106 and tree preservation orders. There is also a query tab (the plus sign in the top right of the page) which can be used to bring up a list of the desired objects, and can be downloaded as a csv (with eastings/northings for display in GIS).</p> <p>The Coventry portal is quite user friendly, and it is likely other local authorities will have the same knowledge displayed in some similar or dissimilar form (perhaps as .pdfs). Even if the information is not available to the public online, it must exist, in which case the local authority may be requested to share it. Knowledge of the local planning system can have an effect on energy projects, such as knowing which areas may be more or less suitable to renewable energy infrastructure. In addition, knowing the location of parking restrictions/dropped kerbs could help with EV infrastructure planning.</p>
Publisher	CCC
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	image; dataset
Format	html; csv
Identifier	https://www.coventry.gov.uk/info/110/planning/1333/online_planning_map
Source	CCC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry. Timeframe is 1990-2021.
Rights	Public data, CCC. https://www.coventry.gov.uk/info/110/planning/1333/online_planning_map/5

9.2 UOBDC-GEO-002: Local Authority Transparency Land and Property list 2018

Title	Local Authority Transparency Land and Property list 2018
Creator	CCC
Subject	Buildings; Non-domestic; Public Sector; Geospatial Data; Point Layer; UPRN Level
Description	UOBDC-GEO-002: This publicly available csv gives information on all the land and property owned by Coventry City Council as of 2018. The information includes: the unique property reference number (UPRN), the internal council UPRN, property name, address, postcode, type of tenure, building area, site area and the easting-northing coordinates (used for locating the objects in GIS). Despite not having information on the energy demand of the buildings, this can be useful for identifying the council's assets and potential for investing in renewable generation. Such analysis for schools has been conducted internally to the RESO project. Furthermore, through GIS, the primary substation to which each asset connects to can be identified, so the impact on the electrical network of additional demand or generation at a council owned site can be considered. It is likely all councils will have this type of information, either publicly available or held internally, so it might be necessary to make a request to a local authority's estates team to obtain the dataset.
Publisher	CCC
Contributor	
Date	2018
Type	dataset
Format	csv
Identifier	https://www.coventry.gov.uk/downloads/file/23571/la-transparency-data-land-and-property
Source	CCC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry. Timeframe is 2018.
Rights	Public data, CCC. https://www.coventry.gov.uk/custom/terms

9.3 UOBDC-GEO-003: Coventry Local Land and Property Gazetteer

Title	Coventry Local Land and Property Gazetteer
Creator	CCC
Subject	Buildings; Domestic; Non-domestic; Building Type; Building Activity; Geospatial Data; Point Layer; UPRN Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GEO-003: Local land and property gazetteers (LLPG) are central corporate databases which contain information for all addresses within a local authority boundary. It has a number of practical applications such as avoiding errors within a local authority's electoral registers or council tax records. Each address has an unambiguous defining code known as a unique property reference number (UPRN) and it is a statutory duty of authorities to maintain these records.</p> <p>https://www.geoplace.co.uk/local-authority-resources/guidance-for-custodians/how-to/about-the-role/what-is-an-llpg</p> <p>The LLPG for Coventry takes the form of a large csv file with approximately 170,000 objects, including domestic/non-domestic buildings as well as pieces of land, streets, infrastructure and signage. Importantly, it contains an easting-northing for each object, so may be imported as a vector layer of points in GIS, along with the address and postcode. Other noteworthy fields include: LPI_RECORD_STATUS, whether the object's address status is approved, alternative or historical which means some objects have more than one entry but the same UPRN; USRN, unique street reference number, like a UPRN but for streets and BLPU_CLASS. BLPU_CLASS is an alphanumeric code that gives information on the use of the object. For example, RD04 signifies a residential dwelling that is a terraced house and CI01 indicates a commercial industrial building that is a factory or manufacturing centre. Some entries only have partial information such as CI (so it is known to be an industrial building, but further knowledge on the activities within the building are missing). The full list of code definitions can be found in GeoPlace Data Entry Conventions and Best Practice for Addresses.</p> <p>https://s3.eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/static.geoplace.co.uk/downloads/GeoPlace-DEC-Addresses-v3.4-2016.pdf?version=1.5&previewFileIndex=</p> <p>This geospatial dataset has been of great importance for the RESO project as it has enabled a deeper analysis of the local building stock. The following tasks have been carried out: counting the number of different building types in a primary substation area, mapping the addresses to certificates in the EPC database and allocating postcodes to a primary substation area. All of these have allowed for the greater understanding of the energy demand of an electrical primary substation area, both in terms of annual figures and a time series profile. In particular, visualising the building level EPCs as colour-coded points has helped identify clusters of poorly insulated homes and target them for support under the Green Homes Grant scheme. Furthermore, mapping postcodes to a primary substation has allowed BEIS postcode level gas consumption statistics to be aggregated to a primary level, which can help show the scale of the vector shifting required to decarbonise heat (potentially through electrification).</p> <p>One drawback of the LLPG is that it does not contain information on building footprints or floor areas. However, this information could be inferred from the overlapping polygons on another layer (e.g. UK Buildings) or by comparing with the EPC data, if one exists for that object. The LLPGs of the UK feed into to a National Land and Property Gazetteer covering the entire country, which in turn and along with input from Ordnance</p>

	<p>Survey, GeoPlace, and Royal Mail's Postcode Address File derives the AddressBase Premium dataset.</p> <p>https://www.aligned-assets.co.uk/products/addressbase-premium-data/</p> <p>Despite not being publicly available, if it is desired to undertake a similar analysis of a local authority area, then the relevant department at the local authority should be contacted for discussion of access; it is likely that a licence agreement may need to be arranged.</p>
Publisher	CCC
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	DAT; MAP
Identifier	https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/e6d9z/coventry-llpg
Source	CCC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry. Timeframe is 2020.
Rights	<p>CCC, Local Government Information House Ltd, OS, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.</p> <p>Public Sector Mapping Agreement. For the full licence terms contact Coventry City Council.</p>

9.4 UOBDC-GEO-004: AddressBase Premium

Title	AddressBase Premium
Creator	OS
Subject	Buildings; Domestic; Non-domestic; Building Type; Building Activity; Geospatial Data; Point Layer; UPRN Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GEO-004: As previously discussed AddressBase Premium is a point based geospatial file which is an amalgamation of the nation's LLPGs along with input from OS, GeoPlace and the Royal Mail's Postcode Address File. There are four tiers of the product available (in ascending order of detail and interoperability with other datasets): AddressBase, AddressBase Core, AddressBase Plus and AddressBase Premium. There are also the Plus and Premium Islands datasets (which cover Northern Ireland, the Isle of Man and the Channel Islands). As with the other OS geospatial datasets, the licensing conditions for access vary between the public and private sector (public sector mapping agreement vs. a framework contract), and exploratory/sample datasets are available.</p> <p>Through a licence from the Council, the RESO project was able to obtain AddressBase Premium csv files for eight 5 x 5 km grids (denoted by their bottom leftmost OS grid reference 1 x 1 km square). A getting started guide and technical specification was also provided; these are both publicly accessible under the product's support page.</p> <p>https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/tools-support/addressbase-support</p> <p>The data seemed initially in a more complicated format than the LLPG, but header files were provided which explained the structure. The data is laid out such that the first column of each row has a numerical code (e.g. 11) and the row of length of X will have the headers as described in the accompanying csv file with that numerical code. Finally, the AddressBase Premium may provide more value to researchers than an LLPG alone because in certain cases it can link to other identifiers such as the TOID used by OS and UARN used by the Valuation Office Agency.</p> <p>https://www.geoplace.co.uk/blog/2018/persistent-and-well-behaved-identifiers</p>
Publisher	OS
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	GML; csv
Identifier	https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/addressbase-premium
Source	OS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2021. Updated every 6 weeks.
Rights	OS, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

	Public Sector Mapping Agreement. For the full licence terms contact Coventry City Council.
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9.5 UOBDC-GEO-005: Code-Point Open and Code-Point with Polygons

Title	Code-Point Open and Code-Point with Polygons
Creator	OS
Subject	Geospatial Data; Point Layer; Polygon Layer; Postcode Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GEO-005: This geospatial data from OS contains the postcodes of the UK as layers for analysis in GIS. There are three datasets available: code-point open, code-point and code-point with polygons. The first of these is open data, available for anyone to download. Code-point only contains the centre point of postcodes themselves as a point layer and is available as a csv or Geopackage file. In this regard, it may be viewed as similar to the NSPL centroids. Code-point and code-point with polygons are premium datasets. There are three types of licenses: commercial, public sector or media/publishing. The public sector geospatial mapping agreement covers those organisations, whereas commercial entities require framework and data contracts, though the data may be sampled for free under an exploration licence. The University of Birmingham has access through Digimap (part of the University of Edinburgh's EDINA service).</p> <p>Code-point contains a point layer but with additional information such as the breakdown of commercial and residential addresses in each postcode (on average each UK postcode contains 15 separate addresses). Unlike the open dataset it also covers Northern Ireland as well as GB. On the other hand, the 'with polygons' dataset includes the outline shapes of each postcode, including large buildings with multiple postcodes. The files for the polygons are available in ERSI shapefile and MapInfo (MID/MIF or TAB) formats. As with the Open Geography data, the code-point polygons can be useful for producing choropleths of BEIS postcode level gas/electricity consumption statistics. In the RESO project, one such colour coded map was made to show the decrease or increase in the mean annual electricity consumption of postcodes over the time period 2013-18.</p>
Publisher	OS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	csv; gpkg; shp; MID/MIF; MAP; TAB
Identifier	https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/business-government/products/code-point-open
Source	OS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2020. Updated quarterly.
Rights	Open: Public data, OS, Royal Mail, Open Government Licence v3.0. http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

	<p>With Polygons: OS, non-public data, only for institutions subscribed to EDINA. https://digimap.edina.ac.uk/webhelp/os/copyright/licence_agreement.htm</p>
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9.6 UOBDC-GEO-006: Open Geography Portal

Title	Open Geography Portal
Creator	ONS
Subject	Geospatial Data; Point Layer; Polygon Layer; Local Authority Level; MSOA Level; LSOA Level; OA Level; Postcode Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GEO-006: The ONS has launched an Open Geography Portal to act as a free and open point of access for geospatial data in the UK. Expanding the Boundaries tab at the top of the page will show the datasets available for download. There are 7 submenus in this dropdown list including: Administrative Boundaries, Census Boundaries, Electoral Boundaries, Eurostat Boundaries, Health Boundaries, Other Boundaries and Centroids. The administrative section consists of boundaries such as counties, local authority areas and parishes. Census covers output areas (OA/LSOA/MSOA) and other geographies used by ONS. Electoral refers to entities used in elections, like Westminster parliamentary constituencies. Eurostat uses the Nomenclature des Unités territoriales statistiques (NUTS) regions to split the UK into statistical areas. Health means boundaries used by the NHS such as clinical commissioning groups and sustainability and transformation partnerships. Other boundaries include areas such as local enterprise partnerships (LEPs). And finally, centroids contains the geometric centre of postcodes or OA/LSOA/MSOAs after applying a weighting for population distribution. The postcodes are available in three forms from three sources: the National Statistics Postcode Lookup, ONS Postcode Directory and NHS Postcode Directory. Unlike the other boundaries which will be polygons when loaded into GIS, the centroids are points.</p> <p>When selected, each file may be downloaded as either a csv spreadsheet, KML or shapefile. There is also an API explorer to allow the data to be queried. These boundaries and centroids are very useful in GIS for displaying energy data at chosen granularities. For example, the electricity or gas consumption by LSOA as published by BEIS can be coupled with these boundaries to produce choropleths. Such diagrams could be useful for identifying clusters of high density domestic heat loads (in kWh/year/km²), and potentially the location of future district heat networks. Alternatively, postcode level consumption data can be mapped to the centroids and can also be overlaid with the primary substation boundaries from WPD to gain information about the statistical regions within that area, be that LSOA or postcode. This data can then be aggregated to a primary substation area to determine its characteristics.</p>
Publisher	ONS
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	csv; kml; shp
Identifier	https://geoportal.statistics.gov.uk/
Source	ONS
Language	en-GB

Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2011 (MSOAs/LSOAs/OAs) and 2021 (postcodes).
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0 (unless stated otherwise). http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

9.7 UOBDC-GEO-007: INSPIRE Polygons

Title	INSPIRE Polygons
Creator	HM Land Registry
Subject	Geospatial Data; Polygon Layer; Freeholds; UPRN Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-GEO-007: This data shows the outlines of plots of registered freehold ownerships in England and Wales (in most cases the plot of land around a house for which the owner is responsible). It comes in .gml format for GIS analysis and is available to download separately for each local authority. INSPIRE is an open source collection of data which came about from a 2007 EU directive, Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community.</p> <p>https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=OJ%3AL%3A2007%3A108%3ATOC</p> <p>It is based on records held by HM Land Registry and each polygon has a unique identification number called the Land Registry-INSPIRE ID. Using the Coventry layer as example, it appears to have good coverage (>75%) of the local authority by area and an excellent rate of the domestic properties included. Of the areas that are uncovered, it is likely that they are either an unregistered piece of land or have an alternative registration arrangement such as a leasehold.</p> <p>https://use-land-property-data.service.gov.uk/datasets/inspire</p> <p>There is little data associated with each polygon (e.g. nothing about the ownership details) but this additional information can be obtained for individual polygons through a Land Registry search for a fee.</p> <p>One application of this data, which has been developed by the Energy Systems Catapult, is to use the INSPIRE polygons in combination with building footprints to determine the space available for off-street parking for every dwelling in the RESO area. This analysis formed part of the Coventry LEAR and is a valuable piece of knowledge for considering the future location of EVs and EV charging infrastructure (e.g. homes with driveways may be able to charge off-street whereas those without may have to charge on-street or at a public station).</p>
Publisher	HM Land Registry
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	GML
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/guidance/inspire-index-polygons-spatial-data
Source	HM Land Registry
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	England and Wales. Timeframe is 2020. Updated monthly.
Rights	Public data, OS, Open Government Licence v3.0.

https://use-land-property-data.service.gov.uk/datasets/inspire#use the data

9.8 UOBDC-GEO-008: Lidar

Title	Lidar
Creator	Environment Agency
Subject	Geospatial Data; Aerial Survey; Raster Layer; Point Layer
Description	<p>UOBDC-GEO-008: Lidar is a form of measuring distances that uses light from lasers (as opposed to radar which uses radio waves). When carried out from above the Earth's surface, images can be produced to visualise the topography of the land. The UK Environment Agency aims to have an accurate Lidar map of the entire UK by 2021 at 1 m x 1 m resolution as a result of surveys carried out since 2016 in 230 logical blocks of the country.</p> <p>There are 4 different datasets: Digital Terrain Model (DTM), Digital Surface Model (DSM), Point Cloud and Aerial Imagery. The DTM layer is a layout of the ground's elevation accounting for features such as rivers and ridges, with surface objects such as buildings or vegetation removed. On the other hand, DSM accounts for these types of objects, allowing the urban topography to be visualised in 3-D.</p> <p>https://geodetics.com/dem-dsm-dtm-digital-elevation-models/#:~:text=%E2%80%93%20DSM%20(Digital%20Surface%20Model,such%20as%20rivers%20and%20ridges.</p> <p>While DTM and DSM are raster layers, the 3-D point cloud is a collection of individual (x, y and z) measurements that are used to generate the terrain and surface visualisations. The cloud consists of billions of these measurements at a high degree of accuracy.</p> <p>https://data.gov.uk/dataset/977a4ca4-1759-4f26-baa7-b566bd7ca7bf/lidar-point-cloud</p> <p>Finally, the Environment Agency has made available aerial imagery at 10-50 cm resolution, photographed between 2006 and 2017 in either full colour (RGB), near infrared (NIR) or RGBN (a combination of visible colours and near infrared).</p> <p>These datasets are available to some universities through the EDINA Digimap service, but as they are under the Open Government Licence, the same data may be accessible to the public via gov.uk (the identifier for this dataset). The Environment Agency has an interactive map from which the data can be queried, either by drawing a polygon or uploading a shapefile, to select the desired 5 km x 5 km squares (given in OS grid notation).</p> <p>Use cases in energy planning for LIDAR have been proposed such as modelling the energy demands of buildings based on their shape, or potentially identifying parked cars which would be an alternative way to assess the opportunities for on/off-street EV charging (although exploratory analysis in the RESO area found the resolution to be insufficient). Nevertheless, the analysis could be conducted by machine learning techniques, to pattern recognise certain features and find estimates for their counts within a given geographical area. Also, depending on the quality of the data and wavelengths observed, the infrared images could indicate the thermal properties of an urban area, which could potentially identify poorly insulated neighbourhoods.</p>
Publisher	Environment Agency
Contributor	

Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	GML; shp; kmz; gdb; MID/MIF; TAB; json
Identifier	https://data.gov.uk/dataset/f0db0249-f17b-4036-9e65-309148c97ce4/national-lidar-programme
Source	Environment Agency
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2006-2021.
Rights	Public data, OS, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/ https://support.environment.data.gov.uk/hc/en-gb/articles/360015443132-Terms-and-Conditions

9.9 UOBDC-GEO-009: Aerial Images

Title	Aerial Images
Creator	Getmapping
Subject	Geospatial Data; Aerial Survey; Raster Layer
Description	<p>UOBDC-GEO-009: Getmapping offer high resolution aerial imagery of the entire of GB at a resolution of up to 5 cm in London, 12.5 cm in most of the UK and 25 cm in North Wales, and the Scottish Borders and Highlands. As a commercial service, in order to access their data, an area can either be drawn to produce a pricing for the given images or, as is more likely to be the case for researchers and parties with similar interests, an enquiry can be made to discuss a bespoke quotation. The raster layers are compatible with GIS software and the following formats are available: JPEG, geoTIFF and ECW.</p> <p>https://www.getmapping.com/products-and-services/aerial-imagery-data</p> <p>Getmapping have also made their 25 cm resolution imagery available through the EDINA Digimap service, so that researchers at subscribed institutions can access the data free of charge. Since the data is updated every 3-5 years, an archive of aerial imagery exists which dates back to 1999. This means new developments and infrastructure (e.g. renewable generation) can be identified as well as a possible range of time for their construction. Furthermore, as with the Lidar data, this detailed imagery has potential to be used by machine learning algorithms for identifying relevant assets (e.g. off-street parking, solar PV) for energy analysis, especially due to its potentially higher resolution in some areas (these areas seem to be linked to flood risk).</p>
Publisher	Getmapping
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	jpeg; geoTIFF; ECW
Identifier	https://digimap.edina.ac.uk/aerial
Source	Getmapping
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 1999-2021. Updated every 3-5 years.
Rights	Getmapping, non-public data, only for institutions subscribed to EDINA. https://digimap.edina.ac.uk/webhelp/aerial/licence/digimap_aerial_eula.pdf

9.10 UOBDC-GEO-010: Coventry LEAR mappings

Title	Coventry LEAR mappings
Creator	ESC
Subject	Mappings; LSOA Level; Primary Substation Level
Description	UOBDC-GEO-010: This dataset was provided via a follow up request to the ESC. Data in the LEAR is given mostly at two different geographical levels, either LSOA or primary substation area. However, as is clear, these two boundaries do not overlap cleanly (one coming from census statistical areas and the other originating from the electricity network). As a result, when wanting to compare attributes whose statistics are published under different geographies for the same area, difficulty arises. Therefore, the LEAR provided the RESO project with a list of mappings of LSOAs to primary substations. This is useful for broad analysis, however, it should still be treated with caution as the LSOAs do not map one-to-one to a primary substation. E.g. there are 201 LSOAs in the RESO area but 425 LSOA to primary mappings. It should also be noted due to methodological differences, the primary boundaries drawn by ESC do not always match the shapefiles that can be downloaded from WPD.
Publisher	ESC
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/2w8x8/mappings-for-UOBDC-lear-supplementary-primary-areas-allocated-to-each-primary-substation-by-esc
Source	ESC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry; 2020
Rights	ESC, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project.

10 SOCIOECONOMIC

10.1 UOBDC-SOC-001: 2011 Census data

Title	2011 Census data
Creator	ONS
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Population; Demographics; Health; Building Type; Tenure; Domestic; Employment; Vehicles; Commute Data; Heat; Local Authority Level; MSOA Level; LSOA Level; OA Level; Postcode District Level; Postcode Sector Level; Anonymised Individual Records; Interactive Map
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-001: The census has been conducted in the UK in ten year intervals since 1801 (except for 1941). Initially its primary purpose was purely the counting of population, but over the years the number and detail of questions have evolved such that the census is now seen by various government departments as a vital tool to help decision making on matters of planning, health, education and transport.</p> <p>Although the next census is scheduled for March 2021, the data will not be released until March 2023, so the most recent available data is from 2011 (published in 2013) which used the following household questionnaire.</p> <p>https://www.ons.gov.uk/census/censustransformationprogramme/census2021milestones</p> <p>https://census.ukdataservice.ac.uk/use-data/censuses/forms.aspx</p> <p>Census data covers a range of topics such as: the number, ages and relationships of people within a household, the type of building, type of and number of rooms (e.g. bedrooms), tenure, car ownership, central heating system, ethnicity, country of birth, language, religion, employment status, place and nature of employment, method of commute, level of education, self-description of health and disability status, whether the resident is an unpaid carer or if this is not their permanent address (such as a holiday home or student residence in term time). Some of these parameters provide direct and indirect insight into the energy characteristics of an area. The immediately useful information would be that related to the buildings themselves such as the central heating system and type of house (e.g. terraced, semi-detached or detached) which has a clear impact on their energy demand. However beyond this, the various other topics can also potentially infer the energy demands of small areas. In the case of Coventry, the age and student household data, could identify areas where the power demand will have additional variations in its seasonality or profile across the working day. On the other hand, the tenure data could be useful for locating clusters of social housing, where a program of retrofit or renewable generation might impact the electrical system, or finding eligible applicants to schemes such as the Green Homes Grant. Furthermore, the commute and vehicle ownership data can be helpful for understanding the transport component of the local energy demand, which will become more important for energy system planners as electricity displaces petroleum based liquid fuels. Data quality issues and levels of confidence for various metrics are discussed in the following link:</p> <p>https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20160108085257/http://www.ons.gov.uk/ons/guide-method/census/2011/census-data/2011-census-user-guide/quality-and-methods/assessing-accuracy-of-responses--census-quality-survey-/index.html</p>

In order to protect participant confidentiality, individual responses are never made available to the public or even ONS accredited secure researchers. As a result, these statistics are aggregated to various geographies before being released and most commonly given in terms of output areas (OAs), small statistical regions used by the ONS. OAs can agglomerate into LSOAs (lower super OAs), MSOAs (middle super OAs) and local authorities, each step following a many-to-one mapping. However, the OA boundaries themselves can change between censuses, so care must be taken in this regard. Other geographical levels available for most statistics include council ward, parish, parliamentary constituency or postcode area/sector/district (e.g. CV, CV1 and CV1 1). There are many platforms on which census data can be visualised and/or downloaded. The Nomis website provides an extensive list of the following relevant categories of datasets: Key/Quick Statistics, Local/Detailed Characteristics, Out of Term Time/Workday/Workplace Population, Origin-Destination Data and (Full) Postcode Headcount and Household Estimates. These datasets all have a code; for example, KS403EW indicates Key Statistic dataset 403 (Rooms, bedrooms and central heating) with coverage for England and Wales. The lists under each heading can be viewed, then queried as per the other Nomis data (e.g. BRES), to be downloaded at the required geographical level and coverage. A link to a user guide can be found on the right hand side of the page, as well as links to Scottish and Northern Irish census data (since most Nomis collections cover England and Wales only, except for those with UK at the end of the code). One main variation in the types of dataset is whether they are univariate (i.e. measure one variable) or cross tabulate two or more variables (e.g. Car or van availability by sex and by age). It follows that the multivariate datasets will have more potential for disclosure as increasing the number of variables will decrease the population size for each bin in a geographical area. Therefore, they are typically only available at a higher geography such as MSOA level or above.

All the aforementioned datasets are publicly available to be downloaded, although more secure and safeguarded de-identified microdata (at either household or individual level) is available through the Secure Researcher Service and UK Data Service.

<https://www.ons.gov.uk/census/2011census/2011censusdata/censumicrodata>

However, to prevent disclosure, these records have had their addresses removed and are only geographically tagged by their local authority (with some smaller local authorities merged to ensure a sufficiently large sample population). To view the safeguarded records an application must be made through the UK Data Service (for which anyone can register) but the secure data can only be accessed by an ONS Accredited Researcher via the Secure Researcher Service. The safeguarded data gives only 5% of anonymised individual responses while the secure data gives up to 10% of individual and household responses while maintaining confidentiality. The UK Data Service also gives other links for exploring the 2011 census.

<https://census.ukdataservice.ac.uk/get-data/explore-online.aspx>

Despite the routes to access this microdata, there does not appear to be a way to find out non-personal responses at a sub-OA level. More granular information on relevant topics for energy researchers (particularly central heating, tenure, vehicle ownership) would be very useful at a postcode level or below (ideally at household and linked to UPRN). As long as the appropriate procedures are in place to protect personal data, through secure and safe access procedures, then this could add value to the design of smart local energy systems. Since although the publicly available OA data usually works well for primary substation level analysis (as they can be mapped in a many-one fashion without losing too much accuracy), if an LV substation area is to be analysed, then the

	<p>uncertainties will be too large to produce meaningful estimates for a given parameter of the domestic properties served by that network asset. Also, there may be a precedent; if population has already been aggregated to a postcode level, then it would seem that, for example, the number of cars/vans or gas heated properties could be too. Furthermore, if household level EPC data is deemed to be non-personal, then it would seem a similar argument could be made for parameters such as these.</p> <p>The census data is also available to be downloaded for universities through the EDINA Digimaps platform, where it can be visualised on an interactive map to an OA granularity (https://digimap.edina.ac.uk/society). The maps also contain data from Ofcom and the University of Liverpool on superfast broadband availability and internet user classifications. For those without an EDINA subscription, DataShine is another tool developed by UCL (https://doi.org/10.1080/17445647.2015.1060183) where rich 2011 census data can be nicely visualised on an interactive map (https://datashine.org.uk/).</p>
Publisher	Nomis; ONS; UCL
Contributor	
Date	2013
Type	dataset; image
Format	xls; csv; tsv; html
Identifier	https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/census/2011
Source	ONS; 2011 Census
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2011. Updated every 10 years.
Rights	<p>Nomis/Datashine: Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/</p> <p>Digimaps: non-public data, only for institutions subscribed to EDINA.</p> <p>Microdata: non-public data, only for ONS accredited researchers and subject to application.</p>

10.2 UOBDC-SOC-002: WPD social indicator mapping

Title	WPD social indicator mapping
Creator	WPD; CSE
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Demographics; Health; Welfare; Fuel Poverty; Heat; Energy Efficiency; Off-gas Properties; Local Authority Level; LSOA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-002: The social indicator mapping project was a collaboration between WPD and the Centre for Sustainable Energy which aimed to use various datasets to gain a deeper insight into the nature, scale and distribution of their customers' vulnerabilities. The methodology report and list of data sources (most of which are publicly available and alluded to in this catalogue) are also able to be accessed on the page. The sources used are the ONS, BEIS, MHCLG, 2011 Census, CDRC, Ofcom, DWP Stat Xplore and Xoserve.</p> <p>The interactive map allows users to bring up a colour-coded layer based on the following percentage metrics at a local authority or LSOA geography: priority service register (PSR) customers (actual and eligible), young and elderly residents, fuel poverty, off gas properties, EPC rating E and below (total and only those with all electric heating), carless households, lone pensioners/parents, access to high speed broadband and various health/disability/benefit criteria. When clicking on a local authority/LSOA, its population, number of fuel poor households and estimated PSR gap (difference between the actual records and eligible households) are displayed. The data for the entire region at LSOA granularity is downloadable as an exported csv. Finally, by selecting the respective options, on and off gas postcode centroids within an LSOA may be displayed, as well as community energy groups (based on data from Regen).</p>
Publisher	WPD
Contributor	
Date	2019
Type	dataset; image
Format	csv; html
Identifier	https://www.westernpower.co.uk/customers-and-community/priority-services/social-indicator-mapping
Source	ONS; 2011 Census; BEIS; MHCLG; CDRC; Ofcom; DWP; Xoserve
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Entire WPD network. Timeframe is 2011-2019.
Rights	Public data, WPD. https://www.westernpower.co.uk/open-data-licence

10.3 UOBDC-SOC-003: English Indices of Deprivation (IMD) 2019

Title	English Indices of Deprivation (IMD) 2019
Creator	MHCLG
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Demographics; Health; Income; Fuel Poverty; Interactive Map; LSOA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-003: The Indices of Deprivation, also sometimes called Indices of Multiple Deprivation (IMD), are a set of metrics for quantifying the level of deprivation in an area. All 32,844 LSOAs in England are ranked from 1-32,844 based on their score, with LSOAs often being classified in deciles 1-10 from most deprived to least deprived. The weighted index is based on the following parameters: income (22.5%), employment (22.5%), education (13.5%), health (13.5%), crime (9.3%), barriers to housing (9.3%) and living environment (9.3%).</p> <p>https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/833959/loD2019_Infographic.pdf</p> <p>File 1 on the webpage for this dataset gives the IMD rank and decile for each LSOA grouped by local authority. This can also be visualised and compared with 2015 and 2010 data through an interactive map made by CDRC:</p> <p>https://maps.cdrc.ac.uk/#/geodemographics/imde2019/default/BTTTTFFT/10/-0.1500/51.5200/</p> <p>Other files on this page include a frequently asked questions document and data for each LSOA by its rank for each deprivation determining parameter (File 7).</p>
Publisher	MHCLG
Contributor	
Date	2019
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/english-indices-of-deprivation-2019
Source	MHCLG
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	England. Timeframe is 2019. Updated every 4-5 years.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

10.4 UOBDC-SOC-004: Approximated social grade (Household Reference Persons)

Title	Approximated social grade (Household Reference Persons)
Creator	Market Research Society
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Demographics; Income; Fuel Poverty; Local Authority Level; MSOA Level; LSOA Level; OA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-004: This dataset is hosted by the UK Data Service and based on data from the 2011 ONS census which has been used by the Market Research Society to infer social class. The social classes are defined as those introduced by the National Readership Survey over 50 years ago: A, upper middle class; B, mid-middle class; C1, lower-middle class; C2, skilled working class; D, working class and E non-working (http://www.nrs.co.uk/nrs-print/lifestyle-and-classification-data/social-grade/). It is often argued that these may be outdated and another classification has been proposed in 2013 by Savage et al which introduces groups such as the precariat and emergent service workers.</p> <p>https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/0038038513481128</p> <p>For each LSOA the number of household reference persons is given along with the number of A/B, C1, C2 and D/E household reference persons. A household reference person is essentially a more modern version of the 'head of the household', so an individual adult member of the household is chosen as a reference point for characterising a household.</p> <p>These types of statistics can be useful for energy analysis because, in general, more affluent households will be more likely to be early adopters of low carbon technologies, particularly electric vehicles. Such inferences could form part of the methodology for future projected EV numbers in WPD's DFES and Regen's NZSW.</p>
Publisher	ONS; UK Data Service
Contributor	
Date	2018
Type	dataset
Format	csv; txt
Identifier	https://www.statistics.digitalresources.jisc.ac.uk/dataset/approximated-social-grade-household-reference-persons-2011
Source	ONS; 2011 Census
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2018. Updated every 10 years.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

10.5 UOBDC-SOC-005: Sub-regional fuel poverty data 2020

Title	Sub-regional fuel poverty data 2020
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Fuel Poverty; Local Authority Level; LSOA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-005: This dataset contains the percentage of households living in fuel poverty down to an LSOA granularity (as well as figures for devolved nations/English regions, counties, local authorities and parliamentary constituencies). The UK government uses the low income, high costs indicator of fuel poverty which means a household is in fuel poverty if it has above average fuel bills which when subtracted from its income would leave it below the national poverty line. However, since this definition neglects people with slightly below average bills but a low income, it is likely the true numbers suffering the effects of energy deprivation are much greater. Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland use the '10% indicator', meaning a household is in fuel poverty if it spends more than 10% of its income on fuel and the remaining income is "insufficient to maintain an adequate standard of living".</p> <p>https://www.eas.org.uk/en/uk-fuel-poverty_50535/</p> <p>Further resources on fuel poverty can be found on the website of National Energy Action.</p> <p>https://www.nea.org.uk/professional-advice-workers/</p> <p>Fuel poverty considerations can be of use when identifying areas to prioritise for energy efficiency improvement grants or connection to a low-cost district heat network.</p>
Publisher	BEIS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/sub-regional-fuel-poverty-data-2020
Source	BEIS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2018. Updated annually.
Rights	<p>Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0.</p> <p>https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/</p>

10.6 UOBDC-SOC-006: Income estimates for small areas 2018

Title	Income estimates for small areas 2018
Creator	BEIS
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Income; MSOA Level
Description	UOBDC-SOC-006: This dataset by the ONS lists estimates for the incomes of households in 2018 using four different metrics at MSOA level for England and Wales. The four metrics are: total annual income, net annual income and net annual income (equivalised) before housing costs and after housing costs. These are explained on the metadata tab of the excel sheet, but essentially total income is that received before tax and net is that after tax and payments to pension funds and external dependants. An equivalence scale is then used to proportion the household income to the needs of its inhabitants based on numbers and ages (http://www.oecd.org/els/soc/OECD-Note-EquivalenceScales.pdf), and finally essential housing costs (e.g. rent, home insurance, water rates, and mortgage payments, although notably neither electricity nor gas bills) are subtracted from this to give the fourth and final metric. In combination with other datasets in this section, this information could be used to gauge the appetite or ability of consumers to directly pay or self-fund aspects of the decarbonised energy system.
Publisher	Nomis; ONS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xls; csv
Identifier	https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/earningsandworkinghours/datasets/smallareaincomeestimatesformiddlelayersuperoutputareasenglandandwales
Source	ONS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	England and Wales. Timeframe is 2018. Updated every 2 years.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

10.7 UOBDC-SOC-007: DWP Benefits, Jobseekers Allowance and Claimant Counts

Title	DWP Benefits, Jobseekers Allowance and Claimant Counts
Creator	ONS; DWP
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Demographics; Income; Health; Welfare; LSOA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-007: This data is hosted by Nomis, a labour market statistics service of the ONS. In terms of data related to welfare recipients, there are three data sets of interest: Department for Work and Pensions (DWP) Benefits (discontinued in 2019), Job Seekers Allowance and Claimant Counts. The DWP Benefits section offers data on benefits such as employment support allowance, incapacity benefit/severe disablement allowance, income support, job seekers allowance, disability living allowance, pension credit and the state pension, either at a higher geography (local authority) with more filters (e.g. age, benefit combination and duration of claim) or a smaller geography (LSOA) with less filters. To access the LSOA data, the chosen benefit for small area datasets must be selected. The reason for the discontinuation of these statistics are unclear, but it could be due to the replacement of some of these benefits with universal credit and the DWP now having their own Stat-Xplore service. This platform is free to sign up for to access data for 16 benefit programmes and in future will provide a wider set of DWP data.</p> <p>https://stat-xplore.dwp.gov.uk/webapi/jsf/login.xhtml</p> <p>Job Seekers Allowance statistics specifically concern those claiming unemployment related benefits and the granularity is at an LSOA level. The data for claimants is broken down by variables such as previous occupation and reason for beginning or ceasing a claim. There are also datasets on the flow and off-flow of claimant numbers, as well as seasonally adjusted data. Finally, the Claimant Count data is similar to the Job Seekers Allowance data but with less options to break down recipients into groups, although it has the advantage of being a better indicator for the number of people claiming because of being out of work. This is because it also includes universal credit recipients who are required to seek work. All of these datasets could be another metric for assessing the energy vulnerability of an area or entitlement to support residents with energy bills or energy efficiency improvements.</p>
Publisher	Nomis; ONS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xls; csv; tsv
Identifier	https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/query/select/getdatasetbytheme.asp?theme=35
Source	DWP
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2002-2018. DWP data discontinued 2019.

Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/
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10.8 UOBDC-SOC-008: Mid-2018 Lower layer Super Output Area population estimates

Title	Mid-2018 Lower layer Super Output Area population estimates
Creator	ONS
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Demographics; Population; LSOA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-008: This data from the ONS gives mid-year population estimates for LSOAs in England and Wales. There is a separate dataset for small area population statistics of Scotland.</p> <p>https://www.nrscotland.gov.uk/statistics-and-data/statistics/statistics-by-theme/population/population-estimates/2011-based-special-area-population-estimates/small-area-population-estimates</p> <p>It is released every year and based on models which use the recorded data from the 2011 census as a baseline. The file is an excel file with tabs for the resident population of all persons, males and females, broken down by age in intervals of one year from 0 to 90+. There is also a tab for the median age of each LSOA and a link to the methodology is provided in the final tab.</p> <p>LSOAs should have a fairly consistent population due to their nature as statically comparative areas; in 2011, 95% of LSOAs had a population between 1,157 and 2,354.</p> <p>https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationestimates/bulletins/2011censuspopulationandhouseholdestimatesforsmallareasinenglandandwales/2012-11-23</p> <p>However, due to population movements and differing growth rates, some areas of the country will increase their number of residents a lot more than others in the ten years between each census. In terms of energy data, it can be useful (alongside other datasets) for predicting the demands of households which may vary based on their population features, both in terms of numbers and age demographics.</p>
Publisher	ONS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationestimates/datasets/lowersuperoutputareamidyearpopulationestimates
Source	ONS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	England and Wales. Timeframe is mid-2019. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

10.9 UOBDC-SOC-009: Population projections for local authorities

Title	Population projections for local authorities
Creator	ONS
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Demographics; Population; Future Scenarios; Local Authority Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-009: This dataset (2018 based) gives estimated population projections at a local authority level from a baseline of 2018 in one year intervals until 2043. The figures are broken down by male and female, and into 5 year age brackets (e.g. 0-4, 5-9 ... 85-89, 90+). The 'Notes and T&Cs' tab gives further details and links to the methodology. Essentially, the projections are based on recent trends (2012-17) for birth, deaths and migration (both internal and international) continuing for the next 25 years. Alternatively, data for other migration scenarios (high international, low international and alternative internal) is also available to download. Returning to the default 2018 based scenario, the variation within the UK is exceptional. For example, Tewkesbury in Gloucestershire is expected to grow 16.4% in population by 2028, whereas the number of residents in Copeland in Cumbria will decline by 3.9% over the same time period.</p> <p>https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationprojections/bulletins/subnationalpopulationprojectionsforengland/2018based</p> <p>It can be useful for energy system projects, in tandem with local plans and DFES projections, as a growing population will lead to an increased base demand for energy (notwithstanding savings from efficiency improvements and electrification). Therefore, areas with a high projected population increase can, in general, be expecting to see more network expansion and/or reinforcement.</p>
Publisher	ONS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xlsx
Identifier	https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationestimates/datasets/lowersuperoutputareamidyearpopulationestimates
Source	ONS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	England and Wales. Timeframe is 2018-2043. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

10.10 UOBDC-SOC-010: Business Register and Employment Survey

Title	Business Register and Employment Survey
Creator	ONS
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Employment; Non-domestic; Local Authority Level; MSOA Level; LSOA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-010: The Business Register and Employment Survey (BRES) is conducted by the ONS and published as part of their Nomis labour market statistics. There are different levels of access for these datasets, open and secure (which has a more accurate level of rounding for small values). Open is available to the public but to access the secure data, one must register for a Nomis account and complete an application.</p> <p>https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/articles/1061.aspx</p> <p>This section will only discuss the open data. For the main BRES data set, selections may be made through the options on the tab at the left hand side of the page. Clicking the 'guide me step-by-step' box above this tab will allow users to be aided through these selections which include geography, date, employment status, industry and percent. Geography lets users select from different sized areas to get the data, from constituent countries of the UK/English regions down to MSOA/LSOA and the dates available are for each year from 2015-19. Employment status gives either the number of employees, part-time employees, full-time employees or those in employment. Part-time and full-time are defined as working either less or more than 30 hours a week, while employment includes employees plus working owners and self-employed people registered for VAT or PAYE. The industry tab allows users to select the industries for which employment statistics will be given. These are broken down according to the Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) codes of 2007.</p> <p>https://www.ons.gov.uk/methodology/classificationsandstandards/ukstandardindustrialclassificationofeconomicactivities/uksic2007</p> <p>These use either letters (A-U) or numerical codes (two to four digit codes beginning with 01-99) to give a description of the economic activity with a more detailed level of description the more digits present; for example section C is for all manufacturing processes, class 24 includes manufacture of basic metals and 2452 represents casting of steel. Finally, the percent tab allows the data to be given either as raw numbers or as a percentage of the workforce of the given area. Once all selections are complete, a summary may be reviewed, the layout chosen (including format, usually .csv or .xls) and data downloaded. Other datasets available, which follow a similar selection/download procedure are available for the public/private sector employment split, as well as both this and the main BRES dataset but excluding PAYE only registered units.</p> <p>In terms of energy planning, these statistics can be useful to determine the types of sectors represented and activities taking place within the non-domestic building stock of an area. Employment based energy consumption mapping is an established method which has been used by Ricardo Energy & Environment in their support for BEIS published statistics.</p> <p>https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/719075/Employment_based_energy_consumption_.pdf</p> <p>This basis for an analysis, rather than using metered gas or electricity consumption, meant that fuels such as petroleum products and coal were able to be disaggregated</p>

	into more sectors than just domestic vs. non-domestic (e.g. commercial, industrial and public sector). An attempt to replicate this breakdown by sector, but for gas and electricity was deployed in the RESO Local Sankey Diagram Methodology (Localised Sankey Diagram methodology: Coventry City Council area (link not yet publicly available)). The document explains the calculations in detail, but essentially the rate of employment in each sector for a local authority was assumed to be proportional to its share of the UK energy consumption for that sector (accounting for population). In addition, the granular BRES data could be used in combination with Energy Consumption in the UK, particularly the end use tables, to produce estimates for the fuels used for different purposes in various manufacturing industries (by apportioning them down from the national employment figure for that sector). BEES could also be used to make similar estimates for the service sector. It should also be noted that these figures can evolve with time should industries leave an area or new ones arrive.
Publisher	Nomis; ONS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xls; csv; tsv
Identifier	https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/query/select/getdatasetbytheme.asp?theme=27
Source	ONS
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Great Britain. Timeframe is 2015-2019. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

10.11 UOBDC-SOC-011: UK Business Counts (Interdepartmental Business Register)

Title	UK Business Counts (Interdepartmental Business Register)
Creator	ONS
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Employment; Non-domestic; Buildings; Building Activity; Local Authority Level; MSOA Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-011: This dataset gives information on either the number of enterprises or local units (e.g. an individual shop or site that belongs to an enterprise, which can also be thought of as a workplace) within a given geographical area. Enterprises may be broken down by turnover or employment size, whereas local units are just broken by the latter. In addition, the SIC code and legal status of the enterprise (e.g. company, non-profit etc.) is also available information. The variable selection and download process is similar to the BRES dataset as it is also hosted on Nomis. However, these datasets can only be downloaded to an MSOA level, rather than LSOA.</p> <p>As with the BRES data, it could be used for inferring energy consumption in the non-domestic sector based on the employment figures and those at national level for the same SIC codes (and then distribute these to the different sized local units). This data also gives an idea of the variation in non-domestic customers, e.g. if there are a few single big employers in an area or lots of small ones. Additionally, it could be a good sense check to compare the number of non-domestic gas or electricity meters with the number of local units. Although this might not be an ideal method, as the meters might not map to the workplaces on a one-to-one basis.</p>
Publisher	ONS
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	dataset
Format	xls; csv; tsv
Identifier	https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/query/select/getdatasetbytheme.asp?theme=49
Source	IDBR
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2010-2020. Updated annually.
Rights	Public data, Open Government Licence v3.0. https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence/version/3/

10.12 UOBDC-SOC-012: Mosaic by Experian (consumer segmentation)

Title	Mosaic by Experian
Creator	Experian
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Demographics; Consumer Segmentation; Postcode Level; UPRN Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-012: Experian provides a commercial service in which it maps households to one of 67 household types built using governmental and commercial sources of data. These household types are then aggregated into 15 groups or disaggregated into 141 person types. By profiling households and their occupants at a granular geography, it could be possible to gain insight into the energy consumption patterns of small areas (https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/kvqnv/common-energy-datasets).</p> <p>As with their competitor Acorn, the data is largely based on a combination of private and public sector sources, such as the ONS and surveys conducted by the University of Essex, YouGov, GfK NOP, BMRB and Research Now.</p> <p>https://www.experian.co.uk/assets/business-strategies/brochures/Mosaic%2520UK%25202009%2520brochure%5B1%5D.pdf</p> <p>In terms of access, there does not seem to be a readily available sample or option to create an account on their website. However, it is possible to get in touch and request a demo or quotation, with potentially different licences depending on the intended use (commercial vs non-commercial).</p>
Publisher	Experian
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	unknown
Identifier	https://www.experian.co.uk/business/marketing/segmentation-targeting/mosaic/
Source	Experian; University of Essex; YouGov; GfK; NOP; BMRB; Research Now
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2021.
Rights	Experian, non-public data, commercial licence required.

10.13 UOBDC-SOC-013: Acorn by CACI (consumer segmentation)

Title	Acorn by CACI
Creator	CACI
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Demographics; Consumer Segmentation; Postcode Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-013: Acorn is a powerful consumer classification that segments the UK population. By analysing demographic data, social factors, population and consumer behaviour, it provides precise information and an understanding of different types of people. They aim to provide valuable consumer insight helping organisations target, acquire and develop profitable customer relationships and improve service delivery (https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/kvqnv/common-energy-datasets). There are 62 types in total, split into a classification hierarchy of 6 categories and 18 groups. Based predominantly on the age, income and type of housing in postcode, a full list of these can be found in their publicly available user guide (https://acorn.caci.co.uk/downloads/Acorn-User-guide.pdf).</p> <p>Details on their methodology, sources and how the data is kept up-to-date are found under the 'What is Acorn?' tab, as well as an Acorn Knowledge excel sheet which can be accessed without signing up. The data is predominantly derived from a combination of open data, government data, commercial data and their own proprietary data sets (for example, major online property sites can be used as a source to gain insight into the private rental market of a given geographical area). By registering for an account, for only personal or academic research use, it is possible to obtain a sample classification of a postcode. This process is repeatable, so could theoretically be used to manually obtain data for an entire area. Although a bespoke quotation for a list of all the postcodes and their Acorn types in a geographic area could be prepared via enquiry, with different terms for commercial and non-commercial intended use. Through this sample access, the full list of Acorn types can also be viewed and sorted by various characteristics such as family structure, housing type, community engagement and consumer behaviour, either as a single search (where each type is given a score for that characteristic relative to a typical index of 100), or as two variables plotted against one another.</p>
Publisher	CACI
Contributor	
Date	2021
Type	dataset
Format	unknown
Identifier	https://acorn.caci.co.uk/
Source	CACI. Combination of open/government/commercial datasets.
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2021.
Rights	CACI, non-public data, commercial licence required.

	<p>Sample postcode level data may be accessed via sign up. https://www.caci.co.uk/legal</p>
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10.14 UOBDC-SOC-014: Food projects & Growing spaces

Title	Food projects & Growing spaces
Creator	CCC
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Community Projects; Health; Food Poverty; Interactive Map
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-014: This interactive map of Coventry has been made by the council to display food projects, growing spaces, parks and partnerships. The layers include: the wards of Coventry City Council, allotments, community projects, educational resources, foodbanks/emergency food, food partnerships, social supermarkets/grub hubs and parks/open spaces. It is non-downloadable but presumably some GIS data must underpin the map, so could be made available on request to the council.</p> <p>Although not directly related to energy, it can provide insight into vulnerabilities and community schemes with potential for positive impacts on decarbonisation and the environment (e.g. localising food production and promoting biodiversity).</p>
Publisher	CCC
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	image
Format	html
Identifier	not publicly available
Source	CCC
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	Coventry. Timeframe is 2020.
Rights	CCC, non-public data, only for internal use within the RESO project. Presumably to be made public at a later date.

10.15 UOBDC-SOC-015: Understanding Net Zero: A Consumer Perspective

Title	Understanding Net Zero: A Consumer Perspective
Creator	ESC
Subject	Socioeconomic Data; Domestic; Heat; Transport; Low Carbon Technologies; Consumer Behaviour; CO ₂ Emissions Data; National Level
Description	<p>UOBDC-SOC-015: This report was based on the findings of a survey designed by the ESC and carried out by ISPOS Mori with over 2000 responses. The aim of the survey was to assess people's attitude towards climate change. For example, how much of a threat it is, what actions should individuals/government take and, at a household level, what activities are perceived as most responsible for climate change? The main findings are displayed on the webpage and the full report can be downloaded upon signing up. One key takeaway is that people tend to underestimate the contribution of gas central heating towards climate change; only 49% see that action as contributing to climate change despite it being the largest single source of household emissions (31%). Moreover, less than 20% of respondents would consider switching to low carbon heating, compared to 34% who said they would fly less often; when flying only contributes to 12% of a household's emissions. Understanding these statistics, the reasons behind them and seeking to alleviate concerns, such as the ones ESC have also investigated in another study on improving the appeal of heat pumps (https://es.catapult.org.uk/reports/decarbonising-heat-understanding-how-to-increase-the-appeal-and-performance-of-heat-pumps/), are necessary challenges for any local authority or community group seeking to promote the decarbonisation of an area.</p>
Publisher	ESC
Contributor	
Date	2020
Type	text
Format	pdf
Identifier	https://es.catapult.org.uk/reports/net-zero-a-consumer-perspective/
Source	ESC; Ipsos Mori
Language	en-GB
Relation	
Coverage	UK. Timeframe is 2020.
Rights	ESC, public data (via sign up). https://es.catapult.org.uk/terms-and-conditions/